

**AN ETHNOGRAPHY OF THE SOCIAL
CONSTRUCTION OF HEGEMONIC MASCULINITY
WITHIN A SCOTTISH PROFESSIONAL FOOTBALL
CLUB**

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Abstract

Whilst much writing has been undertaken on the construction of the idealised form of masculinity via the strictly gendered sport of football very little has been written on the process, dynamics, demonstration and reinforcement of this construction within the often impenetrable and restrictive world of the institution of Scottish professional football. Whilst professional football continues to be associated with traditional working-class masculine values, where a career as a professional footballer has long been regarded as a highly sought after occupation, this study set out to uncover the key features of masculine construction present within the lives of a specific cohort of male professional youth players aged 16–18 within Burncastle Football Club, a professional football club in Scotland. Conducted over a football season utilising an ethnographic methodology via participant observation and 15 semi structured interviews, the study utilised Connell's theoretical concept of 'hegemonic masculinity' to describe and categorise the process and artefacts employed within the football club that conspired to socialise men into this narrow form of idealised masculinity.

The study describes the discourses evident throughout the club that defined masculine identity. The study further describes the institutional norms, practices, expectations and characteristics resplendent with imagery of the idealised man prevalent within the team that ensured that football retained a key position within constructing the idealised form of masculinity and in effect existed as the author describes as a 'school of hegemonic masculinity'.

The findings of the study illustrated the masculine imagery resplendent throughout the club with the 'hard man' being celebrated and idolised in role modelling; and where a culture of toughness and aggression are tolerated and encouraged. The socialisation of these young men into the football culture began at an early age. Male family members supported and encouraged participation into a game where women remained either peripheral, or excluded, and where players openly confirmed their heterosexuality via the objectification and sexualisation of women. The study makes recommendations for future practice and questions the inconsistent nature of the separation of the mens and women games, particularly and especially at a junior and youth level.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Introduction

Several studies, (Connell, 2005, Messner, 1992, Adams, Anderson, & McCormack, 2010) have confirmed that particular types of masculinities are constructed and reconstructed through the institution of sport in general and in particular via physical sports such as football, with the footballer continuing to be perceived as a kind of iconic male (Clark & Paechter, 2007). The professional footballer is instantly recognisable with many commanding salaries of several million pounds per year. It is therefore the goal of many young males to join the ranks of the footballing elite and they will often construct their masculinity around this ambition. Despite a growing involvement of women players, football continues in Scotland to be a highly masculinised sport particularly at elite level with no full time professional women's clubs in existence. This study was conducted within a professional football club playing in the West of Scotland in the 'Burncastle' area.

This chapter begins by firstly providing a context in which the team play by describing the area and within which the club is situated. Additionally, this chapter describes the social, environmental and economic circumstances that exist within the area and where the club draws the majority of its players from. This chapter further provides the background to and a context for the study, whilst also providing an overview of its theoretical basis on masculinity as well as an introduction to the development of Scottish football and wider masculinity within Scottish culture.

Area Profile

In beginning to understand how masculinities were constructed among this group of young male footballers, it is important at this juncture, to explore the geographical area that the club is situated in. This is in order to understand the social structure and the environmental and sociological influences on this construction of masculinities. Whilst exploring and detailing the social environment in which these young players played football and lived in, it will begin to outline the larger social structure of gender relations outlined by Connell (1987) on which this thesis was grounded.

Burncastle, is a town located in the West of Scotland. Slaven (1975) helpfully defines the West of Scotland as the area within the triangle formed by joining Arrochar at the head of Loch Long, Dolphinton on the Eastern rim of Lanarkshire and Ballantrae on the South Ayrshire Coast. Whilst according to Slaven (1975) the area is regularly referred to as the Lowlands, barely half of it lies under 182m. The area itself is relatively small, covering barely 2,500 square miles or around 8% of the Scottish land area. According to Slaven (1975), the region began to prosper after the 1707 union of the Parliament, since the West of Scotland became advantageous for the Atlantic trade including North America and the West Indies, a trade that Scottish merchants has been previously excluded from due to the English navigation acts. Slaven (1975) further points out, that the route from the River Clyde to Virginia for tobacco was the shortest route from any river and port on the British mainland. As Glasgow merchants looked for new cargoes to export during this developing trade route between the Clyde and America, this brought new opportunities for traditional crafts such as woollen goods, linen and leather that were being produced in Ayrshire. As Strawhorn (1975) notes, during the period 1755 to 1811 the County of Ayrshire's population grew from

59,000 to 104,000 as textile mills began to develop across the area including in Kilmarnock and Beith which by 1791 had 5 lint mills and 63 thread makers alone. The Ayrshire region itself began to grow with the establishment of the new town of Catrine on the banks of the River Ayr built solely to accommodate the workers of the new cotton mill (Strawhorn 1975). The rapidly expanding textile industries that included muslins, wool, and printed calicoes were established across the County primarily in order to satisfy the demands of the merchants of Glasgow and Paisley for onward trade across the Atlantic via the River Clyde. In addition, saddlery work also expanded during this time producing boots and shoes, but textiles remained the key industry of the County (Strawhorn 1975). The development of Ayrshire as a key industrial contributor to the growing West of Scotland economy was a significant shift from its mainly agricultural past where most of its inhabitants lived in farm towns with an economy based mainly on subsistence (Strawhorn 1975). Indeed, such was the growth that in the middle of the 18th century there were only three towns in Ayrshire, but less than one hundred years later another ten towns had been established in the County.

The success of the textile industries growth owed much to the geological development of the West of Scotland landscape that formed during the Ice Age (Slaven 1975), where deep valleys formed by the action of small and active streams provided the power that drove the burgeoning textile mills. As these streams bit into the Ayrshire valleys, they uncovered rich coal and iron fields (Slaven 1975). As Slaven (1975), noted the West of Scotland built its industrial success on these natural resources. Hutton (1996) points out however, coal had been mined in Ayrshire for centuries prior to the industrial revolution with monks digging coal for their own use or agricultural

workers supplementing their own income by digging coal for domestic fires. Whilst commercial mining in Ayrshire began in 1684 it was not until around 1840 with the development of new minerals that expanded the iron smelting industry. This coupled with the development of the railways led to a significant expansion of the coal industry the West of Scotland that flourished for around 140 years before ending in the 1980's (Hutton, 1996).

Economically, the industry supports 9,475 full time equivalent jobs and welcomes 4.18 million visitors per year (Ayrshire-arran.org. 2019). With the area being the birthplace of Robert Burns and having three Open Championship venues, and five of the UK's top 100 golf courses (Visit Scotland 2019) it is easy to see why the area makes so much of its tourism credentials. Tourism in the area now accounts for 13% of jobs and is the third biggest employer in the area after the public sector (33%) and retail (15%) (South Ayrshire Community Planning Partnership (2013). This trend for building the tourism industry following deindustrialization appears to be in line with the rest of Scotland. Inglis and Holmes (2003) assert that in 1998, 2 million tourists from outwith the UK spent roughly \$1,340 million on tourism to Scotland, with some 10 million tourists from inside the United Kingdom spending about \$2,200 million on Scottish holidays.

Politically, the Burncastle area of Scotland in which the team play has 8 out of the 354 electoral wards that cover the whole of Scotland. Each ward usually elects three or four councillors to represent that area, often referred to as Multi Member Wards. These boundaries are managed and subject to periodical reviews by the Local Government Boundary Commission for Scotland. In 2017, the area itself had a population of

approximately 112,470 with 48% being male and 52% female. The area accounts for around 2% of the Scottish population and has the 19th highest of all 32 council areas in Scotland. Life expectancies in 2011 were at 77.3 years for males and 81.2 years for females, and were higher than the Scottish average of 76.6 years for males and similar to the Scottish female average of 80.8 years. (Scottish Government 2017). The area has often been thought of as affluent. Indeed in 2012, the area had one of the highest income of households in Scotland with median income per week of £559.80 (Scottish Government 2018) but this is changing across a number of measures. Notwithstanding this general trend, there are some significant pockets with higher levels of deprivation which are often characterised by poorer outcomes. As Phillips (2013) notes, the lost industrial employment of the area resulted in painful social consequences. As The Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) illustrates, 19 data zones in the Burncastle area fall within Scotland's 15% most deprived. Six data fall within the worst 5% in Scotland.

In summary, therefore, Burncastle exhibits all the characteristics of a traditional working class area with a rich vibrant mining history. Within working class mining communities, football was embraced and played a significant role in these communities (Metcalf, 1988). With the decline in heavy industry, the area now exhibits several significant social deprivation characteristics, such as high levels of illicit drug use, high levels of death related to heart disease and high levels of crime (Scottish Public Health Observatory 2017). It is against this background of social deprivation and industrial decline that Burncastle draws its players. As Agergaard and Sørensen (2009) highlighted, football in particular tends to attract its players from predominantly working class areas. In expanding on this Agergaard and Sørensen

(2009) note that the potential for a high salary is one of the reasons that working class men are attracted to the game but more than that it provides an opportunity for upward social mobility, an opportunity to move away from the challenges and hardships that working class areas can present for some. Whilst Burncastle Football club has never played in Scotland's Premier League, with football being embedded in young working class men from an early age by relatives and peers (McGillivray, Fearn, and McIntosh 2005) it offers obvious opportunities for this social upward mobility. Despite the high attrition rate prevalent with football it remains an opportunity for young men to improve their status and achieve a celebrity profile (McGillivray, et al, 2005).

Researcher profile

I note later in this thesis the importance of reflexivity as part of the social research process. In particular the need for personal reflexivity and the crucial role that life stories play within reflexivity (Norton 2017). Not only is this personal reflection crucial but according to Lichterman (2017) it is now conventional since the narrative tells the reader who the author is and how that might matter for the study at hand. Lichterman (2017) suggests that reflexivity is performed in a preface or introductory chapter. This early performance of reflexivity demonstrates and illustrates that knowledge claims are conditioned and partial.

As long as I can remember I have participated in football either as a participant or spectator. One of my first memories of football as a young child was the joy in my household when my team achieved the pinnacle of European football by winning Europe's premier cup competition surrounded by extended family and friends crowded

around a small rented black and white television or the feeling of despair among us when losing to a team in a lower league or our closest rivals.

Growing up during the 1960's / 1970's meant that entertainment opportunities were limited particularly in a working class household with a bricklayer as a father and a mother who worked in a shop, what entertainment there was such as cinemas were restricted to irregular treats. Football therefore became the entertainment of choice for myself and my peers. Whilst girls played with skipping ropes, boys played football. No one ever thought to question the convention. Whilst football has worldwide appeal, perhaps in part due to the limited equipment required, when no football was available tennis balls or even tin cans were used. Every second Saturday was eagerly awaited as the males in our family made the pilgrimage to see our heroes in action at home bedecked in club branded hats and scarves whilst the women went shopping. Monday morning often could not come quickly enough as it was an opportunity to discuss the weekend match, debate key incidents and recreate the goals. Even better if one were present at the game since television provided limited coverage and being there allowed an opportunity to describe the atmosphere including the songs and to question referee's decisions. Monday mornings at school were glorious opportunities to be the centre of attention if you were present at the match on Saturday.

At each opportunity at evenings and weekends when we played football we would adopt the persona of our favourite player in the forlorn hope that his name would enhance our skill. However, I very quickly realised that my peers were developing more skill than I and that my ambition to be a professional footballer was never going to be realised. The popular boys in class were those who played football. The same

boys in the school team were the ones also starting to attract the attention of girls. I quickly learned that if you were not able to play football the next best thing was to be knowledgeable about it in order to fit in so I consumed as much football as I could, collecting football cards (with bubble gum) learning about players, pestering family members and other adults to take me to games.

With the whole nation united around the national football team for World Cups a knowledge of opponents and their key players and even where a particular country that Scotland were playing was situated geographically and its climate, currency and so on ensured that I was able to continue to fit in. I suppose that helped me realise that I was relatively academic. I knew most of what teachers were asking but being too academic could lead to exclusion from whatever level of peer group inclusion I had earned so academic skill had to be balanced against maintaining peer acceptance. Secondary school was a turning point in my life since physical education (PE) sessions were single gender affairs and consisted of football for boys and netball for girls. With limited ability, the significant focus on football at school forced me to concentrate more on academia and seeking out new relationships. Upon leaving school and having no clear career ambition or plan I decided to pursue a career as a teacher and began studying for a degree in the traditionally feminised profession of primary teaching.

Perhaps it was my working class upbringing but I always had an interest in politics and became active politically initially via single issue pressure groups then a mainstream political party. I abhorred injustice and unfairness and witnessed regular instances of it in the lives of the children that I taught. I therefore decided to pursue a different career in social work/social care working with those individuals who I viewed as

experiencing the most injustice, unfairness and prejudice namely those experiencing challenges with their alcohol use. With several of my family employed in the rapidly declining heavy industry of steel production and the now defunct coal industry, significant use of alcohol was common among several of the older males. I recall attending football matches as a child with these men and alcohol featured heavily before, during and after games. I was always intrigued as to why sport so heavily promoted as healthy should be so inexorably linked with the heavy use of alcohol. In keeping with the general inductive approach adopted as part of this thesis where “the researcher begins with an area of study and allows the theory to emerge from the data” (Strauss and Corbin, 1998 p 12), alcohol became an artefact utilised within the wider construction of gender identity that became the focus of this study. It was given the implicit place that alcohol had and continues to have with football and the link that alcohol and in particular heavy use of alcohol had with being a man that stimulated initial interest in this particular field of study. In exploring further, I began to question why particular activities such as the heavy consumption of alcohol and participating in football are associated with being a man.

To this day, I maintain an interest in football. As my close friends also share this, football is a main part of our conversation. Fortunately age has now determined that skill in playing the game is no longer required in order to ‘fit in’ and gain acceptance with a peer group however being able to talk about the game, being able to analyse tactics and performance and, where possible attend matches remains important to some men. It is this realisation that football remains important to some men throughout their lives that has led to the development of this study. The legendary Scottish football manager Jock Stein who not only led Glasgow Celtic to a world record nine league

titles in a row but managed Glasgow Celtic to become the first British Club to win the European Cup in 1967 is alleged to have once said that football without fans is nothing. I have come to the conclusion that he could also have said that men without football are nothing.

Football in Scotland

There is no doubt that football continues to remain central to sport in Scotland and Scottish society, with attendances at Scottish football stadia some of the highest ever recorded in the history of the game. The 1969-70 European cup semi-final at Hampden Park attracted a record 136,505 spectators. The 1937 Scotland v England attendance of 149,415 remains a European record attendance, and the 1937 Scottish Cup final between Celtic and Aberdeen remains a European record for a club match with 146,433 spectators in attendance (Bradley 1995). Even in the midst of a global economic downturn as well as a range of other leisure activities available to the consumer, nearly 4.5M watched Scottish Premier League (SPL) and Scottish Football league (SFL) clubs in season 2009-10 (McLeish 2010). Indeed, for seven successive seasons total league attendances have been over 4M. With a population approximately one eleventh of England and Wales, Scotland attracts one seventh of the total league figures south of the border. Expressing these attendances as a percentage of the population, SPL attendances are around 70%, the English Premiership just over 25% (Ross, 2005). Whilst attendances are spread among all Scottish football clubs, Scottish football has a long history of domination by two clubs, Celtic and Rangers. On only 18 occasions since the first season of Scottish league football in 1890/1891 has a club other than Celtic or Rangers been crowned champions of the top division. (Adams, Morrow & Thomson, 2017)

Masculinity – An overview

In examining masculinity (and femininity) it is important first of all to begin with an understanding of gender since gender construction is fundamental to the construction of our sexual identity. It is easy to accept that gender identity is fixed since we often take it for granted believing that we are able to automatically recognise gender. In fact we order and live our lives around the belief that gender is easily recognised and easy to understand.

For example, we take for granted the fact that conventional marriage requires a male and female, men's shirts button to the opposite side from women's. We even have separate shops in which to buy these shirts. We dress baby boys in blue and our baby girls in pink. We have different toys as we grow up and are even directed towards different styles of music based on our gender. We accept these distinctions almost without thought or question. We believe and accept that gender distinction is natural and that men and women are different.

However, if we examine the development of gender and scratch below the surface we begin to discover an almost insidious side to its acceptance. Believing that men are different from women in all ways helps us to accept the significant imbalances that exist between men and women.

Even those who argue for greater equality for women seem to accept the natural order of gender difference by calling for increased participation of women in business (or politics) since a woman's empathetic personality trait or relationship personality trait may bring benefits to the business or the organisation that a man could not (Connell

2009). Research in fact demonstrates this not to be true with women in senior positions behaving similarly to men in senior positions (Connell 2009). Furthermore, significant research exists beginning around 1890, that there are in fact no differences in personality traits, intelligence and so on (Connell 2009). Connell (2009) further notes that every proposed or imagined gender difference has been debunked by research. In fact, this natural order of gender difference only seems to have existed in Europe from the 18th Century since prior to this time women were not seen as a separate gender but as inferior men (Connell 2005, Connell 2009).

In the gender debate, reference is often made to the biology that separates men and women predominantly around sex and gender. As Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013) helpfully note, sex is purely a biological categorisation of humans predominantly based on reproduction whereas gender is the social elaboration of the biological categorisation of sex. In illustrating, this we recall our earlier social differences and further assert that there are no biological explanations why women wear nail polish and men do not. According to Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013), however that whilst we often think of sex as biological and gender as social, or sex as nature and gender as nurture, the distinction, as already referenced and discussed previously is not clear cut. Our discussion above illustrates what Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013) outline as nature and nurture intertwine as they argue that there is no obvious point at which sex leaves off and gender begins since there is no single objective biological criterion for male or female sex. In explanation, Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013) further suggest that the three key criteria for sex assignment (anatomical, endocrinal chromosomal features) are selected based very much on cultural beliefs about what actually makes someone male or female. Thus Eckert and McConnell-Ginet (2013)

conclude that actually the very definition of the biological categories male and female, and people's understanding of themselves and others as male or female, is ultimately social.

In becoming a man, acquiring the gender identity of masculinity (or manliness) is developed through a complex process of interaction with culture and environment that develops and changes as society changes and develops. Masculinity and what defines a man is therefore defined by relationships, experiences, motivations, and feelings. But this gender identity is not simply acquired via societal norms or imposed by cultural influences. We construct ourselves as masculine or feminine by claiming a place within our gender order by the way we conduct ourselves. Therefore in discussing and recognising masculinity as a social construction we recognise that masculinity refers to male bodies but it is not determined by male biology. If masculinity is constructed by ourselves by claiming a place within the gender order by the way in which we conduct ourselves, then it must follow that not everyone will construct the same type of masculinity. The reality is that in constructing our gender identity we develop and combine characteristics of masculinity and femininity (Connell 2009). This would therefore suggest that there is no one form of masculinity and we should therefore utilise the term 'masculinities'.

Indeed, we further know that within the range of masculinities that that we construct for ourselves some masculinities are dominant and others are subordinated or marginalised. (Connell 2000). Within Western culture the most recognised example of subordinated or marginalised masculinity is gay masculinity. However, whilst gay masculinity may be the most widely recognised subordinated masculinity, it is not the

only one. Heterosexual men may also be subordinated and excluded from the recognised legitimacy of masculinity. However heterosexual they are, some masculinities are subordinated to the extent that they are defined by using terms which are demeaning and abusive (geek, mummies boy, nerd, Jessie, wimp, sissy etc) (Connell 2005).

If these masculinities (gay and other males) are subordinated, it follows that there must be a dominant form of masculinity. Within the current Western gender order we define this dominant masculinity as hegemonic since it claims and sustains a leading position in social life (Connell 2005). This form of masculinity is viewed as normative and the most honoured or desired. It embodies what being a man is all about.

Crucially, it is essential to note that hegemonic masculinity is currently the accepted strategy for the defence of patriarchy. If conditions for the defence of patriarchy change, the bases for the dominance of a particular masculinity are eroded, (Connell 2005); however this dominant group will not give up the power and dominance easily.

After the Great War, societies in Western Europe began to challenge the social order and capitalism across Europe began to suffer with the increase in Socialist movements in Russia, Germany and Italy. The rise of Fascism, with its reassertion of male supremacy via its glorification of violence and redefining of masculinity re-established the capitalist gender order. The defeat of Fascism, whilst stopping the insidious glorification of hegemonic masculinity did not alter the reassertion of the dominance of the gender order as the arms race then began across the world as the USA, Russia

and China sought to assert their dominance via the build-up of nuclear arsenals (Connell 2005).

Whilst the social order is maintained via global violence, hegemony often maintains its position via localised violence such as via homophobic attacks, but maintaining this dominance as we have already alluded does not always require violence. With hegemonic masculinity being promoted as the most culturally exalted form of masculinity it may be that the most visible bearers of hegemonic masculinity are not always the most powerful people. They may be film actors, sportsmen or even film characters (Connell 2000). It may not even be that the hegemonic form of masculinity is the most common but even although many men live in a state of tension with the ideal or even remain some distance from it, it does remain the most honoured or desired within the current Western gender order (Connell 2000).

Football and masculinity

Football has been recorded as being played as early as 1500BCE although it appears that this particular form was not as we know it today (Giulianotti 2000). However, a game similar to our current game appears to have been played in China during the Han Dynasty (206BCE – AD220) (Giulianotti 2000), but the game as we know it began to be codified in the nineteenth century as a means of teaching leadership, loyalty and discipline to society's elite. In fact football shared this trait with the development of other sports around this time.

Messner (1992) points to the conscious development of sport in Britain in the 19th and early 20th Century's as a means of preparing boys from the public schools to one day

administer the empire. He further notes that team sports were particularly encouraged as they encouraged loyalty and obedience. Sports were therefore used to develop 'manliness' to administer, rule and dominate colonised peoples (mainly non-whites).

The headmaster of Harrow from 1881 to 1895, the Reverend J.E.C. Welldon is quoted in Messner (1992 p10):

“In the history of the British Empire it is written that England has owed her sovereignty to her sports”

Messner (1992) provides further insight into this historical development of sport where he notes that The Duke of Wellington, a former pupil of Eton College, a British independent school for boys aged 13 to 18 founded in 1440 by King Henry VI, is alleged to have remarked that the battle of Waterloo was won on the fields of Eton although there is no robust verification of this remark. Furthermore, according to Messner (1992) that The Duke had directed in the 1840's that every military barracks, both at home and overseas should have its own cricket ground. Even today according to Messner (1992) that sport continues to be a major feature of Eton. During the Michaelmas half, the sport curriculum is dominated by football and rugby union. During the Lent Half, it is dominated by the Field Game a code of football, but this is unique to Eton and cannot be played against other schools. Aided by AstroTurf facilities on Masters' field, Field Hockey has become a major Lent Half sport. During the Summer Half, there is a division between wet bobs, who row on the River Thames, and dry bobs, who play cricket, tennis or athletics. Dorney Lake, in Buckinghamshire, is owned by the college and hosted the rowing events at the 2012 Summer Olympics. As well

as the Duke of Wellington, Princes William and Harry are Old Etonians. (Messner 1992).

Muscular Christianity

As football developed, each academic institution had its own football rules and two separate camps emerged as to how the game should progress. In one camp sat Rugby and Eton who favoured a game similar to rugby that allowed handling and in the other sat Harrow who did not favour handling. Harrow won out and established the rules of the game in 1854 as the football association was formed. In 1877 the laws of association football were formally codified five years after the first FA cup was played (Giulianotti 2000).

It was not just Rugby, Harrow and Eton that football was played and encouraged. It was encouraged at all the great public schools of England (Eton Winchester, St. Paul's, Shrewsbury, Westminster, Merchant Taylors, Rugby, Harrow, and Charterhouse) (McDonald 2007) to develop 'manly' character and physical fitness, in order to tackle what was perceived at the time to be a real threat to the Empire from other European Countries and America (McDonald 2007). Football however, was not just used for physical fitness in order to develop physically fit defenders of the Empire, it was also used in Victorian England to develop Christian morality (Watson, Weir and Friend 2005). As Parker and Watson (2014) note the regime at Rugby under the leadership of its headmaster Thomas Arnold when he arrived in 1828 specifically utilised sport in conjunction with teaching in the 'Classics' as a means to develop not only manliness but 'Christian Manliness'. This development of Christian morality eventually became a significant important element of football (and other sports) since

Watson et al (2005) note, the well-known authors Thomas Hughes and Charles Kingsley believed that at the time the Anglican Church had become weakened by a culture of effeminacy. This perceived culture of effeminacy was so prevalent that it was believed that many Christian men were preferring to engage in sports rather than attend Church (Bruner 2014). It is perhaps unsurprising then that there was such hostility to sport within Protestantism believing that sport had no spiritual value (Parker and Weir 2012). Kingsley however, according to Watson et al (2005) saw a direct link between 'manliness' and 'godliness' and therefore considered that physical fitness had a spiritual value and therefore sport provided an antidote for this perceived culture of effeminacy prevalent within the Anglican Church at the time.

The ideas of Kingsley and Hughes of sport, spirituality and manliness quickly took hold and such was the influence of these Victorian authors that they became key players in the relationship between sport and religion in the UK (Watson 2011). The influence of Kingsley on Victorian Britain of developing manly character and physical fitness is evidenced by the fact that his novel *Westward Ho!* published in 1855 became a significant tool in the recruitment of men for the Crimea War (Winn 1960). According to Winn (1960) not only did *Westward Ho!* establish Kingsley as a key figure in athleticism and the promotion of manliness, it established Kingsley as the founder of the 'Muscular Christianity' movement which became one of the most influential expressions of the Broad Church movement within Anglicanism. With the central themes of the novels of Kingsley and Hughes resplendent with imagery of high moral values, physical endeavour, Christian manliness, loyalty and self-sacrifice, this Muscular Christianity movement provided the perfect opportunity for those within the Anglican church to reconnect it to its masculinised structures that were being eroded

(Parker and Watson 2014). This reconnection was solidified further by the work of The Cambridge Seven. These Cambridge Seven were, according to Bruner (2014) essentially unremarkable young men who volunteered to travel to China to carry out missionary work as part of the China Inland Mission (CIM). However, what made the Cambridge Seven unique was not just the fact that they were well educated but that they were athletic and represented an idealised masculinity (Bruner 2014). For example, among the seven was C.T Studd who was a first class cricketer who had played for England against Australia (Bruner 2014). Studd, alongside Stanley Smith, a champion rower for Cambridge (Bruner 2014) meant that these 'Muscular Christians' had an immediate impact and appealed to many evangelical Christians who saw Smith and Studd as not only good virtuous Christian men willing to undertake missions to spread the Gospel but 'manly' Christian men (Bruner 2014)

The work of Studd, Smith and others as Muscular Christians firmly established sport within Christianity and as such paved the way for the construction of idealised masculine identity in Britain (Bruner 2014). The terminology however did not sit well with everyone. Whilst Kingsley detested the expression 'Muscular Christianity', (Winn 1960), Thomas Hughes the author of *Tom Browns Schooldays* published in 1857 whom Winn (1960) credits as the author of the most important book ever written about public schools championed it (Winn 1960). As Mathisen (1990) notes, in the follow up to *Tom Browns Schooldays*, *Tom Brown at Oxford* published in 1961, Tom Brown specifically addresses the concept and the 'brotherhood' of muscular Christianity. Such was the reach and impact of *Tom Browns Schooldays* and the popularity of what Redmond (1978) describes as 'the cult of athleticism that a French translation reached a young Baron de Coubertin who made a pilgrimage to Rugby before ultimately

founding the modern Olympic Games. Such was the significance of the works of Kingsley and Hughes combining athleticism and manliness within Christianity, it has led to Tom Brown's Schooldays being described as the 'bible' of Muscular Christianity and Charles Kingsley as its patron saint (Redmond 1978). Indeed, with seventy editions of Tom Brown published during Hughes' lifetime alone and the book seen as the most popular novel of the nineteenth century (MacAloon 2006) it is easy to see why such emphasis was placed upon this work.

Despite the impact of Muscular Christianity on Victorian society, the origins of the term 'muscular Christianity' itself are not as clear as Winn (1960) appears to suggest. Redmond (1978) for example disputes that *Westward Ho!* with its brave, strong, honest and chivalrous protagonist Amyas Leigh as the origin of the term. Redmond (1978) alternatively suggests that the term was in fact first used in a review of Kingsley's novel 'Two Years Ago' published two years after *Westward Ho!* in 1857 with its muscular, broad shouldered and good at all sport protagonist Tom Thurnall. Whenever the term was coined, Redmond (1978) notes that it may have originated as a result of Kingsley and Hughes' participation in the Christian Socialist movement with Hughes being active in teaching boxing and establishing an athletics programme as well as launching a cricket team. As a Christian Socialist, Mathiesen (1990) suggests Hughes' used his 'Muscular Christianity' philosophy in order to improve life in general for the Victorians. Mathiesen (1990) suggests that Hughes viewed Tom Brown as a role model for Victorian boys. This role model with his values of reliance on others and unselfish acts encapsulated via participation in sport anticipated that life in Britain would gradually improve as these lessons would permeate the larger non sport world bringing benefits to all. This Muscular Christianity forged via the medium of football

and other sports was not just restricted to England but became the basis on which Christian morality was brought to Africa and Asia (Mangan 2001). The conquerors of Africa and Asia used football in much the same way that it was used in England. Football taught morality, hard work, loyalty, and obedience as well as the development of manliness (Mangan 2001). All these qualities were a key element in turning the local populations in Africa and Asia from uncivilised to civilised and of course Christian (Mangan 2001).

With over 160 years having passed since the publication of Tom Brown's Schooldays, its legacy remains. The Christian Socialist ideas of its creator Thomas Hughes influenced a movement for social change across the world (Kidd 2006). Missionaries like Theodore Leighton Pennell, who taught football in Afghanistan (Mangan 2001), A.G. Fraser and Cecil Earle Tyndale-Biscoe whom Mangan (2006) describes as the 'ideological heirs' of Hughes were not only bringers of Christianity but were also philanthropic and bringers of trade, winning admiration irrespective of religious affiliations (Mangan 2016). The medium of sport was firmly established across the Empire and the wider world by these Muscular Christian missionaries to teach Christianity. Muscular Christians in Canada for example laid the foundations on which the Canadian publically funded Medicare system was built on (Kidd 2006). Another Canadian, Egerton Ryerson, utilised the ideals of Muscular Christianity, viewing sport as a vehicle for education in citizenship and social responsibility coupled with Christian manliness via a curriculum of cricket and football which became the framework for public education in Canada that was free, universal and compulsory (Kidd 2006).

Purpose of the study

This study examined the construction of masculinity within Scottish professional football. As the main sport in Scotland, the highly masculinised domain of professional football continues to remain a key factor in producing and reproducing masculinities. From an early age, many young boys in Scotland dream of becoming professional footballers. With the preponderance of boys clubs aligned and associated with professional clubs, some young boys will begin this journey at a relatively young age.

Therefore, a young male may spend much of his development as a man (from child to teenager to adult) progressing through a professional football club's system where they can often become influenced by older male adults including coaches and older players. The purpose of this study was therefore to explore the ways in which football contributes to the construction of masculinities for this group of young people.

Significance of the study

This research is important in contributing to the evidence base on how masculinities are constructed among working class men in Scotland since as Holligan (2015) notes by their very nature, working class young men are traditionally subordinated and construct a masculinity associated with toughness and muscularity. With the importance of location in shaping the performance of young men's masculine identity (Ward, Tarrant, Terry, Featherstone, Robb, and Ruxton, 2017), this ethnographic research is conducted within a working class post-industrial community.

The level of interest and engagement in football among the working class has led to Williams (2006) noting that no other organised sport across Scotland and Europe has a greater hold on the time and emotions of the working classes. This research therefore examined how football contributes to a particular construction of gender identity. Given that the subjects of the study are young male professional footballers, this research will further add to the body of literature on how professional athletes construct their masculinities as well as providing an insight into Scottish Professional football. With Dufur (2006) asserting that sport provides a useful arena in which to study gender and society, this study whilst exploring the ways in which masculinity is socially constructed through football also adds to the wider evidence base on gender in society. Dufur (2006) further suggests that as sport has been used by men to separate themselves from women by excluding them from participation by placing an emphasis on strength and physical size, this research further adds to the body of literature on how masculinities are constructed within other highly masculinised sports that have an emphasis on the development of masculine characteristics such as aggressiveness, competitiveness and domination over others. Whilst increasing numbers of women compete in sports, Jakubowska, and Byczkowska-Owczarek (2018) note that there remains a perception that there still are feminine sports and masculine sports; a perception that has remained unchanged since studies began in the 1960's.

As Parker and Manley (2017) note from their research in two English professional football clubs, the organisational culture of professional football is restrictive in nature due to levels of discipline and control imposed. Furthermore, the restrictive nature of football is highlighted by Adams, McCormack and Anderson (cited in Roberts,

Anderson and Magrath (2017 p337) who call it “an impenetrable fortress”. This restrictive culture therefore has the potential to limit research on and with professional athletes. This study therefore further contributes to the literature on gender construction with professional athletes. This thesis is particularly significant therefore given the limited evidence available on professional football players. With a social constructionist perspective supporting a view that gender construction is culturally specific, this thesis takes place in Scotland and will not only provide a further contribution to the evidence base on the lives of Scottish Professional footballer player but specifically will provide an insight into how these young Scottish Professional footballers construct a masculine identity. With McGillivray, et al (2005) recognising that young Scottish players adopt what they describe as an exclusive masculinity by rejecting formal education, this study will explore other masculinities at play within Scottish football as well as the artefacts that the players utilise in the construction of masculinities.

Whilst this study focuses on only one of the 42 professional football clubs playing in Scotland, it seeks to provide insight into the factors and artefacts that are used by professional footballers to construct masculinities. The specific construction of masculinities within this football club could be significant for the wider culture within football and could stimulate further research in this area with other clubs.

Aim

The aim of this research is to explore the social construction of masculinities in the lives of young professional footballers in Scotland within the context of one professional club

Research Questions

1. How are masculinities constructed and performed in the lives of young professional footballers within the context of one professional club?
2. What implications are there in terms of how football contributes to the construction of masculinities in Scotland?

Conclusion

In this introduction I have outlined the theoretical framework on which this thesis is founded, namely the concept of hegemonic masculinity devised by Connell (1987) and reworked and updated by Connell and Messerschmidt (2005). In outlining this theoretical framework, I have explored and critiqued the 'natural order' argument of a dimorphic species of male/female whilst recognising and addressing a particular critique of the theoretical concept of gender itself. In addition, this chapter has outlined the justification for the study and located this justification within the context of the author's own particular interest in the topic and the limited research in the closed institution that is professional football. The next chapter will therefore further expand on the theoretical framework surrounding the nature of gender construction and its relationship with football.

CHAPTER 2: GENDER

Introduction

This thesis began with the assertion that sport and football in particular play a significant role in young males' construction of gender identity and in particular one form of construction, namely hegemonic masculinity. This chapter seeks to further explore the main theoretical framework of masculinities. Additionally, the chapter seeks to explore and explain via examination of academic texts the elements within sport and football that men use to construct this particular narrow form of masculinity. The chapter further develops and supports the argument that sport and in particular football allows for the construction and reconstruction of particular types of masculinities and specifically a narrow idealised hegemonic form of masculinity.

Social Construction of Masculinity

Over the last 25 years there has been a substantial growth in research and theorising on the nature and meaning of masculinity (Ainsworth *et al* 2014). Indeed, such is the interest that Messerschmidt (2012) noted that between 2006 and 2010 there were 540 citations in scholarly academic journals of hegemonic masculinity alone. During this time, much of the feminist and feminist-inspired work on masculinity has concluded that the masculine character is socially constructed rather than biologically given and categorised through the possession of hormonal, physical and genetic features, which through genetic programming leads to certain behavioural traits (Swain 2000). This theoretical conception of masculinity as a social construct owes much to the work of the Australian sociologist Raewyn Connell (1987, 1992, and 2005) and others (Carrigan, Connell, and Lee 1985).

This social constructionist theory of gender, described as the most influential theory in the field of men and masculinities (Wedgwood 2009), suggests that masculinity cannot be reduced simply to the biological body, the psyche, culture, or institutions. It involves all of these, and more (Watson 2015). Rather, masculinity or manliness is developed through a complex process of interaction with culture and environment that develops and changes as society changes and develops. Masculinity and what defines a man is therefore defined by relationships, experiences, motivations, and feelings, but also can be about class, race and ethnicity (Messner, 1992). The complexity of defining such a diverse, mobile and often unstable construction, Benyon (2002) argues that there is therefore not one masculinity but rather multiple masculinities given that different cultures, as well as different time periods, see masculinities constructed in many ways. In addition, more than one form of masculinity can be identified within the same culture. Rather than simply being a diverse plurality of masculinities, Connell (2000, 2005) allows for a theorisation of hierarchies amongst masculinities, with hegemonic masculinity at the fore.

Understanding masculinities in these terms allows us to recognise the relational and hierarchical aspect within these differing constructions of gender. These insights are critical to understanding the complex dynamics of subordination not only of women, but also of men by men who hold power and privilege, and therefore to contribute to a better understanding of male power and the process of subordination (Dowd 2010). These dynamics of subordination help us better understand why, for example, the USA and Russia have never had female heads of state. Connell's term hegemonic masculinity has become a widely used descriptor for this dominant form (or configuration) of masculinity, which is seen to help perpetuate this domination of

masculinity over femininity. With masculinity being as much about relation to other men as it is about relation to women (Dowd 2010), the terms complicit, subordinate and marginalised masculinities are also used to describe other configurations of masculinity, which sit in relation to hegemonic masculinity in the gender hierarchy (Lusher & Robins 2010).

Hegemonic Masculinity

During the 1960's a range of studies began to question the natural facts of belonging to one gender or another (Wedgewood 2009). According to Buschmeyer (2013) this research investigated what is meant by femininity and masculinity if it is not biologically determined. As Connell (1993) notes much of this research was driven by the advent of Women's Liberation movement and another concluding that it is less the body that classifies people as either a man or a woman, but more what people do, how they dress, their facial expressions, and other learned attributes (Buschmeyer 2013). Whilst this early research on masculinities recognised that masculinities were socially constructed, the gender role theory that arose from this research on masculinities was seen as inadequate as it did not account for diversity in masculinities, nor did it account for understanding the power and economic dimensions since it was used to refer to behavioural expectations associated with more or less static social positions (Connell 1987). The inability of sex role theory to account for power and oppression led Connell to theorise the relational concepts of masculinity and femininity which have meaning in relation to each other (Wedgewood, 2009). This work led to the term 'hegemonic masculinity' being first used by Connell in a 1982 publication to describe particular kinds of behaviour which are made culturally dominant and come to be seen as the pattern of masculinity in general (Wedgewood, 2009). Wedgewood (2009) notes that

further research later refined the concept with hegemonic masculinity becoming a culturally exalted form at the top of a hierarchy of masculinities. As Kimmel (1997) succinctly notes, the term 'hegemonic masculinity' is a means to recognising that all masculinities are not created equal. Following critique of hegemonic masculinity, the concept was refined further by Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) and redefined as the pattern of practice (i.e., things done, not just a set of role expectations or an identity) that allows men's dominance over women to continue.

Connell (1987) explains that, whilst only a minority of men may overtly enact this particular masculine characteristic by actively subordinating women, hegemonic masculinity is viewed as normative. It embodies what being a man is all about and, by the portrayal of this normative role it is accepted by women. Kenway & Fitzclarence (1997) describe hegemonic masculinity as the standard bearer of what it means to be a "real" man or boy. It can be viewed as a role, status set, perspective, behaviour or personal characteristic. Although not all hegemonic men include or contain all aspects at once, they may possess particular elements. For example, both a professional athlete and a Chief Executive Officer of a major corporation incorporate differing elements of hegemony. The athlete embodies physical strength, whereas the Chief Executive Officer symbolizes authority and prestige (Ricciardelli, Clow and White 2010). Furthermore, in contemporary Western societies, this hegemonic masculine character typically includes being white, middle-class, a breadwinner or provider as well as being strong, competent, in control, competitive, assertive (if not aggressive), and heterosexual (Grindstaff & West 2011).

Hegemonic masculinity assists in preserving the social order. It is taken as a gender practice that legitimises patriarchy and maintains the dominant position of men and

the subordination of women. Crucially it is essential to note that hegemonic masculinity is the currently accepted strategy for the defence of patriarchy. Whilst the number of men actually actively practicing hegemonic masculinity may be quite small, the majority of men benefit from the patriarchal dividend that it produces via the advantage that men gain from the overall subordination of women (Connell 2005). As Wedgwood (2009) highlights, whilst the concept of hegemonic masculinity is clearly the most popular and influential element of Connell's theory of masculinity, it has also attracted the most criticism.

Critique of Hegemonic Masculinity

The theoretical concept of masculinities devised by Connell (1987, 1995) was revised by Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) following a particular critique of the concept by Demetriou (2001). In his critique of the concept of hegemonic masculinity, Demetriou (2001) does recognise that the notion of hegemonic masculinity was important as it attempted to give an account of what the sex role framework left largely untheorized. Whilst broadly aligned with the theory, Demetriou (2001) however suggests that the original model is over simplified. In seeking therefore to explain and revise the model, Demetriou (2001) identified within hegemonic masculinity two key elements which he described as external hegemony or hegemony over women and internal hegemony described as hegemony over men. Furthermore, Demetriou (2001) questions whether these two forms of hegemony are the same thing, complementary or is one the result of the other? In seeking to understand and further explore the relationships between external and internal hegemony, Demetriou (2001) returns to the originator of the term of hegemony itself, Gramsci, and notes that Gramsci distinguished between leading classes and dominated classes with the leading classes defined as those classes

allied with the leading class and the dominated class defined as those opposed to it. Demetriou (2001) therefore suggests that this aligns with the led group being analogous with internal hegemony and dominated group analogous with external hegemony. Whilst Demetriou (2001) agrees that there is a distinction between class hegemony and hegemony within gender relations, he however points out that there are striking similarities that have been ignored by Connell. Demetriou (2001) posits therefore that Connell ignored that in Gramsci's original conception, the classes allied to the leading class will unite thereby creating what he refers to as a historic bloc towards domination. Therefore, Demetriou (2001) suggests that Connell created a false dualism between hegemonic and non-hegemonic masculinities since with reference to Gramsci he suggests that these masculinities are not always in opposition and that non hegemonic masculinities are not always subordinated. In conclusion, with reference to Gramsci, Demetriou (2001) therefore proposes what he refers to a hybrid masculine bloc which legitimises patriarchy by rendering the patriarchal dividend invisible since this dividend is not just within the hegemonic masculinity bloc.

Other scholars have also been critical. Moller (2007), for example, like Demetriou (2001) acknowledges the influence of the work of Connell in the field of studies on masculinity by explaining and identifying the ways in which some men dominate not only women but other men. Moller (2007) suggests, however, that Connell's model of hegemonic masculinity ignores the complexity of gender practices by failing to engage with other theoretical frameworks on gender by insisting on the maintenance of a model of a hierarchy of masculinities that are distinct. Moller (2007) argues therefore that by this failure to engage with other theoretical frameworks and insisting on a rigid framework, Connell ignores the wider practices of masculinity by maintaining a rigid

focus on the unsavoury elements of masculine abuses of power. Moller (2007) further notes that that by maintaining this rigid framework, Connell as a social constructionist must recognise that there must be conditions under which masculinities can change.

A further critique of the theory of hegemonic masculinity takes up this subject of the changing nature of masculinity and is particularly relevant within the sporting arena and football in particular. In the original formulation, Connell (1987) contends that hegemonic masculinity is constructed not only in relation to women but to subordinated masculinities. In practice, Adams et al (2010) point out that central to the construction of masculinity is the requirement to confirm heterosexuality and be homophobic. Football, as Magrath (2017) reminds us, remains a stronghold of homophobia and a hostile environment for sexually diverse supporters. Indeed, Willis (2015) reports the results of a study that indicated that around 24% of gay men have actively avoided sports like football, as they perceive it to be unsafe. Willis (2015) further notes that another study reported that among Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender (LGBT) people, 70% have heard homophobic language used in football in the past five years. Anderson (2009), however, suggests that in football there is now evidence of decreasing homophobia and what Anderson (2009) refers to as homophobia which he defines as the fear of being thought to be homosexual where a highly homophobic culture exists. Given this reduction in homophobia, Anderson (2009) suggests that the model of hegemonic masculinity proposed by Connell (1987) may no longer be an appropriate or adequate framework for theorising gender inequalities since he argues that with men no longer needing to construct their masculinities in opposition to homosexual or subordinated subject positions and via homophobic language and, where homophobic attitudes are treated with contempt, multiple masculinities can co-

exist, with gendered behaviours of boys and men being less different from that of girls and women. Accordingly, Anderson (2009) proposes a new inclusive theory of masculinity with a more equitable concept of masculinity and one that is less rigid in its vertical notion of hierarchy.

In proposing this inclusive masculinity theory (IMT), Anderson (2009) contends that this decline in homophobia is as a result of the social and cultural changes within Western society that further render the concept of hegemonic masculinity outdated and therefore unable to accurately theorise men's attitudes and practices that previously constituted hegemonic masculinity. Anderson (2009), in a further critique of the theory of hegemonic masculinity, posits that rather than the assertion by Connell (2005) that one form of masculinity is culturally exalted at a given time, it is in fact now the case that two dominant but not dominating forms of masculinity exist. One form being the conservative form with the other being the inclusive form. This theory of inclusive masculinities is evident in a number of studies that centre on football or on the traditional masculinised sports arena (Adams 2011, Anderson 2008, Anderson 2011, Anderson and McGuire 2010, Magrath 2017) which has led to the expansion of the inclusive masculinity theory into the exploration of the experience of bisexual young men and young gay men (Maloney, Roberts, & Caruso, 2017)

However, the theory of inclusive masculinities itself is not beyond critique. Whilst Connell herself has not engaged with inclusive masculinities theory directly (Maloney et al, 2017), she continues to argue that an examination of the masculinities of the main power-holding elites suggests that a huge task remains in the fight for gender equality (Connell 2006). In addition, whilst Connell (2016) recognises that counter-hegemonic projects among men have increased, they have limited reach and impact.

De Boise (2015) suggests that rather than the concept of hegemonic masculinity being flawed, it is the concept of inclusive masculinities that is flawed to the extent that it offers little to the critical studies on men and masculinities agenda since the critique of hegemonic masculinity has arisen from a misrepresentation and even a misunderstanding of it. Whilst challenging inclusive masculinities theoretically, De Boise (2015) further challenges the assertion that physical intimacy and tactility between men playing sports equates to a societal shift in attitude around homosexuality since this has always existed in football without any challenge whatsoever to an intensely homophobic culture. Blayac, Conilleau, Delahaye, and Quanquin,(2011) remain convinced that, despite the concept of hegemonic masculinity having met many criticisms, it provides a well-established and complex analytical tool.

Media and Masculinities

According to Connell (1987) an important element within the social and cultural construction of masculinity is the media. With young people now consuming almost eleven hours of media content per day, more now than at any point in the last decade (Giaccardi, Ward, Seabrook, Manago and Lippman 2017), the role of the media in contributing to gender construction is now therefore much more significant. Such is the significance of this mass media, that it not only includes traditional media such as television and film but also now includes online music and music videos as well as computer games and internet surfing. Accordingly, this mass media now makes it one of the most influential forces in young boys' lives (Kivel and Johnson 2009). Given the extent of mass media consumption it is particularly important in an analysis of gender

construction, since as MacDonald and LaFrance (2018 p2) note the mass media tend to “conform to and create stereotypes”. In addition, MacDonald and LaFrance (2018 p2) further note that mass media “often forms the basis for treating members of some groups differently from others”. For example, Harris and Clayton (2002) in an analysis of the UK tabloid press found that within sports reporting, despite increasing participation of women only 6% of reports were of female sports activity. Where female athletes were featured within the tabloid press, images were often of the female athletes taken during periods of inactivity, whilst male athletes were shown in action and engaged in physical endeavour (Harris and Clayton 2002).

Nilsson and Lundgren (2020) for example undertook a review of the Swedish press in order to assess how men and masculinity was now being represented following the development of the #metoo movement in 2017 that spread across the world in response to sexual violence against women. Nilsson and Lundgren (2020) justify their analysis of Swedish media as they claim that Sweden is widely regarded as the most gender equal country in the European Union. Their analysis concluded that masculinity continued to be represented and associated with violence and aggression but what was emerging was a ‘new man’ who is both strong and gentle at the same time. Media representations of this ‘new man’ in mass media are not new however, as Baker and Levon (2016) highlight the concept of the ‘new man’ that emerged in the 1980’s and was seen as a more caring, sensitive man who was concerned with his appearance. Within the print media in the U.K, this ‘new man’ image coincided with the launch of men’s magazines such as Esquire and GQ. According to Baker and Levon (2016) the arrival of this ‘new man’ created a shift from the traditional masculine ideology of aggression, strength and power. However, this ‘new man’ imagery portrayed in the

pages of these emerging publications was countered and rejected with the creation of 'lad' culture prevalent in the pages of Loaded magazine and FHM magazine (Baker and Levon, 2016). This 'lad' culture sought to reassert 'traditional' masculine ideologies such as sexism, homophobia and the confirmation of heterosexuality (Baker and Levon 2016).

Alongside such magazines as FHM and Loaded that promoted traditional hegemonic forms of masculinity, men's health and lifestyle magazines still continue to encourage dominant and aggressive behaviours, the rejection of seeking help and excessive alcohol consumption (Lewington, Sebar and Lee 2018). Furthermore, Waling, Duncan, Angelides, and Dowsett (2018) found not only do these particular men's magazines promote and encourage dominant and aggressive behaviours, whilst also promoting a muscular body image of men, they further promote the sexualisation of women via sexual imagery hereby maintaining a strong heterosexual influence. Despite this, Cleland (2014) has found evidence of a more inclusive form of masculinity now emerging within traditional mainstream print media, with more acceptance of homosexuality, particularly in sport and the media's representation of it. Whilst attitudes towards homosexuality within the British print media do appear to be changing, Cleland (2014) does however concede that the continued overall emphasis of idealised forms of masculinity has inhibited elite footballers from 'coming out' as gay. Arcimowicz (2020) also found evidence of more inclusive forms of masculinity in the traditional print media via the portrayal of the Polish footballer Robert Lewandowski. Whilst Arcimowicz (2020) did find portrayals of Lewandowski as exhibiting traditional hegemonic masculine characteristics of success, hard work, muscularity, this imagery was only evident when Lewandowski was actually playing

football. Outside of football, Lewandowski was portrayed in the media as a family man, and caring for the feelings of others.

Mass media, is of course much wider than just print media. As Giaccardi, et al (2017) note, sports television and films are also significantly associated with, as well as promoting particular masculine ideologies. Specifically, Giaccardi et al (2017) reported that within television programmes, adverts, films and magazines, portrayal of men tended to portray them as aggressive, dominant, active and in a work role as opposed to a family role. Furthermore, Giaccardi et al (2017) reported that women were under represented in mass media and when they were present were often sexualised, scantily dressed or conducting traditional stereotypical subordinate roles such as helpless victim or housewives. This imagery according to Giaccardi et al (2017) was not restricted to one particular genre within mass media but was prevalent across all genres such as comedies, dramas, and video games. Indeed, such is the role of one particular genre of mass media, film, in constructing particular masculine ideologies that Broch (2015) outlines the use of a film by the Hollywood star Al Pacino by a Norwegian handball coach to imbue his players with notions of idealised masculine imagery such as aggression, sacrifice, and never give up attitudes. This imagery as Broch (2015) highlights was utilised by the coach to assuage the concerns of the players around what is normally recognised in Norway as a female sport. Whilst within the new media evidence of more inclusive masculinities are emerging such as the ridiculing and parodying of hyper masculinity by influential YouTube gamers (Maloney, et al 2017), Ging (2005) concludes that in fact the majority of mainstream media texts perpetuate the hegemonic form of masculinity. According to Vokey, Tefft, & Tysiaczny

(2013), some publications even include suggestions of violence and aggression towards women.

Indeed, as Messerschmidt (2000) reports, some men use violence, particularly sexual violence towards girls and women, as a means of expressing control and power due to a lack of other masculine resources. Sexual objectification of women and girls provides legitimacy as having sex is what real men do (Messerschmidt 2000). Men should always be ready for sex, initiate sex, be sexually experienced with multiple partners and actively pursue women since low sexual desire and sexual inexperience is ridiculed and leads to questions regarding sexual orientation (Murray 2018). Whilst at the same time sexual violence is often used as a tactic to maintain dominance over women (Smith, Parrott, Swartout, & Tharp 2015).

Constructing hegemonic masculinity is not just about sexual violence and domination over women. For Michalski (2017) there is a clear link between gender identity and violence. Like Messerschmidt (2000), Michalski (2017) notes that when individuals, have limited economic or political power then status obtained through violence enables them to secure a reputation as a real man. Masculinity is of course culturally specific, and different cultures see masculinities constructed in many ways (Benyon 2002). In China, the culturally exalted form of masculinities portrayed in magazines is one that Tan *et al* (2013) describe as “refined and sophisticated”. Even publications deemed to be serious and intellectual depict men in positive portrayals of ‘manliness’ targeting men with adverts for commodities seen as typically masculine goods such as cars, banking, and information technology, whereas adverts targeted at women are often for trivial everyday commodities (Wörsching 2009)

Portrayals of hegemonic masculinity in popular mass media present exemplars that begin to enable us to make sense of the relationship between cultural norms or scripts for hegemonic masculinity and 'configurations of practice' embodied by actual men. It is the sporting arena however that has provided the most fertile ground for the provision of exemplars that enable us to make sense of how hegemony is sustained, particularly in sports where masculinity is linked to socially sanctioned aggression and physical power (Grindstaff & West 2011). Despite recent gains by women, sport appears to be still largely organised by men and for men.

Sport and Masculinity

In modern society we believe that men view and value sport as an opportunity to develop positive personal qualities such as teamwork, moral character, self-restraint, and a sense of fair play (Adams et al 2010). Adams et al (2010) conclude that sport continues to be closely connected to the gendering process. From the ancient Olympiad to the present, sport has been a primary site for defining, cultivating and displaying Western ideals of masculinity (Sabo and Jansen 1998).

Connell (2005), Messner (1992), and Adams (2010) illustrates how hegemonic masculinity is constructed in sport in this early part of the twenty first century by demonstrations by men of physical prowess, often using sexism, aggression or discrimination, against females; to distance themselves from association with femininity and from homosexuality. These demonstrations of are often promoted by sports coaches who use discourses that draw on narratives of war, gender, and sexuality to facilitate aggressive and violent responses such as the need for players

to adopt 'a warrior attitude' or 'grow some balls' or to 'stop acting like a poof' (Adams *et al* 2010).

For a particular masculinity to be hegemonic it must be culturally exalted, with exemplars who are celebrated as heroes (Connell 2000). These heroes play a significant role in the process where young boys are taught by the gendered routines of the sporting world that they inhabit (Parker 2006) to accept the values associated within sport, such as competition, toughness and winning at all costs (Messner 1989). Dufur (2006) suggests, however, that because masculinity, at least in part, is defined as that which is not feminine, some male athletes' relationships with women can be problematic by suggesting that men who play sports hold more traditional attitudes toward women than do non - athletes, regardless of the type of sport that the men play. According to Dufur (2006), the problematic nature of some male athletes' attitudes towards women can also, result in violence against women. Whannel (1999) agrees by considering the power aspect of developing hegemonic masculinity by suggesting that the characteristics of hegemony developed in sport such as toughness and aggression may sometimes be directed against women with some sports stars linking their power as sporting stars to the assumption that men should control women or assert power over them. Although Dufur (2006) recognises this type of disregard for women is not limited to male athletes, she suggests that the hyper masculine ideals of sport may in fact encourage sexually aggressive behaviour.

Whilst sport often has the appearance of being something which unites men, it is also a practice that divides men since sporting practices marginalise and stigmatise gayness (Whannel 1999). However, it is not just gay masculinity that is marginalised,

and stigmatised it is also other subordinated masculinities. Messner (1992) notes that boys are often judged by their ability (or lack of) in competitive sport and that having sporting ability helps to build and define masculine identity. For other males seeking to build their masculine identity but who lack the skill can create this gender identity by being knowledgeable about sport (Messner, and Sabo 1994). In modern day Western culture many men believe that, in order to be masculine, sport needs to feature significantly within their lives. The prominent nature of sport via mass media provides men with a vehicle to do this (Messner et al 1993). Such is the impact of mass media sport as an institutional site for the construction of masculinity that boys are much more likely to watch televised sport than girls (Messner, Dunbar, and Hunt 2000). In addition, Messner (2013) found that only 5% of television sports news was allocated to women's sports and that 99.5% of commentators on sports programmes being male. When women are used as sports commentators they are most often used in stereotypical roles, often cheering the men on (Messner, et al 2000). Even during the break in televised sport during the adverts, women are marginalised, excluded and sexualised (Messner, et al 2000).

Developing gender identity in football

Walvin (2014) describes football as the most popular sport in the world. Whilst the game of association football as we know it was formally codified in 1877 following the establishment of the rules of the game at Harrow, football has been recorded as being played as early as 1500BCE (Giulianotti 2000). As Stasi, and Evans (2013) note, football is globally recognised as a symbol of masculinity (Stasi and Evans 2013) and is central to the promotion and maintenance of men's dominance over women (Adams *et al* 2010) via the exclusion of female participation in the game. So despite football's

mass appeal, it continues to be an overwhelmingly masculine pursuit at both national and local levels across Europe (Clark and Paechter 2007). As Esson (2013) highlight, football is also utilised by some footballers in Africa who demonstrate their masculinity via displays of wealth. Further, a career in football is now seen by some as a way to circumvent an education system considered to lead to unemployment, or unacceptable employment in the feminised informal economy (Esson 2013). For Rubinstein, and Lansisky (2013) more football players than other sports players were seen as the most anti-feminist. In addition, Rubinstein & Lansisky (2013) also found that the football players they studied were also the most likely to be interested in male-typical occupations and hobbies.

There have been successful attempts made to attract women to watch and play football, with a report by the FA of England in 2005 revealing that 130,000 women and girls were playing football in leagues or cups, and that football has overtaken netball as the most popular sport for women in England (Clark & Paechter 2007). However, football continues to be a game for men by men with the 'footballer' still being perceived as a kind of iconic male and masculinity being performed through football (Clark & Paechter 2007). Such is this involvement of women across the world as well as the UK that for example in Denmark 21% of footballers are women, with Germany having 15% and England 5% (Pfister, Lenneis, and Mintert, 2013). Caudwell (2011a) however highlights the dichotomy of, on the one hand governing bodies of football encouraging female participation in the game but on the other hand actively discouraging females from playing an active part in the elite hegemonic football culture. Even in Japan where football has emerged as a major cultural force over the past one or two decades there is only one girl for every 109 boys playing football

(Manzenreiter 2008). Caudwell (2011a) further highlights that the game's governing bodies strive to ensure that the women's game is separate and distinct from the men's game by actively promoting imagery of femininity within the women's thereby separating it from the men's masculine game.

Despite the promotion of 'feminine' football promoted by the governing authorities alluded to by Caudwell (2011a), such is the link with masculinity and football that for many female top-level European footballers, embracing football means opposing or rejecting their femininity (Clark & Paechter 2007) and often being seen as 'tomboys' (Pawlowski, Ergler, Tjørnhøj-Thomsen, Schipperijn, and Troelsen 2014). Although this notion of rejecting femininity is disputed by Skogvang & Fasting (2013) who argue that football-playing women have multiple identities and that the female footballer can slide in and out of different femininities and masculinities without experiencing it as problematic thereby challenging the hegemonic femininity. Grindstaff & West (2011), however, disagree with this notion of hegemonic femininity since although some femininities are culturally idealised, no femininities are hegemonic because all forms of femininity in society are constructed in the context of the overall subordination of women to men. Jeanes (2011) suggests rather that it is in fact the discourses of acceptable female embodiment that restrict the ability of girls to use football for alternative performances of femininity since football playing girls have to look 'feminine' and be committed to cultivating a slim idealised body.

Caudwell (2011b) notes that women are active participants throughout the game and not just as players but as coaches, managers and as spectators. Caudwell (2011b) highlights, however, that whilst women are visible throughout football it remains an

activity that men and boys do. Given this, Pfister, et al (2013) note that research on women in football is limited with the majority of this available research being purely focussed on the female football player, despite evidence provided by Jones (2003) and Pope (2010) demonstrating that women have throughout the history of the game attended football matches. This lack of research may, as Malcolm, Jones and Waddington (2000) suggest, be related to methodological issues in regards to the collection of data given that easily identifiable groups of supporters such as those with season tickets, those who buy programmes or even members of fan groups tend to be unrepresentative of the crowd as a whole. Jones (2003) and Pope (2010) propose, however that the lack of research on women football fans may in fact be related to the view that women football fans are viewed as being less authentic or committed than male fans rather than as a result of methodological challenges.

This view of women supporters having a lack of authenticity, Pope (2010) suggests, stems from the 'gentrification' or 'bourgoiseification' of football that commenced according to Pope (2010) after the 1989 Hillsborough stadium disaster where ninety six Liverpool supporters lost their lives. The changes implemented after Hillsborough that included all seater stadia were intended Pope (2010) suggests to make the game more family friendly, and to move the game away from the 'hooligan' era. As Pope (2010), notes, this perceived feminisation of the game that sought to attract more women actually led to a backlash from some male fans as women fans were viewed as part of the move to a middle class game away from its traditional working class roots. Toffoletti, and Mewett, (2012) suggest that this lack of perceived authenticity and not being a 'real' fan may in fact be related to how some women actually consume the game itself attending the match primarily to objectify the players.

Toffoletti, and Mewett, (2012) suggest, therefore, that by attending football games to objectify the male players not only does this act jeopardize women's legitimacy of fandom but it can also further marginalise women within the game as it confirms the idealised male body image as desirable and confirms the woman's femininity thereby affirming hegemony. This affirmation of hegemonic masculinity Toffoletti, and Mewett, (2012) suggests is not just in the way women look at the footballer's body but also in the actions of the player such as being active, strong and powerful. Toffoletti, and Mewett, (2012) do recognise that this female fan that performs emphasised femininity as described by Connell (1987) is rejected by other women who follow football as being non authentic and indeed aligns further with Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) in their redefining of the gender hierarchy by suggesting the need for a more holistic understanding of the gender hierarchy where "the agency of subordinated groups as much as the power of dominant groups" (p848). Unfortunately, according to Pope (2013), these females who reject the model of emphasised femininity and view themselves as authentic fans (Toffoletti and Mewett, 2012) have remained on the whole invisible due to requirement in society for the maintenance of a version of emphasised femininity as the norm.

Pope (2010) posits that in fact the lack of academic research on female fans may in fact be as a result of this perception that female fans are not authentic and only attend the game to lust after the players, despite the assertion by Jones (2008) that between 15% and 20% of a football crowd are female. Whilst 15% - 20% of women attend football matches, according to Malcolm, Jones and Waddington (2000) despite the 'feminisation' of the game by the football authorities in order to increase engagement

by women, no significant increase in numbers was detected. Pope (2010) further explores this 'feminisation' concept and suggests that whilst women are more minded to attend football matches as a result of stadium safety and a reduction in hooliganism, stadium facilities remain male friendly and retain this 'masculine' focus. Whilst Pope (2010) acknowledges that 'real fans' are unlikely to be put off by limited and or dirty toilet facilities or a cold stale pie, Pope (2010) suggests that football stadia do need to become less male focussed in their imagery. In Scotland, where a reported 8% of fans are female, a study has been commissioned to explore why women do or do not attend football games (BBC Sport 2018).

Whilst the stadium itself can be masculine in nature, practices within the stadium can be discouraging to female supporters. Ben-Porat (2009) agrees with Popes (2010) assertion that football stadia are male focussed by describing them as 'permission zones' (p885) where behaviours deemed unacceptable outside the stadium is permissible. So, for women who do attend stadia, practices of masculinity are normative and emphasised femininity is expected and desired. Manzenreiter (2008) provides examples of the impact of these permission zones where despite over 42% of attendances at football matches in Japan being female, in many of the grounds women were banned from the area behind the goal, public displays of full nudity in the ground was common as well as sexualised chants and images such as the carrying of inflatable sex dolls.

It is not only through the exclusion or discouragement of women that hegemonic masculinity is constructed in football. Skelton (2000) notes that as well as hegemonic masculinity being constructed in football in relation to women, it is also heterosexual

and is constructed in relation to subordinated masculinities. A study by Swain (2000) demonstrated how football provided a basis for a group of year 6 boys to perform hegemonic masculinity and maintain this status through the marginalizing and feminising of other boys as well as by excluding girls. Boys demonstrating a lack of skill or competence became feminised and were subjected to homophobic abuse, as the hegemonic group acts within the cultural imperative of heterosexuality.

I further note the work of Adams et al (2010) that central to the construction of masculinity is the requirement to confirm heterosexuality and be homophobic. The openly gay footballer Justin Fashanu was banned from training with Nottingham Forest FC by his manager Brian Clough when his sexuality was discovered despite becoming Britain's first £1M black footballer (Clough 1995). Despite this, Caudwell (2011c) highlights that there is a distinct lack of research on the topic with most studies instead focussing on sexism and racism. Caudwell (2011c) therefore highlights the extent of homophobic chanting and abuse that is directed at opposition players and opposition fans across the world. Not only is homophobic chanting extensive, Caudwell (2011c) reports that it has become normalised and, despite significant coverage of closed circuit television (CCTV) homophobic chanting goes largely unpunished. Whilst Caudwell (2011c) reports that racist chanting has largely disappeared and is now deemed unacceptable due in part to high profile campaigns, activity tackling homophobia has had little success. Caudwell (2011c) however highlights the work of 'The Justin Campaign' established following the death of Justin Fashanu. Other campaigns have also sought to tackle homophobia such as a 2013 publicity campaign coordinated by a gay rights charity and a leading bookmaker, involved requesting

English and Scottish professional footballers to wear rainbow laces on match day. (The Guardian 2013).

Despite claims that there was general support for the campaign's message, a number of leading clubs in England refused to participate. In addition, the organisation that oversees football in England (Football League) also did not back the campaign (The Guardian 2013). In Scotland, the only team to publically back the campaign was Stenhousemuir, a Scottish Professional Football League (SPFL) team playing in the third tier of Scottish football (Herald Scotland 2013). Despite these campaigns, Caudwell (2011c) concedes that challenging explicit homophobic gestures will be difficult. Skogvang & Fasting (2013) contend, however, that the culture of homophobia in football and the secrecy around homosexuality is more to do with the football clubs and agents rather than specific individuals since the clubs and the agents put pressure on gay players to keep their sexuality hidden since it threatens the ability of the sport to reproduce the hegemonic form of masculinity.

Gender construction and identity in football is therefore multi-faceted and complex in nature. Work undertaken by Parker (1996, 2001 and 2006), for example, noted that this complex construction of masculinity also required that elite athletes in football demonstrated specific qualities within their role. Specifically, Parker (2001) suggest that footballers require a keen and 'hardy' enthusiasm for the game itself, a forceful 'will-to-win', an acceptance of workplace relations based on authoritarianism/subservience, as well as an ability to conform to institutional ('official') rules, regulations and disciplinary codes. Furthermore as Parker (2001) continues these elite footballers require a commitment to social and professional notions of solidarity and group cohesion. Parker (2001) notes that these stipulated

norms and values are required should the athlete stand a chance of progressing to a higher level.

Coakley and Pike (2014) further identify four norms that they suggest form the criteria that are required to be an athlete in high performance sport. These four norms are described as the sport ethic. The first norm requires that the athlete is dedicated to the game above all other things. The second is that the athlete strives for distinction by continually seeking to improve and achieve perfection. Thirdly the athlete must accept that there are risks and they are required to play through the pain, and finally that any other obstacles to perfection require to be overcome (Coakley and Pike 2014). These four norms or the 'sporting ethic' can be subsumed into what Gearing (1999) describes as the key elements of professional sport such as courage, risk-taking, uncertainty and tension, and an overriding preoccupation with winning and success. For many elite athletes, this sport ethic is defined as the criteria for what it means to be a real athlete (Hughes and Coakley 1991).

The excitement that sports provide for athletes means that if they want to continue in it as long as possible (coupled with the fact that often being chosen to play or to receive sponsorship is based on this), they must demonstrate a willingness to conform unquestionably to the sporting ethic. (Coakley, and Pike, 2014). Indeed, as Anderson (2008) highlights, the complex reproduction of orthodox masculinity in men's team sports only promotes those who conform to this orthodox hegemonic form of masculinity inherent within some team sports.

The athlete by their uncritical acceptance and commitment to what they have been told by important people in their lives may become too committed to the four elements

of the sporting ethic and overconform to this as overconforming athletes receive recognition by their peers (Coker-Cranney, Watson, Bernstein, Voelker, and Coakley, 2018). As Bush, Anderson and Carr (2012) highlight, by not conforming, athletes are taught at an early age that questioning those in authority may result in serious consequences for the athlete such as deselection or even becoming mocked, ostracised or stigmatised as not being team players. To succeed in sport one must therefore conform or even over conform to the sporting ethic in order to illustrate ones compliance to the orthodox form of masculinity (Anderson 2008).

Gramsci and Hegemony

The terminology of hegemony utilised in this thesis derives from the work done on hegemony by the Italian Marxist Antonio Gramsci whom according to Kendie (2006) is now recognised by many as the greatest Marxist thinker since Karl Marx himself. As Bairner (2007) noted, this appeal of Gramsci's Marxist ideas within social sciences may however be more to do with a withdrawal from Marxist ideologies within the social science community and specifically a rejection of orthodox Marxism by social scientists that often resulted in Stalinist policies evident within the Soviet Union. Bairner (2007) further explained that since Gramsci died in 1937, he was not forced to explain or justify the failings of Soviet Communism which was according to Bairner (2007) the biggest reason for the retreat from Marxist ideologies in general and the orthodoxy of Marxism - Leninism. For the political left, embracing Gramsci, allowed them to replace an orthodox and dogmatic economic determinism ideology with an ideology that embraced the concept of democracy (Bairner, 2007). The adoption of Gramsci and his ideology was an alternative to the classical orthodox Marxism of Lenin whose analysis was only relevant and appropriate in the East whereas Gramsci was viewed as the

theorist for the West (Joseph, 2002). Much of his appeal to the political left social scientists was however the fact that Gramsci himself rejected the notion that his writing was to be a prescriptive and doctrinal blueprint for change (Garrett 2009).

The development of Gramsci's political and ideological formation owed much according to Garrett (2009) to his own social development. By way of explanation, Garrett (2009) points out that Gramsci himself grew up in Sardinia in the South of Italy, an area of the country that was viewed with disrespect and underdeveloped by the richer North. Furthermore, Garrett (2009) highlighted that Gramsci's own physical and mental health issues enabled him to empathise with and understand the plight of those at the margins of society. Whilst Gramsci's social development shaped him, it was not until he attended university in Turin where he encountered Marxist ideology for the first time as many of his university lecturers had links with the socialist movement with Gramsci eventually rising to become leader of the Italian Communist Party and a Member of Parliament (Hoare and Smith, 1999). The Marxist ideology of Gramsci is explored within his prison notebooks written during his imprisonment from 1926 – 1937 by the Italian Fascist Government led by Mussolini. These 2,848 pages of handwritten notes were preserved and smuggled out of Italy by his sister in law Tatiana after his death (Kenway, 2001). It is within these prison notebooks that Gramsci develops and explores the terminology of hegemony that denotes the predominance of one social class over others. This represents not only political and economic control, but also the ability of the dominant class to project its own way of seeing the world so that those who are subordinated by it accept it as 'common sense' and 'natural'.

According to Stoddart (2007) Gramsci's theory of hegemony derives from and expands on Marx's notion of ideology where society adopts the ideas and interests of the dominant social class by the naturalisation of the capitalist relations of production with workers coming to accept that the capitalist mode of production is the only viable option where they sell their labour in return for goods and commodities. Stoddart (2007) further notes that Gramsci's work in fact reinterpreted the Marxist notion of ideology due to its limited applicability to everyday social interaction. In reinterpreting ideology, Gramsci placed more emphasis on the importance of Capitalist culture through social institutions such as schools, churches, courts, and the media, among others, who spread and promote beliefs, assumptions, and values and thereby socialise people into the norms, values, and beliefs of the dominant social group (Stoddart, 2007). Stoddart (2007) highlighted that such is the importance of these institutions that the group that controls these institutions controls the rest of society. Whilst according to Lears (1985) Gramsci did not specifically name this form of hegemony, Lears (1985) defines it as cultural hegemony as the masses consent to the given direction of social life. This cultural hegemony is according to Kendie (2006) how Gramsci explained why there had not been what Marx referred to as a proletarian revolution or successful counter-hegemony efforts in the industrialised West. The power of the ruling class is not localised just within the economic base but within the values, beliefs, habits and modes of thought of the proletariat via the control by the ruling class of the spiritual, ideological and cultural spheres of the society. (Kendie, 2006).

For Gramsci, the means of production therefore were not just the physical process of human labour but also human cultural life which he referred to as the material

infrastructure and cultural superstructure (Fulton, 1987). For Gramsci, Socialism will not be achieved in Western Capitalist democracies by bloody armed revolution but only by winning hearts and minds via education and politics by the development of an alternative hegemony involving intellectuals and the masses (Fulton, 1987). For Gramsci, education was a significant factor in winning these hearts and minds towards the Socialist transformation since education exists within this cultural superstructure that the ruling class utilise to continue their power (Durakoğlu and Güney, 2015). In fact, according to Gramsci, education is merely a tool utilised by the ruling classes to reproduce capitalism therefore education can become a powerful tool in the development of an alternative hegemony (Durakoğlu and Güney, 2015). This alternative hegemony can only happen however when an education system becomes democratic by educating all the people to have the qualifications of a ruler (Durakoğlu and Güney, 2015).

Lears (1985) reminded us, however, that cultural hegemony is always paired with domination since without it hegemony has little meaning. So whilst hegemony implies power through consent, force coexists alongside with one or the other predominating. For example, whilst in Western Capitalist democracies, the ruling bloc control the means of coercion such as the army and police it is the power of civil society that sustains them (Fulton, 1987)

Scotland, Cultural Identity and masculinity

Messner (1992) reminds us that masculinity or manliness is developed through a complex process of interaction with culture and environment that develops and changes as society changes and develops. Therefore, in describing and understanding how masculinity is constructed in Twenty First Century Scotland, it is

important that we explore and describe the cultural identity of Scotland including not only what being Scottish is, but also how that culture has developed.

In order to promote domestic cohesion, state formation and economic and social development, Western Governments in the eighteenth century theorised that the creation of 'others' was a necessary adjunct to state formation and national solidarity (Lebow 2012). In effect, national identity was conceptualised via an 'us' and 'them' or by reference to who and what we are not. Whilst Scotland does not possess all the trappings of a modern nation state, there is no doubt that it can be described as a nation (McCrone 1992, McCrone 1997, Bairner 2001, Abell, Condor and Stevenson 2006) with its identity often defined as not being English (Craig 2003).

According to Giddens et al. (2016), culture refers to the values, norms, and material goods held or created by a given group. Giddens et al (2016) reminds us that these values are defined as the abstract ideals shared by groups; they can change over time and may in fact differ within different cultures. Similarly, the norms, the principles or rules of social life can also change over time as of course will the material goods a society creates that influence the ways people live. This is evident above in the development of the British culture and British society from the 17th Century. Of course, culture and society differ but are interrelated with one unable to exist without the other, with society identified as a system of interrelationships which connects individuals (Giddens et al 2016). For Sewell Jr (1999), culture stands for a concrete and bounded world of beliefs and practices. These beliefs and practices are individual to a particular culture and even two cultures that share a language may have different habits, customs or behaviours. These different habits, customs and behaviours led to the

need for industrial Britain to impose a British culture for the economic benefit that it brought Sewell Jr (1999), despite this, many of the habits, customs and behaviour of the Scots remained.

This combination of values, beliefs, and practices within a culture therefore provides guidelines for individuals on how to dress, talk, act, and what is and what is not acceptable behaviour. Whilst culture is the combination of values, beliefs, and practices of a particular group, identities are specific and unique for each person. For example, Wahl and Scholl (2014) define identity in respect of how one views oneself and how others see you.

In Scotland the nature of identity has received significant debate and continues to receive significant debate (Kiely et al (2001; McCrone 1997). As Kiely et al (2001) note, identity for some is relatively easily defined as it is determined by you based on where you live and the culture that you exist within. Indeed, the given identity is often easier when like Scotland, boundaries have been fixed for over 500 years with no contested territories (McCrone 1997). McCrone et al (1998) suggest that we can easily explain the most obvious national identity characteristic described by Reicher, McCrone & Hopkins (2010) as an ethnic definition of national identity. This ethnic definition includes being born in Scotland with lines of descent and ancestry. McCrone et al (1998) go a little further than Reicher et al (2010) and separate out birth and ancestry into two distinct and separate categories for claiming national identity; you can be born in a country or have ancestry or lines of descent.

In 18th Century Britain, it was impossible for the ruling classes to wipe out this ethnic identity that had been developed over at least 500 years. In 21st Century multicultural Scotland, we have individuals who participate in Scottish society and consider themselves Scottish but don't have any claim to either birth or ancestry. McLaren (2015) describes this as civic identity where after a short period of time, those who were not raised in the country or who did not share in the country's traditions can, in fact, become true country nationals, by feeling themselves to be part of the nation and, importantly, participating in the political system by voting and engaging in other civic activities. According to Kiely et al. (2001), the adoption of a civic identity is the preferred option by those in power thereby reasserting the belief that identity is determined for citizens of the country out with our control. According to Malesevic (2011), it is not only the political ruling elite that ascribes a national identity. It is also the research world that, via empiricists, regularly rely on large-scale surveys with a view to assessing the attitudes of various populations.

For Giddens (1991), however, this determination of 'who am I' may have held true in earlier societies with a social order based firmly on tradition. This tradition would provide individuals with clearly defined roles and therefore a clear identity of 'who am I', but Giddens (1991) argues that in what he describes as post-traditional societies defining 'who I am' is something that we work out for ourselves. This self-identity therefore becomes a reflexive project, something that we continuously work on and reflect on. The self is therefore not something we are born with, and it is not fixed (Giddens 1991).

As Burr (1995) reminds us, one of the key characteristics of the theory of social constructionism is a critical stance towards taken-for-granted knowledge, i.e. the fact that something is widely believed and highly valued does not necessarily make it true. In taking this argument further, whilst many claim to possessing a national identity, it is still only a claim, not proof of its existence. Social constructionists furthermore question the basis that our knowledge and understanding of our world is not naturally occurring, suggesting that in fact it is made by the daily interactions between people in the course of their life through language and social experiences. The challenges faced in attempting to define a Scottish national identity are compounded therefore by the fact that actually having a national identity is not a naturally occurring phenomenon. I contend therefore within our ontological position that there is no single definition of a Scottish identity and that in fact many 'Scotlands' exist as well as a multitude of constructions of national identity. Our understanding of our environment is the result of the interactions and social processes in which people engage with each other (Burr 1995, Kiely et al 2001). However, whilst establishing identity is complex it is important as according to Wahl and Scholl (2014) identity can give us a sense of belonging and can help us find people with whom we might belong.

Bradley (2002) illustrates this construction of identity in a study of Scottish football fans where he illustrates that even among a nominally homogenous group of predominately Scottish born white working class, young males' identity is performed and reproduced utilising a complex range of artefacts. For example, a number of these football fans, despite geographically and ethnically being defined as Scottish, identified their national identity as Irish, with this being driven based predominately on the football team that they supported. Bradley (2002) further notes that, even within the cultural

nationalism of followers of the Scottish national football team singing together, the patriotic song Flower of Scotland being Scottish is defined differently depending on where one lived or which particular political party one supports. With the ever increasing globalisation of football a new national identity is emerging and being constructed and performed; that is the football identity (Boyle and Haynes 1996).

Giulianotti (1995) suggests that fans of the Scottish national football team construct an identity in direct opposition to that of fans of the English game with their reputation for violence (Carnibella, Fox, Fox, McCann and Marsh 1996, Taylor 1971, Williams, Dunning and Murphy 1984). According to Giulianotti (1995) these fans according to construct their identity around fun, and friendship in what he describes as a “carnavalesque” supporter culture. This image of the “carnavalesque” has received criticism, however, by Free and Hughson (2003) who suggest that Giulianotti (1995) dismisses, and is ambivalent to the objectification of women via sexualised singing and behaviours at football matches.

Despite Giulianotti's (1995) assertion of the creation of a new “carnavalesque” identity, in Scotland's post - industrial working class areas one substantiation of hegemony remains the image of the hard man or what Lawson (2013) describes as ‘tough’ masculinity. This ‘tough’ masculinity according to Lawson (2013) is characterised by physical strength, fearlessness, aggression, social competitiveness, and (usually) violent reactions against perceived insults. Whilst many men are unable to enact many of the properties such as actual violence for fear of legal ramifications, or being assaulted themselves, McCarry (2010) notes that violence and aggression are still accepted as normative characteristics of hegemonic masculinity in modern day

Scotland. This tough, often violent, masculinity is, according to Holligan and Deuchar (2015) associated with Scottish history particularly during the period 1800–1860 where urbanisation and industrialisation in Scotland gave rise to inward migration of unemployed working-class young men from the Scottish Highlands and Ireland to Glasgow and Lanarkshire when loss of kinship networks and material insecurities led to significant rises in violence. Holligan and Deuchar (2015) further explain that for many young men who have become marginalised through the collapse of heavy industry and the lack of meaningful opportunities for employment, violence may provide a means of ‘doing masculinity’ in a world where other resources are unavailable.

Crisis of masculinity

This marginalisation leads therefore to the work of Gee (2009) who notes that in current Western society there has therefore been some confusion as to what it now means to be a man thereby perpetuating a notion that masculinity is somehow in crisis. Gee (2009) explains that this confusion and the notion of a crisis in masculinity may have arisen as a result of media influences, since men may become confused about their own masculinity when they are unable to meet the expectations of the hegemonic standards depicted in the media. McDowell (2000) agrees by noting that the popular press in the U.K regularly highlight that men are somehow in trouble and are now becoming more disadvantaged. McDowell (2000) notes that representations of this disadvantage are seemingly evidenced by alluding to girls now outperforming boys in the traditional male subjects of science, technology and mathematics.

Whannel (1999) cites a range of other factors as contributing to this potential crisis such as the decline of the old manufacturing base in Western civilisations, the rise of the service sector, male unemployment and a 'feminisation' of work via part time, and flexible working. McDowell (2000) provides further evidence and noted that the traditional male occupations within the manufacturing industries of shipbuilding, car plants and steel industries have now largely been replaced by a service sector that tends to favour women over men. Such is the extent of this perceived crisis of masculinity that Clare (2001) notes the implications are wide reaching and include higher suicide rates, higher rate of imprisonment, and higher levels of drug and alcohol problems. Hopkins however notes that the discourse surrounding the idea that men are in crisis is contested and problematic. Beynon's (2002) examination of the discourse surrounding the notion of masculinity in crisis for example found that masculinity and men are often confused and conflated so that it remains unclear whether it is masculinity, men, or both that are supposed to be in crisis. Further, as Whitehead (2002) points out, as men are not a homogenous group, there can be no singular crisis of masculinity. As Kimmel (2000) notes, all the talk of boys failing grades in schools doesn't seem to apply the middle class boys whose sense of entitlement and success remain unchanged and unchallenged. As Kimmel (2000) highlights there can be no singular crisis of masculinity as we require to speak of masculinities given the different definitions of manhood we construct.

Beynon (2002) further points out that that the alleged crisis is not in fact a recent phenomenon and points to several periods of masculine crisis throughout history. As Kimmel (1987) highlights a crisis of masculinity occurred in the USA in the middle of the 19th Century with the expansion of industrialisation replacing the dominant of

farming industry. This crisis of masculinity continues Kimmel (1987) where men at this time therefore lost control of the labour process and lost control of their independence. In addition, Kimmel (1987) notes, the power of women increased as domestic servitude declined and women increasingly accessed education. Benyon (2002) notes that not only is a talk of a crisis in masculinity oversimplified, talk of a crisis in patriarchy may also be similarly over-simplified as the concept of patriarchy tends also to perceive men as an undifferentiated category. Engel's (2010) initial analysis of patriarchy recognised the unequal arrangement of power between males in the family, thus the use of the term 'gender order' therefore, may be more appropriate, as it recognises that the power men may hold over women is not complete, total or uncontested (Messner 1990).

Whilst some men dominate military, economic and social institutions, this is not however the core issue; it is the means by which culture shapes and legitimises men's everyday behaviour into appearing natural that enables certain inequalities to continue. What Connell's ideas on hegemonic masculinity suggest is that men's gender practices are subject to change in line with broader societal shifts to make them seem legitimate. Connell (2005) argues that representations of gender are not fixed and will always change to ensure their legitimacy. Hegemonic masculinity embodies a currently accepted strategy. When conditions for the defence of patriarchy change, the bases of dominance of a particular masculinity are eroded. Connell (2005) therefore cautions against associating a crisis of masculinity with the traditional sense of crisis tendencies, through which a coherent system is destroyed or restored through the crisis, as masculinity is not a system in this sense, rather it is a "configuration of practise within a system of gender relation" (p. 84)

The entry of women into workplaces, the public visibility of gay men or even the election of black male MPs does not throw patriarchy into disarray, it merely forces the presentation of certain gendered practices to change. As Whannel (1999) notes current masculinity is relatively secure in its dominance, therefore masculinity itself is not in crisis nor is it really a crisis in male power, but rather a crisis in the cultural modes through which masculinity presents itself. Whitehead (2002) perhaps is more succinct in noting that given that men have overwhelming control over resources and power, it is hard to imagine this group in any such crisis. Indeed a 'crisis' of masculinity may not always disrupt masculinities, but can initiate attempts to restore a dominant masculinity (Connell 2005).

Conclusion

As Messner (2002) highlights, the construction of masculinity is a complex process of interaction with culture and environment that develops and changes as society changes and develops and is culturally specific. Of the many complex factors influencing the construction of masculine identity, sport and in particular sports such as football encourage the display of characteristics that are seen as masculine, such as toughness, and aggression. However, despite the global popularity of the game, the culture and subculture associated with football and the reproduction of dominant masculinities has largely been taken for granted. This chapter has sought to explore the configuration of practices that characterise masculinity. In addition, it has set out the local context via the exploration of a recognition that masculinity is culturally specific. As Emslie, Hunt and O'Brien (2004) conclude, masculinity is defined in terms of being heterosexual, being respected, not being feminine, and not being gay.

CHAPTER 3: THE BEAUTIFUL GAME

Introduction

This chapter seeks to set the focus on football itself or as many including McGillivray, et al, (2005) and Magrath, (2017) describe it, “The Beautiful Game”. Whilst the sport of football is considered an important contributor to masculinity construction (Steinfeldt Vaughan, LaFollette, and Steinfeldt, 2012), according to Harvey (2005), it is only in the last thirty years or so that football has become an area for significant academic interest. Since then, Harvey (2005) suggests, football has continued to grow from a sport centralised in Europe and South America to a game watched and followed by hundreds of millions across the globe. As audiences have grown, a multitude of studies and research has followed. This global appeal of football has not only attracted academics and researchers but also global multinational businesses. As Hamil, Michie, Oughton and Warby (2000) note, the notion of football as a people’s game is rapidly being replaced by terminology such as customer, brand, product and audience.

Football has certainly become big business for the financiers and markets but as Hamil, Michie, and Oughton (1999) remind us, it continues to play an important role in a country’s social and cultural life. Kuper (1996) points to the fact that when the Dutch football team beat Germany in 1988, over 60% of the Dutch population took to the streets to celebrate. This gathering was significant in that it was the biggest public gathering since the liberation of the Netherlands during World War two. In Barcelona, the museum of the football club has more visitors than the Picasso museum, and is the most visited in the city, Salvador Dali once submitted an entry to an art competition run by the club and Pope John Paul II was once a season ticket holder (Kuper 1996). Whilst television, merchandising and other commercial income has transformed

football from its humble beginnings to where it is now, spectators continue to play a significant role in the revenue of clubs (Hamil, et al., 2000).

Had it not been for a confluence of factors that emerged during the latter part of the 19th Century in Scotland, such as the shorter working hours manifested as a half day Saturday coupled with the rapid extension of railway networks and increasing demand for leisure then the game may not have become as important and as significant as it is today particularly as a number of other sports were already popular among Victorians such as curling, quoiting, golf and horse racing (McDowell 2010). Clayton (2015) observes that such has been the impact of football in Britain that it is now officially recognised for its contribution to Britain's cultural identity, with the minutes of the meetings from 1863 that codified the rules of the game being exhibited alongside the Magna Carta and Shakespeare's First Folio in the British Library. These six meetings took football from the hybrid kicking and handling game without an administrative body overseeing the sport, the regional variations of the game and the considerable differences in rules to the multibillion pound industry of today (Clayton, 2015). Given the importance of football in modern society it is useful to reflect on the words of Strutt (1830 p9) who noted that:

“In order to form a just estimation of the character of any particular people, it is absolutely necessary to investigate the sports and pastimes most generally prevalent among them”

This chapter reflects on the development of the modern game in Scotland from its inception via Queens Park FC in 1868. The chapter then focuses on the history and

development of the current best known teams in Scotland. As hegemonic masculinity is an integral characteristic of Scottish Football (Macbeth, 2007), this chapter outlines how hegemonic masculinity has been performed throughout the history and development of the game.

If You Know Your History 1868 – Present

Whilst significant numbers of people consume professional football in Scotland via television or as spectators, the early beginnings of the game were less about those attending and more about the players. As Ross (2005) notes that prior to the second half of the 19th Century, the game was predominantly participatory with entire towns gathering on feast days engaging in a game that involved hundreds and lasted all day. During these games, no titles, cups or money was won. In fact nothing but the pride and passion of defeating a local rival was the prize (Ross, 2005).

According to Ross (2005) this rivalry, passion and pride remains today and has helped sustain the game throughout the Centuries that followed the codification of rules and the standardisation of the game into what we recognise as football today. As King (1997) highlights, it these particular elements within the game that some men utilise in their construction of masculinity.

Whilst evidence exists of a game that resembles modern football being played as far back as the 16th Century (Harvey 2005), the game began in Scotland in 1868 with Queens Park obtaining the Football Annual. This Football Annual first published in 1868 was a reference book that contained all of the various codes and rules of football. Harvey (2005) further notes that in 1870 Queens Park joined the English football

association but by 1872 with other clubs now in existence (Airdrie, Kilmarnock, The Thistle, The Eastern, Third Lanark Regiment, Vale of Leven, Dumbarton, Renton and Clydesdale) and with the secretary of Queens Park actively and vigorously advocating for the football association rules, the Scottish Football Association was formed in 1873.

Such was the interest in the new Scottish Football Association that between 1875 and 1880, the number of affiliated clubs grew from 27 to 140 (Harvey 2005). The subsequent introduction of professionalism unsurprisingly saw a rise in the number of professional soccer players in Scotland rising from 560 in 1893-4 to 1,754 in 1913-14 (Tranter 1998). The formation of the Scottish FA then set in motion a chain of events that lasted until 1989 when in 1872, Queens Park responded to an invitation by the secretary of the English football association to represent Scotland against England. As Ross (2005) notes, not only was this game historic in that it was the first international ever but it was also the first recorded incidence in the world of spectators being charged to watch a football match. Whilst five previous games had been held between 1870 and this game in 1872 that described themselves as internationals between England and Scotland, all these games took place in London with most of the players largely based there, with very few of the Scotland players having been born in Scotland (Leese 2015). Leese (2015) notes that illustrations of that first England versus Scotland international game, published shortly after its conclusion provide a record that demonstrated how the game was developing with the Scottish players portrayed as utilising a passing methodology consisting of short and long passes rather than the individual physicality that defined the early development of the game in England. Leese (2015) further suggests that Scotland played this way because they had not been indoctrinated by the English public school philosophy that valued and

promoted physicality and endurance. The success of this first international game with the reported 4000 convinced Queens Park and others such as Rangers, Kilmarnock, Dumbarton and Morton that they needed a private ground of their own where they could charge admission. In addition, the realisation that money could be made from football also brought about the realisation that to continue to attract spectators, club games required to be competitive rather than just the playing of 'friendlies' (Ross 2005)

As Vamplew (2016a) notes, on the whole clubs across Britain tended to lose money by playing 'friendlies'. So, despite protestations from many including Queens Park, a Scottish Football league was formed in 1890 (Ross 2005). Whilst this helped clubs generate income for the trustees (Vamplew 2016a) and ultimately to pay professional players, football also began to be used for philanthropic purposes to alleviate poverty, deprivation and tragedy and 'friendly' games continued to take place with the proceeds being allocated for charitable purposes particularly prevalent in Glasgow around the late 1870's (Vamplew 2016b).

The game continued to grow throughout the last decade of the 19th Century to the point where the 1892 Scottish Cup final between Celtic and Queens Park played at Ibrox Park, the home of Glasgow Rangers attracted a crowd of 40,000 (McDowell 2010). Even as early as 1896 football in Scotland had become a lucrative business and in attempting to attract more spectators to generate more income, clubs started building 'stands' where supporters could be sheltered from the weather (Vamplew 2016a). A game that began as a participative sport was now fast becoming one for spectators. Such was the specific rise of the game in Scotland that Kay (2009) notes

that in the 1878-79 season 126 clubs entered the Scottish cup. In England, it would not be until 1882-83 season where over 100 clubs entered the FA cup.

The contribution of Queens Park Football Club to the modern game in Scotland cannot be underestimated. Not only were Queens Park the first Scottish Club and the first to play an international fixture by representing Scotland against England, in addition they toured Denmark in 1898, 1900 and 1903, before the formation of La Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA), who now govern the sport worldwide (McDowell 2014). It is due to Queen's Park that the modern rules of the game were adopted in Scotland and that a governing body via the Scottish Football Association was founded at the insistence of Queens Park (Robinson 1920). As Robinson (1920) further notes, despite the rapid growth of football towards the end of the 19th Century, Queen's Park continued to be a significant force in Scottish football throughout the 1880's and 1890's with several players representing Scotland at international level.

However, towards the end of the Century, Queen Park went into a decline. According to Robinson (1920) this occurred when professionalism was recognised by the SFA in 1893 and adopted fully in 1896 resulting in the amateur Queens Park club not having a player selected for Scotland since 1902. Robinson (1920) further notes that despite significant attempts by Queens Park to resist professionalism in the Scottish game including suspending players and teams from the league, the pressure exerted on the SFA by member clubs due to their players being attracted South of the border to England who had adopted professionalism in 1885 led to the adoption of the professional game in Scotland. Despite this significant setback, Queen's Park continued to fiercely defend its amateur status, even banning ex-players who had left

to pursue a professional career from the annual club dance in 1911 (Robinson 1920). Although the Scottish football league was still in its infancy, by the beginning of the 20th Century as Queens Park went into terminal decline, two teams in Scotland were already becoming more powerful than all the others and were making more money than all the others (McDowell 2010)

The Old Firm

Whilst football continues to attract the paying spectator, it is thanks to Celtic and Rangers that Scotland has higher attendances per head of population than all other countries in Europe (Ross 2005, Kuper 1996). Indeed, when Scottish Football is mentioned, it is not uncommon for many to think of Celtic and Rangers who arguably are Scotland's biggest and most famous teams since between them they have divided the vast majority of all trophies won in Scottish football for over one hundred years. This domination has occurred according to Bradley (1995) as they contain the best and most expensive players, have the biggest stadia and attract the biggest crowds. As Vamplew (2016a) notes, the economic significance of their sporting, religious and tribal antagonism has led to the two Glasgow clubs being often referred to as 'the Old Firm', with the term first being used in 1904 (Morrow 2013). Such is the dominance of the Old Firm that no other team has won the top Scottish league title since 1984/85. (Morrow 2013). In addition, 70% of the turnover of the Scottish Professional league is accounted for by these two teams, and in 2004 the Scottish economy benefited by £118M. (Morrow 2013). Despite this dominance both on and off the field, Giulianotti (2005) argues that football in Scotland is dwarfed by the five big football leagues in England, Spain, Germany, Italy and France. As an example, Giulianotti (2005) noted that in 2003 the total turnover of the SPL was one eighth of the league in England

meaning that Scottish teams in general and Celtic and Rangers specifically are becoming increasingly uncompetitive in European competitions. This has led to Celtic and Rangers seeking out opportunities for other markets including the possibility of entering the English league structure (Morrow 2013). A recent report by European Football's governing body, the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA 2019), illustrated that the financial gulf remains as on average, income from television money in England is €145m per club. The aggregate income from TV revenue for a Scottish club is just €1.9m (UEFA 2019).

Despite a vote in 2009 of English club chairman against admitting the Old Firm into the English league structure, Morrow (2013) suggests that the issue of both teams leaving Scottish football remains a priority for them. However, the successes and dominance of these teams has according to McDougall (2013) extended the tribal antagonism that exists between the sectarian divide with Celtic identified as the team for Roman Catholics, and Rangers championing the cause of Protestantism (McMenemy, and Poulter, 2005). Not only is Celtic identified as the Catholic team, it remains a vehicle for Irish nationalism and Irish republican sentiment (McDougall 2013). Indeed, in a study Conner (2014) conducted amongst 132 Celtic supporters, it was found that 28% were born in Ireland (North and South) with 24% continuing to live in the island of Ireland. To this day, the Irish tricolour continues to fly above Celtic's stadium despite attempts by the Scottish Football Association in 1952 to have the flag removed (Conner 2014). According to Bradley (1998) the Scottish Football Association even threatened to remove Celtic from the league if the flag was not removed. This threat was issued after a crowd disturbance at a Celtic versus Rangers game and the SFA decided that the flying of the flag contributed to it. Celtic resisted the threat, seeing

it as an attack on their Irish identity. Bradley (1998) notes that despite an overwhelming vote of 26 to 7 among clubs supporting the stance of the SFA, the SFA quickly realised that it had no legitimate authority to enforce the demand. As Celtic's resistance continued, other clubs realised that the income generated by Celtic played a major part in the vibrancy of the game, their attacks waned and the club continued to fly the Irish flag.

The foundations of Glasgow Celtic were set long before the actual football club was formed (McDougall, 2013). According to McDougall (2013), many Roman Catholic Irish fled to Scotland in 1845 to escape the hunger, poverty and deprivation of the Irish Famine. These Irish immigrants provided the supporter base for the club to be formed in 1888. Burdsey and Chappell (2001) note the UK national census of 1901 revealed that there were 205,000 Irish-born people in Scotland settling mainly in the coal mining areas of the West of Central regions. According to Ross (2005), whilst many football clubs in their formative years identified the opportunities to make money from charging spectators, for Glasgow Celtic - formed by Brother Walfrid, a member of the Catholic Marist Order - the Club was formed to provide assistance to the poor Irish Catholic immigrants living in Glasgow who had fled Ireland during the Great (Irish Potato) Famine (Conner 2014). Brother Walfrid further identified that the money raised by the football club could improve the morale of the Irish community, increase their confidence and keep them within the Catholic faith (Burdsey, and Chappell, 2001), a confidence and morale that had been significantly challenged in the decades prior to the formation of the club. Celtic Football Club's founders were all expatriate Irishmen and the clubs supporters were in the main drawn from the Irish community (Bradley 1998). This community even came together to build a ground in which to play. Celtic

moved to their current ground in Parkhead in the East end of Glasgow in 1892, and in keeping with their Irish identity laid shamrocks from County Donegal in the North West of Ireland in the centre of the turf (Carr, Findley, Hamil, Hill, and Morrow, 2000).

Other Irish football clubs emerged around this time such as Edinburgh Hibernian which was formed in 1875 and consisted initially of a playing staff of only practicing Catholics (Burdsey, and Chappell 2001). Similarly in Dundee, where the Irish immigrant community formed firstly Dundee Harp in 1879, followed by Dundee Hibernian in 1909 (Burdsey, and Chappell 2001), it was the success of Glasgow Celtic in the newly formed Scottish league and other competitions that firmly established and embedded Celtic within the Scottish footballing landscape (Bradley 1995). Whilst Edinburgh Hibernian (now named simply Hibernian) and Dundee Hibernian (now known as Dundee United) continue to play football in Scotland, the changes such as the removal of the harp that dominated the entrance to the ground of Edinburgh Hibernian and the changing of the name and club colours of Dundee Hibernian decreased the association and affinity of both clubs with the local Irish communities during the early years of the 20th Century (Burdsey, and Chappell 2001).

Unlike Celtic, Rangers Football Club began life as a sporting association (Bradley 1995). The club was formed in 1872 in Gareloch and occupied a number of grounds prior to settling at their current ground at Ibrox on the south side of Glasgow in 1899 (Bradley 1995). The early beginnings of the team were unremarkable until towards the latter end of the 19th Century where the success in the Scottish League and cup competitions of Celtic and to a lesser extent Hibernian led to jealousy and resentment amongst many Protestants in Glasgow due to the domination of the Irish 'immigrant' teams (Conner 2014). Whilst all other teams competing in Scotland at the time were

Protestant, the emerging success of Rangers in the last decade of the 19th Century coupled with the emerging rail network enabled supporters of Queens Park and Third Lanark to switch allegiance to Rangers.

This increased support enabled Rangers to become the focus for Protestant identity and resentment of the Irish domination of the game (Bradley 1995) and as a vehicle for the longstanding anti-Irish and anti-Catholic sentiment enhanced by the settled Ulster Protestants who had brought with them from Ireland social and cultural institutions including the Orange Order (Davies 2006). As Walker (1992) notes, established in Ireland in 1795, the Orange Order, a secret mason style Protestant society was committed to the defence of The Crown against Irish rebels who supported a united Ireland. This Protestant identity within the football club was entrenched with the appointment in 1888 of John Ure Primrose as a club patron who was an active Unionist and who formed an allegiance with the Orange Order thereby inexorably linking the club with the traditions of Ulster Protestants (Burdsey, and Chappell 2001). Burdsey & Chappell (2001) further note that Primrose often expressed anti-Irish and anti-Catholic sentiments and assisted in the formation of Clydebank FC as another expressly overtly unionist team. As Deuchar and Holligan (2010) point out, there remains a belief that Rangers continue to represent the ruling classes operating on an anti-Catholic agenda.

Sunshine on Leith

According to Kelly (2007), in any discussion of the Irish diaspora in the 19th and 20th Century and their impact on Scottish football, it would be remiss to ignore or exclude consideration of the impact of Hibernian football club since they were the first 'Irish'

club in Scotland serving an Irish population that made up 30% of the population of Edinburgh's old town by the mid 19th Century. Formed in 1875, the club were fiercely proud of their Irishness and as Kelly (2007) notes, the rules for the new club carried the Irish harp symbol with the motto Erin-Go-Bragh (Ireland Forever) and were named in honour of the Ancient Order of Hibernian (a Catholic secret society dating from 1641). Hibernian, like Celtic, faced significant challenges from the early pioneers of the game in Scotland, initially around gaining admittance to the local Edinburgh football association and the Scottish Football Association primarily as a result of the clubs Irish heritage (Kelly 2007). Again, like Celtic, the resentment of Hibernian was multiplied by early successes on the field (Kelly 2007). Whilst Hibernian were accepted into Scottish football and eventually managed to have players called up to the Scotland team such as the ongoing anti-Irish sentiment, they were not trusted to play against Ireland (Burdsey, and Chappell 2001). To this day, Hibernian remains one of Scotland's most prodigious and best supported teams outside of Glasgow (Kelly & Bairner 2018) winning three first division championships, in four seasons during the club's golden era in the late 1940s and early 1950s and bringing 150,000 supporters to the streets of Edinburgh after the 2016 Scottish Cup victory against Rangers as well as becoming the first British team to compete in the European cup in 1955 (Hibernian Historical Trust 2018).

Of course, no discussion of Hibernian Football Club would be complete without discussion of its 'other' Heart of Midlothian Football Club (known as Hearts). Whilst the historical development of Hibs in Edinburgh mirrors the development of Celtic in Glasgow, Hearts began life much the same way as Rangers with its link to John Hope, a Protestant temperance campaigner and leader of the 3rd Edinburgh Rifle Volunteers

whose membership was restricted to men of good standing. As Kelly and Bairner (2018) note, this good standing was a euphemism for a commitment to Protestant No Popery and abstentionism. Whilst Hibernian and Hearts had similar beginnings to Celtic and Rangers, Kelly and Bairner (2018) suggest that this early history reveals a closer association to sectarianism than the early years of Celtic and Rangers. Despite this, Kelly and Bairner (2018) argue that whilst there remains a sectarian element among the support of Hibs and Hearts, the rivalry is now geographical with the Hibernian support celebrating the district of Leith where the club is situated and Hearts supporters celebrating their links with the City of Edinburgh.

Bigotry and Sectarianism

The anti-Catholic rhetoric of John Hope in Edinburgh and John Ure Primrose in Glasgow coupled with the flood of immigration into Edinburgh and Glasgow inevitably led to tensions particularly within Glasgow that manifested as racism and what we now today as sectarianism (McDougall 2013).

There remains, however, significant debate as to the extent of and even the existence of sectarianism (Raab and Holligan 2012). Whilst Clayton (2005) points to the challenges in actually quantifying and identifying sectarianism, Raab and Holligan (2012) note that significant numbers of residents in Glasgow still believe sectarianism remains a significant issue in modern day Scotland. Given these apparent challenges surrounding sectarianism, it is no surprise that a number of definitions exist as to what sectarianism actually is. One definition is provided by Deuchar and Holligan (2010: 13-14):

“a system of attitudes, actions, beliefs and structures, at personal, communal and institutional levels, which always involves religion, and typically involves a negative mixing of religion and politics”

Clayton (2005 p100) widens the definition by suggesting that sectarianism:

“relates to any activity which involves ‘oppression and exclusion’ of a particular community, which may lead to victimization and ostracism”.

Both definitions involve the consideration of a range of factors. However, in Scotland sectarianism remains primarily and predominantly identified in relation to support for either Rangers or Celtic (Raab, and Holligan 2012). As Clayton (2005) notes, when Rangers and Celtic meet the issue of sectarianism becomes evident and apparent culminating in regular and frequent violent incidents as football, politics and religion become interchangeable. It is a game where despite taking place in Scotland with a predominantly Scottish audience, the flags that are flown illustrate and demonstrate political allegiances with Rangers fans flying the Union flag to demonstrate allegiance to the British Union and Celtic fans flying the Irish tricolour in support of the Catholics of Ireland (Clayton 2005). The political dimension of their games reflects not only the flying of flags but the singing of songs by the Celtic support that commemorate the struggle for Irish independence and the signing of songs by the Rangers fans in support of the loyalists of Northern Ireland.

As Deuchar and Holligan (2010) point out, the roots of sectarianism in Scotland go back further than the histories of both clubs to the defeat of the Jacobite army in 1690

at the Battle of the Boyne which subsequently led to the introduction and enactment of laws that suppressed and marginalised the Irish Catholic population by depriving them of their civil rights. Burdsey & Chappell (2001) however suggest that it was in fact the Reformation of 1560 that rid Scotland of its Catholic culture in favour of the Calvinism of John Knox. This Reformation restricted and isolated Catholics by forcing them into the peripheral regions of Scotland that set the context in which the newly arrived Catholic immigrants in the late 18th/early 19th Century from Ireland therefore found little opportunities to retain ties with their homeland via their faith, language and culture. This faith, language and culture was further restricted following the failed Irish rebellion in 1798 that paved the way for the incorporation of Ireland into Britain and which established the Home Rule movement leading eventually to the formation of the Irish Republican Army (IRA) who fought for the re-establishment of the Irish Republic after partition in 1922 and the formation of the Ulster Volunteer Force (UVF) to resist Home Rule (Deuchar and Holligan 2010). Therefore, according to Deuchar and Holligan (2010), sectarianism is often closely associated with the political issues in Ireland and in particular the period from 1960 to 1998 that defined the Troubles.

Despite the historical precursors including immigration from Ireland and the 'Home Rule' question, Bradley (2015) points out that the term sectarian(ism) was not widely used until the 1980's and 1990's. Indeed as Bradley (2015) observes the term is now predominantly used solely in relation to Celtic and Rangers football clubs. Kelly (2010) points the current discourse in Scotland perpetuated in the main by the media that suggests that both teams are equally culpable of shaping and sustaining sectarianism. Bradley (1996) disagrees with this, suggesting that in fact much of the blame for the current problem of sectarianism is in fact laid at the door of supporters of Glasgow

Celtic as well as those of the Catholic faith who have separated Catholic schools for their continued perceived lack of assimilation into traditional Scottish/British nationhood by their maintenance of Catholic and Irish linkages and heritage (Flint 2012). As an example, Bradley (1996) points to the criticism levelled at Celtic supporters who do not give allegiance to the Scotland national football team, preferring instead the Republic of Ireland.

As Kelly (2010) notes, sectarianism continues to be a problematic term and suggests much that is claimed to be sectarian is in fact anti-Irish racism. As Clayton (2005) highlights, racism exists in Scotland and is often founded upon the perception of the immigrant 'other'. Reid (2008) provides an example of the 'immigrant other' by outlining the media treatment of Neil Lennon, an Irish Catholic who has played for and managed Glasgow Celtic where clear parallels exist with this media narrative despite claims to the contrary. Reid (2008) points out that this failure to equate sectarianism with racism despite apparent and obvious parallels has been referred to as 'Scotland's Shame' (Devine, 2000). As Kelly (2010) concludes, sectarianism in Scotland is not restricted to Celtic and Rangers. Indeed Kelly (2010) suggests that Celtic and Rangers provide a smokescreen in which anti-Irish racism continues to be manifested across Scottish society and not just restricted to football, the West coast of Scotland or predominantly working class men.

Despite this assertion, attempts continue to be made to address sectarianism via legislation that focuses entirely on the language and behaviour of Celtic and Rangers supporters (Waiton, 2018). In opposing such legislation, Waiton (2018, p.169) adopts a social constructionist perspective arguing that sectarianism itself has been created

by the political elite in order to justify and sustain what he refers to as the 'anti-sectarian industry'. Bruce, Glendinning, Paterson & Rosie (2005) agree, suggesting that sectarianism in Scotland is more myth than reality guided purely by perception rather than robust large scale statistical evidence. Walls and Williams (2005) dispute and refute this assertion arguing that Bruce et al (2005) misrepresent the available data illustrating direct discrimination against Catholics in Scotland. Indeed, as Kelly (2010) notes until as late as 1989, Rangers Football Club openly refused to employ Roman Catholics.

Whether sectarianism is myth or reality, McMenemy, Poulter, and O'Loan, (2005) note that street violence linked to football allegiances do occur. McMenemy, et al, (2005) concede that conflict related to sectarianism between supporters of the Old Firm is less destructive or visible than in the North of Ireland or in other areas of the world where issues of religious conflict beget terrorism or war. However, whilst sectarianism is less visible in Scotland, McMenemy, et al, (2005) maintain that it remains a problem and its attachment to the nation's most popular sport means that there is a risk that the association between sectarianism and football will remain in perpetuity. As Williams, Neville, House, and Donnelly (2013) illustrate, sectarianism often culminates in incidences of violence among supporters but also incidences of violence against women. Whilst violence is often associated with the Old Firm, violence at football is not just related to Scotland's two top teams.

Violence and Aggression

As Gibbons, Dixon, and Braye (2008) illustrate, football-related violence is not a new phenomenon. According to Gibbons et al (2008), whilst the 1960's, with increases in permissiveness and the development of youth subcultures, resulted in oppositional behaviour that led to societal concern around football hooliganism, violence related to football has been around since the modern game began in the 1870's. For example, Tranter (1995) describes an incident in 1899 in a local derby game between Greenock Morton and Port Glasgow Athletic as the most serious incident of football violence to occur at a football match in Scotland prior to 1914. Tranter (1995) goes on to note that the incident resulted in a number of pitch invasions and large scale fighting among a group of around 200 supporters. He suggests that the riot was not simply due to divisions related to religion but was also related to class. On one side was the lower working class culture, represented by the supporters of Port Glasgow, and the other was the respectable working class and middle class culture, of Greenock Morton.

In 1898, it was the turn of Celtic and Rangers fans to riot when a fifty thousand crowd overwhelmed the mere forty police officers on duty at Celtic Park, in what McDowell (2013) describes as the first Old Firm disturbance. In 1909, a far more serious riot occurred again between Rangers and Celtic, when the expected extra time was not played in the Scottish Cup final a field invasion of around 6000 spectators took place, with the ensuing riot lasting over two and a half hours resulting in goalposts being used as battering rams, bonfires built on the pitch, 58 police officers and 60 others injured (Vamplew 1980). As McDowell (2013) reminds us, prior to 1902 Celtic and Rangers were far from the dominant clubs in Scotland and were not solely responsible for violence that took place on and off the pitch in relation to Scottish football in its early

years. In fact, as McDowell (2013) and Tranter (1995) both note, the Inverclyde area was the most prolific for crowd disturbances, with early games involving Port Glasgow, Morton and St Mirren regularly being disrupted by pitch invasions on and off field violence. As well as the aforementioned 1899 game, trouble had flared previously at games played in 1897 between Port Glasgow and Morton and Port Glasgow and St Mirren (McDowell 2013). In 1898 in a Port Glasgow and Morton tie, the pitch was again invaded and Morton players were subjected to stone throwing.

Whilst pitch invasions were a common occurrence in the Scottish game in the nineteenth and early twentieth century, McDowell (2013) suggests that these were often precipitated by fighting in the stands since there was no segregation of supporters. As well as pitch invasions, missile throwing by supporters in an attempt to injure players was another common tactic as indeed was players often responding violently to supporters that further incensed them. Vamplew (1980) helpfully suggests that football violence in late Victorian and Edwardian Britain was borne out of and was a result of one of five factors that he describes with the mnemonic 'FORCE' (frustration, Outlawry Disorder, Remonstrance, Confrontation and Expressive). According to Vamplew (1980) many early football riots were a result of supporter's frustration, especially when they saw a particular injustice such as the 1909 Rangers and Celtic game where there was an expectation that extra time was to be played. Outlawry disorder events at football on the other hand occur when spectators who are violence prone use the event to act out their anti-social activities by attacking officials, fighting with rival fans, and destroying property. Remonstrance- related disorder occurred when a section of the crowd used the match for an expression of a political grievance. McDowell (2013) helpfully provides examples of this remonstrative

behaviour citing several protests during an 1896 tour of Scotland by London's British Ladies Football Club who played against male teams with a match in Glasgow ending with the women's team being chased from the field and objects being thrown at their carriages as they left.

As McDowell (2013) continues, these matches were viewed by the press at the time as subverting Victorian feminine identity as well as threatening male privilege. Confrontation on the other hand occurred in local derbies among supporters with different ethno religious or socioeconomic backgrounds. Finally, Vamplew (1980) suggests that the expressive crowd disturbances occurred due to intense emotion among the crowd that accompanied a victory or a defeat, particularly if the result was unexpected. Despite, disturbances occurring at football matches throughout its history, it was not until the 1980's that significant media and Government attention was given to the issue resulting in significant academic research in the area (Gibbons et al 2008).

Studies ranging from the 1970's through to the 1990's proposed a variety of explanations for football hooliganism. According to Gibbons et al (2008), early studies in this genre such as those by Taylor (1971, 1982) and Hargreaves (1986) adopted a Marxist perspective suggesting that football violence was a working class phenomenon in opposition to the growing commodification of football. Other studies of the time (Marsh, 1978; Marsh, Rosser, and Harré 1978) suggest again it was a working class phenomenon but was due to a need to release aggression. Moorhouse (1984, 1991) disagrees with these essentially Marxist perspectives, suggesting that football violence occurs across all socioeconomic groups and in fact occurs equally

among middle class spectators living in relatively prosperous areas. Indeed, Moorhouse (1984) points to Scotland where the period after 1960 led to significant socioeconomic disadvantage but very little 'hooliganism' occurred out with the 'Old Firm' encounters. Studies such as Elias and Dunning (1986) concluded that 'hooliganism' was a quest for excitement via the exhibition of risk-taking behaviour. Gibbons et al (2008) conclude with later ethnographic studies (Armstrong and Harris 1991, Armstrong 1998) conducted in the 1990's that suggested that this violence was in defence of the club or the towns reputation or that by engaging with this gang provided a sense of belonging and/or shaming rivals.

Conclusion

Football in Scotland is interwoven into the fabric of Scottish society, its development mirrored and reflected and, indeed, continues to reflect the challenges and issues prevalent in modern day Scotland. I have illustrated how football in Scotland has throughout its development been used by some men to construct their masculine identity. Whilst the widespread crowd disorder of the late 19th early 20th Centuries are now largely a thing of the past, displays of aggression and violence at football games remains an issue (O'Neill, 2004). As Williams, et al (2013) point out, immediately following a match between Celtic and Rangers there is a statistically significant rise in reports of domestic abuse. As Messner and Sabo (1994) highlight, sport breeds intolerant men who are prone to violence and domestic abuse.

Whilst some men in Scotland utilise football, aggression and violence to construct their masculinity, some other men construct their identity via open displays of racism at

football via sectarian chanting, banners and flags. As Deuchar and Holligan (2010) highlight, the bigotry evident at football games, provide some men with an avenue to create their masculine identity. Deuchar and Holligan (2010) further note that despite the ending of 'The Troubles' in the North of Ireland on which much of sectarianism was based, affiliation to Celtic or Rangers continues to be passed down from father to son. This is viewed by some fathers as a means of ensuring their son's hard man image and avoiding the possibility of him being gay.

CHAPTER 4: BEING A FOOTBALLER

Introduction

Unlike many other careers, becoming a professional footballer is distinct and separate as it is a career that doesn't feature in the repertoire of many schools' career advisors (Bourke, 2002). It is a career path where significant numbers fail at an early age and it is a career that can be over by the time a player enters their mid-30's (Grossmann, and Lames 2015).

Whilst according to Bourke (2002), the vast majority of young men choose a career in football for the love of the game, Bourke (2002) notes that the possibility of fame and fortune remains a factor in choosing football. This possibility of achieving fame and fortune within football is remote however as the supply of young footballers with this ambition of seeking fame fortune and recognition within the game exceeds the demand of the elite clubs. As Bennett, Vaeyens and Fransen (2019) point out, with 250 million players worldwide, the odds of significant success within the game remain extremely low. However, with wages in the upper tier of English football averaging in excess of £400,000 per annum it is understandable why in the study by Bourke (2002) over 75% of the young footballers questioned retaining the ambition to play for a top tier English club. For young players playing the game however, the route to the pinnacle of the game either in England or within other top tier leagues such as Germany is constrained. For example, in Germany Bennett et al (2019), note that there are around 6.6 million people playing the game, so an aspiring professional footballer in Germany faces a considerable barrier in their quest to the top never mind an aspiring footballer from out with the country. Grossmann and Lames (2015) further note that

only around 10% of young German men playing for development teams actually go on to sign a full professional contract with a senior German league team with around 45% actually giving up the game entirely. Given the levels of local available talent, Bennett et al (2019), highlight that an aspiring footballer from out with the top elite nations faces additional barriers in their quest for fame and fortune. Not only will the elite nations have an extensive talent pool, they also have the financial resources with which to develop this available pool. Grossmann and Lames (2015) helpfully provide stark statistical data that quantifies the challenge for a young footballer seeking to play in an elite league by noting that of all the aspiring football players born in 1993 only five players who are currently playing senior German football were born outside the country.

BECOMING THE BEST

The identification of talent has been described as,

“The process of recognizing current participants with the potential to become elite players” (Williams and Reilly, 2000, p.658).

Bennett et al (2019) however point out that talent itself is not a universally understood and accepted concept with pre-set and predetermined characteristics. Despite this, a range of multi-dimensional approaches such as physical, physiological, technical, and mental qualities are regularly utilised by physiology, biomechanics and sport psychology to predict future success and often dominate the field of talent identification (Lund, and Söderström 2017). Whilst agreeing that the complexity of football requires

that teams recruit players with a range of qualities that require a number of criteria be considered in identifying which youth players have the potential to develop into elite players and which do not, Lund and Söderström (2017) challenge the assumption that young players' transition into elite players can be predicted via the use of general models. For example, Lund and Söderström (2017) note that there is strong evidence that the Relative Age Effect (RAE) is a widely used criteria by coaches in talent identification. Put simply, RAE suggests that players born earlier in the year are more likely to be more physically mature than players born later in the year thereby holding an advantage in the maturity/physicality criteria utilised and favoured by many coaches. In fact, Lund and Söderström (2017) note that players born earlier in the year were four times more likely to be selected for Sweden's under 16 youth team than their younger counterparts.

Similarly Bertomeu (2018) found the RAE in operation in Argentina where those having an early birth were more likely to progress to a full professional career than those born later in the year. Such is the widespread use of RAE that Bertomeu (2018) found evidence of its use in talent identification in Spanish football, German football, French football, Belgian football and Australian football despite little evidence existing that physical maturity equates to increased skill or greater talent (Hill and Sotiriadou 2016). Lund and Söderström (2017) conclude, therefore, that rather than judging which players have the potential to develop into elite levels, coaches tend to focus on seeing the best players at that moment. Lund and Söderström (2017) therefore provide further challenge to the assumption that talent identification can be made into a rational and objective process since such a model fails to take account of those experiences and insights of the coaches themselves particularly given the assertion by Cushion and

Jones (2006) that players may progress to a full professional contract purely by gaining status as a coaches favourite by displaying the attitudes required. Potrac, Jones and Cushion (2007) suggest that a better understanding of the means and methods employed by coaches is therefore required. By doing this, Potrac, et al (2007) propose it will lead to better coach education and thereby ultimately improve performance by players. Clarke, Cushion, and Harwood (2018) provide a further illustration of the subjective and socially constructed nature of talent identification via an exploration of how young players make sense of being talented. As Clarke, et al (2018) assert, for some young players the simple act of being chosen for or choosing an academy enhanced their talent identities.

The Football Academy

As Cushion and Jones (2006) point out, a place within an academy is now generally considered a prerequisite for a professional career. As Wilson (2017) highlights, the football academy is now seen as a major pathway in developing young players and that even within the wider sports environment, transitioning from talented youth footballer to full professional footballer is regarded as the most difficult and complex (Larsen, Alfermann, Henriksen and Christensen 2014). According to Wilson (2017), these football academies seek to develop young players in order that they are able to progress within the football club to first team level and save the club money on transfer fees or be sold to another team and bring in income for the club. Indeed, such is the importance placed upon football academies that the governing body of football in Europe, the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA), has exempted spending on youth development from its financial fair play regulations that limit spending by

senior clubs in order to encourage increased investment in home grown youth development (Wilson, 2017). Mills, Butt, Maynard and Harwood (2014) highlight the advantages of the football academies and contend that the development of young footballers and their potential future success is largely shaped by their environmental experience. Whilst Mills et al (2014) concede that whilst actual future success will be defined by a range of factors such as resilience and confidence, these factors will be meaningless without the provision of an appropriate environment.

Mills et al (2014) highlight that some coaches now promote active learning that includes problem solving type drills and coach player dialogue as opposed to the traditional passive learning coaching style where players were taught to 'soak up' learning like a sponge. Despite this, Cushion and Jones (2006) reminds us that the football academy continues to operate via an authoritarian discourse that is legitimised and accepted by the players. For Parker and Manley (2017) this authoritarian discourse is often prevalent throughout the academy via its bureaucratic hierarchical structures. Cushion and Jones (2006) helpfully provide some examples as to how this authoritarian discourse is manifested either via abusive language or specific threats or even the challenge to a player's masculinity that reflects the notion of the hegemonic form of gender construction prevalent within football. Manley, Palmer, and Roderick (2012) describe other methods of control utilised in what Parker (1996) likens to Goffman's (1961) definition of a 'total institution' given the enclosed and formally structured existence that young players inhabit. According to Manley, et al (2012) the organisation uses a range of surveillance techniques such as fitness testing, physiological testing, and video analysis. Manley, et al (2012) suggest that by reducing the players to numbers, it illustrates how docile bodies are constructed through the

imposition of surveillance. Manley, et al (2012) provide further exploration of how this surveillance is used within the academy to exert control by noting that the football club instil an athletic identity among the players, via the creation of one dimensional athletic identity centred on the ambition to succeed forsaking all other goals and interests. Manley, et al (2012) conclude that data collected is utilised to construct this identity by highlighting failures such as weight gain or a drop in fitness to encourage players to work harder. MacKenzie and Cushion (2013) provide further challenge to the usefulness and value of surveillance data utilised in performance analysis, by questioning whether in fact even within the positivist paradigm that it operates in, it provides the desired outcomes in respect of performance. Despite this, as Parker (2006) points out the strategies that are employed within football clubs to maintain order and social control are often viewed as central to the effective working of a football club and have even received some acclaim within the game.

Deselection and release

As McGillivray and McIntosh (2006) note, becoming an elite professional player requires significant sacrifices. Despite this, around 25% of professional players are released by clubs in Scotland each year due to the political, social and economic environment that exists in Scottish football (McGillivray, and McIntosh 2006). In England, around 10% of professionals leave the game each year (Gearing, 1999). For youth players, competing for a professional contract, the figures are even starker with the failure rate estimated to be around 85% (Brown, and Potrac 2009).

Brown and Potrac (2009) highlight that footballers may be released (required to leave) from clubs for a variety of reasons that include as a result of injury or deselection by not meeting the clubs expected levels of performance. Gearing (1999) points out that, whilst some ex-players are able to remain within the game as managers or media commentators, this option is not available to most. Despite an average life in football only amounting to eight and a half years, the conclusion of a career for whatever reason is met with a sense of considerable loss (Gearing 1999). As Brown and Potrac (2009) explain, the loss experienced by players who are forced out of the game is a loss of their identity. This loss of identity developed via the peculiar and unique formal and semi-enclosed structure of a football club (Gearing 1999) can, according to Brown and Potrac (2009) result in anxiety, depression, anger, low self-esteem and even a feeling of humiliation, despite, as McGillivray, and McIntosh (2006) suggest, that there exists a recognition by the footballers themselves that they are merely embodied assets within a game that cares little about their long term future.

This loss of self-esteem is perhaps unsurprising as Brown and Potrac (2009) describe the heightened level of self-esteem gained by recognition of their talent by peers, parents and their coaches. The particular feelings attributed to loss of identity are explored further by Gearing (1999) who describes the particular elements of the game that contribute to the loss of the athletic identity. Gearing (1999) highlights that for some professional footballers the excitement of the game itself provides an almost intoxicating effect that he likens to the high of drug use. Additionally, Gearing (1999) notes that on leaving the game some players miss the camaraderie involved in football such as the dressing room banter, the joking, and the pranks that contribute to bonding within the team that create a sense of togetherness. In coping with this loss that

Gearing (1999) suggests is similar to bereavement, he defines two specific groups of players, those whose careers end naturally and those whose careers are end prematurely. For those whose careers end prematurely such as the 85% of youth players, Brown, and Potrac (2009) suggest that they are more likely to experience much more pronounced emotional difficulties particularly if they have developed a high level of athletic identity.

Lifelong learning

Whist Brown and Potrac (2009) highlight that the development of a strong athletic identity can produce positive outcomes such as continued adherence to sport and exercise in the long term and a positive impact on athletic performance, individuals with a strong sense of athletic identity are less likely to explore or engage in alternative lifestyle opportunities such as educational programmes. As Clarke, Cushion, and Harwood (2018) point out that even for younger players who train part time as they are still likely to be in full time education struggle with the competing demands of sport and education, ultimately adopting an athletic identity in order to give 100% to football. As McGillivray, et al (2005) in their study within Scottish professional football found, 64% of players that they surveyed left school aged 16 or under. Given that according to Parker (2000) young players just see it as inevitable that they will achieve full time football, education is therefore dismissed as irrelevant. Whilst the need to dedicate 100% to football has been suggested as a reason for the lack of engagement in educational opportunities (Clarke, et al 2018), others highlight the potential impact of class (Parker 2000; McGillivray, et al 2005). With the majority of footballers being predominantly working class, education is allegedly viewed within a middle class

framework so it is something that is unachievable whilst football is achievable (McGillivray, et al 2005). Parker (2000), offers another possible and connected explanation as to why young players disengage with education as for many young people, football provides a reflection of the manual labour that is inherent within their masculine identity construction.

As a result of a lack of engagement with education, many footballers leave the game lacking the necessary skills required in order to obtain alternative employment (Gearing 1999). McGillivray and McIntosh (2006) suggest, however, that the precarious economic position within Scottish football is changing attitudes of players. In maintaining these changing attitudes McGillivray and McIntosh (2006) highlight the benefit of what they describe as 'learner representatives' who are professional footballers themselves and are more likely to be listened to by younger players. Furthermore, in sustaining engagement with educational opportunities, McGillivray and McIntosh (2006) suggest that these opportunities must be fun, non-coercive and the players themselves must see the benefit. It is only via this transformational change within the game that will allow players to construct multiple identities as opposed to the singular athletic one that is currently prevalent.

Conclusion

In this chapter, I have set out the journey of young football players from initial talent identification through life at the academy and the journey out of football. Whilst a life in football forms a relatively short period in life only averaging around eight years, it is a time describe by Levinson (1978) as terminating pre-adulthood and beginning early adulthood where young men develop their sense of self (Gearing 1999). The notion of

football as a total institution as described by Parker, and Manley (2017) creates for these young men a sense of self where the masculine identity of aggressiveness and physical prowess intertwine with their professional identity contributing to a prolonging of adolescence for some which is retained upon leaving football, which then may impact upon their next period of life leaving many unprepared and unskilled for life after football (Gearing 1999). The unpreparedness of players for life after football has been recognised (Gearing 1999), and whilst educational opportunities are provided and players encouraged to engage, the athletic identity prevents many players from engaging (Parker 2000; McGillivray and McIntosh 2006). As Brown, and Potrac (2009) highlight, with as many as 85% of young footballers not progressing to full professional status and with the potential impact that this has on the young players' wellbeing much more requires to be done.

McGillivray and McIntosh (2006) note that footballers' unwillingness to engage in offered opportunities for further education is not merely the fault of football itself where the masculinised culture rejects education as effeminate as some authors claim (Gearing 1999). Nor does the blame lie purely at the door of the football clubs themselves as other authors claim (Kremer et al., 1997; Coakley and Pike 2014, 1998; Whannel, 2002) but both share responsibility (McGillivray and McIntosh 2006). In doing more to prepare players for life after football, Jones, Glintmeyer and McKenzie (2005) propose that coaches should help to develop athletes develop multiple identities rather than the singular athletic identity, whilst for Clarke, Harwood, and Cushion, (2016) some of the responsibility lies out with football and lies with parents. In supporting young players in preparing for life after football by developing multiple

identities, any changes must not only have support from the hierarchy within football, but must also be incremental and flexible (McGillivray and McIntosh 2006).

CHAPTER 5: RESEARCH METHODS

Introduction

This chapter provides an outline of the design of the research itself, describing in detail the research strategy and the rationale for its adoption of this particular approach. The chapter also describes the methods employed within the strategy as well as describing the stages utilised to ensure that the research was robust.

The fieldwork was conducted over the course of a football season (August 2014 - May 2015) at Burncastle Football Club. During the season, I attended two training sessions per week (two hours per session) where I was able to observe the players' coaching routines by shadowing the coaching staff. Following the conclusion of formal coaching drills and routines, I had access to the coach's team talk that concluded these sessions. On match days which were typically on a Sunday morning I was permitted access to the players' dressing room prior to the match, at half time and at full time. During a match itself, I observed the game from the side of the pitch beside the coaches and the team substitutes. In addition to the collection of data during training and on match days, semi structured interviews were conducted with 15 of the male professional youth players following the final training session of the season.

Research Paradigms

This research was qualitative in nature which according to Creswell (2009) is an inquiry that explores a social or human problem. Hazzan & Nutov (2014) explore the nature of this problem more widely and suggest that qualitative research seeks to understand people and their behaviour in a social, cultural and economic context. This distinguishes it from quantitative research that Duffy (1987) suggests is based on

positivist epistemology and emphasises the search for the facts and causes of human behaviour through objective, observable and quantifiable data. Within this quantitative paradigm, there is only one truth, existing independently of human perception with the researcher acting as an objective scientist whose main tasks are to manipulate the external environment and observe the effects on the subjects. This objectivity therefore allows the researcher to study a phenomenon without influencing it or being influenced by it (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). It allows the researcher to discover or reveal knowledge by selecting a set of variables established as hypotheses and to collect data pertaining to them since all the research is doing is uncovering an existing reality.

Therefore, Bryman (2015) helpfully suggests that, in effect, quantitative and qualitative research differ in respect of the general orientation to the conduct of the research which he refers to as the research strategy. This research strategy is defined by Bryman (2015) as the consideration of the connection between ontological considerations (the nature of social entities) and epistemological considerations (the question of what is regarded as acceptable knowledge). Ontological considerations, according to Bryman (2015), are focussed primarily around whether or not social reality exists independently and is external to social actors who have no control over it. Conversely, this social world can be viewed as an entity that is in a constant process of reformulation as social actors modify it through their practices. These two opposing ontological positions are often referred to as objectivism and constructionism (Bryman 2015). Whilst objectivism, with its roots in realism and essentialism, posits the existence of a world, external to humans and independent of human experience, and relies on the existence of reliable knowledge about the world that we strive to gain, constructionism claims that reality is more in the mind of the knower. The knower

therefore constructs a reality (or at least interprets it) based on his or her perceptions (Jonassen, 1991) with Burr (1995) suggesting that all knowledge is derived from looking at the world from some perspective or other. In fact, as Burr (2005) highlights our knowledge and understanding of the world is made by the daily interactions between people in the course of their life through language and social experiences. Therefore, our current understanding of the 'truth' (accounting for variations across cultures and historical time periods), and the accepted social behaviours and understandings of our environment are the product of these interactions and social processes in which people engage with each other. Snape & Spencer (2003) further suggest that most contemporary qualitative researchers now believe that the laws that govern the social world are not in fact immutable and therefore most qualitative research now adopts a constructionist ontological philosophical position.

The deep-rooted philosophical differences between qualitative and quantitative design therefore begin with different worldviews. These different worldviews then dictate the methodological approach adopted (Morse, and McEvoy 2014). Since the current study established the meaning of a phenomenon from the view point of the participants, by studying things in their natural setting (Denzin & Lincoln 2005) as opposed to testing theory by specifying narrow hypotheses and the collection of data to support or refute the hypotheses (Creswell 2009), it adopted a constructionist position. Furthermore, by seeking to understand human behaviour rather than explain it, this thesis is interpretivist in its epistemological orientation.

In conducting research, as well as the philosophical consideration of how the social world is viewed (ontology) a further philosophical question arises as to what is or should be regarded as acceptable knowledge. Clarke (2001) suggests that there are

essentially two divergent and opposing views often described as positivist and interpretivist. These opposing views as to what is or should be regarded as acceptable knowledge and how it can be acquired are referred to as an epistemological consideration. Clarke (2001) suggests that in the positivist epistemology, there exists an objective external world independent of human perception which is amenable to quantitative measurement by following a scientific model of enquiry with the key aim of collecting facts about society and statistically analysing these facts in order to produce an explanation of how the social world operates.

As this study established the meaning of a phenomenon from the views of the participant (Creswell 2009) then a question arises as to whether this particular view of the social world can be studied using the same principles and rules of the natural sciences where knowledge within a positivist paradigm is only acceptable if it can be tested through the use of empirical evidence (Gray, 2009). Bryman (2015) further outlines the key methodological concerns within this positivist quantitative paradigm, specifically the requirement to ensure and maintain objectivity, causality and replicability. Causality is, according to Bryman (2015), more about describing why things are the way they are rather than merely describing the way things are. The positivist researcher will therefore seek to examine and explain the causes of a phenomenon, much like the researcher in the natural sciences. The removal or reduction of the scientists' contaminating influences should lead, according to Bryman (2015), to the ability to replicate and reproduce the results from different scientists. Bryman (2015) therefore argues that taking a position that believes that, since human beings think and reflect, then scientific methods are inappropriate for the study of society particularly as the researcher as a human is inevitably part of the very social

relationships they are exploring and it is therefore impossible for science to be completely objective or detached (Elias, 1987). Therefore, if we want to understand social action, we have to delve into the reasons and meanings which that action has for people; this requires a different logic of research procedure.

Mason (2002) highlights that adopting an interpretivist epistemological approach allows us to see people, their interpretations, meanings and understandings as the primary data sources as well as seeking their perceptions rather than imposing an outsider view. As Bryman (2015) further notes, the interpretivist epistemological position is underpinned by an inductive approach where the theory is generated by the research as opposed to within the positivist paradigm underpinned by a deductive approach outlined by Bryman (2015 p13) where,

“the purpose of theory is to generate hypotheses that can be tested and that will thereby allow explanations of laws to be assessed”.

Research Methods

In seeking to explore and understand the research questions under consideration, ethnographic methods of qualitative research were adopted. Ethnography has been defined by Humphries & Watson (2009 p40) as,

“a written account of the cultural life of a social group, organisation or community which may focus on a particular aspect of life in that setting”.

Adopting an ethnographic approach to methods brings the researcher and the subjects of the inquiries into close contact interactionally and, often, emotionally (Shover 2012)

and therefore allows the researcher to build a complex, holistic picture, analyse words, reports, and detailed views of informants, by conducting the study in a natural setting (Cresswell 2009). Indeed, this contact between the researcher and the subjects of the study in the natural setting is a key element of ethnographic methods of research (Bell 2010), since according to Taylor (1993) it is about getting in where the action is and telling it like it is. Woods (1991) parallels ethnography with the work of the documentary film producer reader, who tries to convey to the audience a deeper insight of the subject group peeling away at the layers of complexity. The documentary film-maker tries to get under the skin of the subjects without losing the ability to appraise objectively.

As well as conducting research in a natural setting, ethnography is often defined by its participative role with the researcher often engaging in the customs and practices of the group (Woods 1991, Taylor 1993, Hammersley & Atkinson 2019, Bell 2010) thereby seeking to share the same experiences of the group and to understand better why they act in the way they do.

Ethnographic research can often be difficult to define because it is used in different ways in different disciplines with different traditions (O'Reilly 2005). This difficulty is complicated by the overlap ethnographic research has with other terminology used in social research and may well be as a result of the confusion around the role and function of ethnography although Harrison (2014) is abundantly clear that ethnography is a distinct methodology rather than a method. Harrison (2014) makes it clear that a method is simply a technique or tool used to collect data. Therefore, ethnographic methods focus attention on the use in research of direct observation, semi-structured

personal interviews, or the collection and analysis of life histories, diaries and other personal documents (Shover 2012) but its unique and defining nature is its aim of, for example, uncovering beliefs, values, perspectives, and motivations from within the group (Hammersley and Atkinson 2019). While questioning, observing and recording in the field with the aim of uncovering beliefs, values, perspectives, motivations and so on, from within the group, ethnographic research may also involve the researchers learning and speaking the language of the group, learning the customs of the group, learning the nuances and customs of the group, in effect, becoming a member of the group (Woods 1991).

In summary, ethnographic research can perhaps be best defined by its participative nature. As a participant the researcher is therefore best placed to understand and therefore able to interpret the relationship between all the characteristics and elements that help define the group or culture under study and ultimately tell their story. Such is the importance of this participatory role within ethnography, Shah (2017) describes it as a revolutionary praxis since it may well produce new knowledge as well as potentially allowing us to question our preconceived perceptions about the world that surrounds us. Indeed Malinowski, whom Harrison (2014) described as the founding father of the ethnographic approach, himself makes this point suggesting that the researcher entering the field with preconceived ideas and theories may well become illuminated by their findings (Malinowski 1932).

From Theory to Practice

We noted earlier that we defined ethnography predominantly by its participative role with the researcher often engaging in the customs and practices of the group. We assume that the participant observation is observation carried out when the researcher is playing an established participant role in the scene studied with non-participant observation being the opposite. However, Atkinson and Hammersley (1994) contend that this dichotomy of roles is not helpful since it suggests that the non-participant observer plays no recognised role when in fact it is impossible to study the social world without being part of it. In recognition of this, I adopted the widely used fourfold typology developed by Gold (1958),

- *The complete observer*, who maintains some distance, does not interact and whose role is concealed
- *The complete participant*, who interacts within the social situation, but again whose role is concealed
- *The observer as participant*, who undertakes intermittent observation alongside interviewing, but whose role is known
- *The participant as observer*, who undertakes prolonged observation, is involved in all the central activities of the group and whose role is known.

This typology is helpful in understanding the number of roles that I adopted during this study. However, prior to conducting any field work I required access to a football club. I was mindful of the work of Parker (2006) who by highlighting the hierarchical and authoritarian nature of football clubs meant that I required to make initial contact with someone who was in charge. Fortunately for me, someone with whom I work closely

in my day to day job acted in his spare time as a director of the youth academy. After informal contact via email with this director I was invited to a meeting some weeks after with other directors to outline the purpose of the research to them. In doing so, I provided them with a research outline and explained its purpose.

As Reeves (2010) notes, gatekeepers perform a crucial function in accessing a site since they can be either a help or a hindrance to the researcher depending on their views as to the validity of the research or their duty to protect the welfare of the people under their charge. Permission was granted in principle for access to the players but the hierarchical and authoritarian nature of football required further permission from team management that included the youth head coach and the first team manager whom Mulhall (2003) describes as informal gatekeepers and also need to be approached before access is given. Again, I was required to outline the purpose and nature of the research to them. With no one in the youth academy structure receiving payment for their involvement, permission was ultimately granted by the team management structure on condition that I assisted to ensure the smooth running of the academy as far as my capabilities were able to. It is therefore useful here to examine the roles I undertook in relation to the typology outlined earlier by Gold (1958).

Specifically, I acted as the team bus driver for driving the team to away fixtures across Scotland being recognised within the typology as 'the observer as participant' where as team bus driver I could interact with the team whilst maintaining detachment due to the role as driver. During training sessions, however, I assisted the coaches in handing out training bibs and collecting them in again, collecting cones and balls and other general support activities such as moving equipment and so on. As such, during these training sessions I was identified as 'participant as observer' within the Gold (1958)

typology as I was actively involved in the operation of the team and its functioning. Whilst travelling to matches and at training sessions, I adopted one particular role and function as defined within the typology devised by Gold (1958), on match days, itself, I moved between differing roles. Prior to the match, I assisted the coaches by setting out the match day strips for the players' arrival, transporting team lines to the referee and setting out half time and full time drinks and snacks I adopted the role of 'participant as observer'. However, during the match itself, I adopted the role of complete observer when observing supporters of the football club and the opposition team and officials observing from the touchline of the pitch.

In conducting these tasks for the club, I was mindful of what Reeves (2010) describes as establishing rapport given the power the gatekeepers had over the research. Furthermore, Reeves (2010) suggests that whilst the establishment of positive relationships will ensure continued access to the field, it will enable the researcher to gather rich and detailed data. This positive rapport was developed over the course of the football season from August 2014 – May 2015 where I attended two training sessions per week for approximately 25 weeks. I also attended 20 games played by the team during the season. The level of my attendance allowed me to become a 'regular fixture' around the club meaning that the players and coaches got to know me and accepted my presence there.

It is through the establishment of rapport, Reeves (2010) suggests, that rich data can be gained. Mulhall (2003) suggests, however, that the typology of Gold (1958) may not be that useful nowadays as it involves elements of covert research whereas people have the right to privacy and to know they are part of a study and whilst investigators

have no special privileges, ethical considerations were particularly relevant with this study.

Ethical considerations

Ethics are a key issue within all research. As O'Reilly (2005) notes, ethnographic research may be considered inherently unethical since we are moving into people's lives, watching them, questioning them, analysing them and maybe even being critical of what they say and do. Hammersely and Atkinson (2007) recognise that, despite the best intentions of the ethnographer to give people the opportunity to decline to be observed, it is not always possible, at least not without making the research highly disruptive or rendering it impossible. Indeed, in this research, spectators at football matches, the match officials and the opposition teams were observed covertly without consent since obtaining their consent would have proved highly disruptive and the obtaining of consent was impractical.

Gobo (2008) concurs by arguing that in this instance covert observation is not unethical since the researcher is acting in a non - participant observer role or indeed complete observer (Junker 1960) and therefore maintains a certain distance. Gobo (2008) further suggests that situations where covert data collection is accepted are venues such as stadia. Gobo (2008) additionally suggests that this is the case for the opposition players and match officials who are performing a public function, and therefore their work is aimed at satisfying the customer whether or not this is the researcher. Given this role, Gobo (2008) argues it is not unethical to conduct covert observation in certain circumstances. In addition, since the researcher in the field was conducting the research in natural settings such as a football stadium, the control that

the researcher had over the research process was limited, the researcher simply did not have the power to ensure that all participants were fully informed or that they freely consented despite the involvement of the gatekeepers.

It was my intention therefore to be completely overt and to engage all participants in a process of informed consent. As Plankey-Videla (2012) remarks, ensuring informed consent is an ongoing process and does not just end with the permission of the gatekeeper which is why participants were informed verbally and were provided with an information sheet detailing the focus and nature of the project before being asked to sign a consent form confirming their voluntary participation. The young men were also informed that at an early stage before, during or after the interview they were free to withdraw from the research without consequence. I decided to only interview participants once as I was mindful that Gusterson (2008) advised not to interview the same subject twice as the purpose of this ethnographic research was not one of sampling or seeking to elicit a stable pre-existing reality that is characterised within a positivist paradigm. Rather, as Gusterson (2008) notes, my purpose was, through these dynamic events, for participants to perform themselves in response to particular lines of questioning.

The participant information sheet and consent form is attached as appendix 1. Prior to undertaking the research, the researcher was subjected to a records search under the terms laid out in The Protection of Vulnerable Groups (Scotland) Act 2007 to ensure the safety and protection of these young men. This need for informed consent needs to be balanced against the researcher's needs to fit in and become unobtrusive (O Reilly, 2005). While some of the young people in this research were not concerned

with being named in public documents, the decision was nevertheless made to protect their privacy. As such participants' names have not been printed in this thesis, nor in any wider reports, journal articles, or conference presentations and proceedings resulting from this research. Instead, throughout this thesis the names of players, coaches and the team itself have been changed to protect this privacy.

The University of The West of Scotland Ethics Committee granted approval for this research in October 2012.

Meet the Participants

Burncastle Football Club is over 100 years old and like many clubs out with the top elite teams has seen better days. The training pitch, where the majority of the observations took place, is therefore situated in a local school within the town away from the 'main ground'. The pitches, are open for public use during the evening but the club has an ongoing booking with the local authority over use. The school training pitches are occasionally used by the first team as well.

Michael is 18 years of age, but still in full time education at school. He has been with Burncastle for the past three years. Michael has played for one of the two Glasgow clubs as well as a junior club. Michael's father has a footballing background having played football in the junior leagues before retiring.

James is 18 years of age and is still at school. James has only played for Burncastle for two years having signed straight from school team. James has no one in the family involved in football. Whilst he would like to have a professional career in football, he has been accepted for a university place after Summer.

Paul is 18 years of age and attends college on a part time basis studying sports science. Paul comes from a footballing family as his father played professional football for another lower league team in Scotland. Paul's brother played amateur football before receiving serious injury that ended his footballing career.

Fraser is 17 years of age and been with Burncastle for past 2 years after being released by senior Scottish club after 3 years with them having signed from school.

Dougie is 18 years of age and first year with Burncastle after spells playing for three senior professional clubs. Is hoping that the disappointment of being released by senior clubs will provide a springboard for him in a lower league.

Derek is 17 years old just finished school and fits football around a part time job. Joined the club from a local boys club having been signed from school. Derek is the first in his family to play football at a serious level

Ian is 18 years old and at university. Currently lives in Glasgow having signed from a Glasgow club and travels for training and matches. Ian is In last year of the professional youth ranks and if not selected for reserves/first team soon may give up to concentrate on academic career.

Alan has just turned 18 and been playing with the club for 3 years now. Alan is full time with the club and attends college to study sports science through the club. Alan has featured on the substitute's bench for the first team and has played for the reserve first

team. Alan more often trains with the first team and hopes that he will make first team appearances soon to support his development towards hopefully signing for a more senior team.

Craig is currently 17 and from a 'sporting' family where his mum plays netball at International level. Craig like his father is a low handicap golfer and was given a choice whether to pursue golf as a career. Craig decided to pursue football following signing for Burncastle two years ago.

Scott is 18 years old and following in brothers footsteps after brother played for the club managing several appearances for the first team before stepping down into junior (semi-professional) level. Scott has been with club for three years, as he is not currently in employment, education or training, Scott focusses purely on his football hoping that football will be a viable career.

Neil is currently 17 years of age, still at school from a football family with dad, brother and uncle having played the game at amateur/junior level.

Jack is currently 18 years old and played for a number of local boys/amateur teams before joining Burncastle around three years ago. He attends college part time studying sport and is sponsored at college by the club. He had been training regularly with the first team prior to a leg injury that kept him out of football for around 6-8 months. Jack is hoping that by training and playing with the youth team will result in a quick return to the first team. Jack is another full time youth player within the club.

Sean is 18 years of age and has just returned to the club having spent several months on loan with a professional club in England. Is on a professional contract with Burncastle unlike the majority of the other pro youth players, and has ambition to move up the Scottish league with another club.

Gerard has just turned 17 years old and is in first year with club having signed from a local community boys club. Gerard attends school full time and would like to go to university or college to do sports science but would consider giving this up as he sees a football career as his first priority.

Johnnie is currently 18 years old and has played football most of his life having been encouraged by his dad who currently is still playing football for a local junior team. Hoping to sign a professional contract with the club upon leaving school this year.

Field Notes

In ethnographic research, field notes perform a vital role (Wolfinger 2002), and according to Bryman (2015) can take various forms from mental notes, that are useful when it is inappropriate to be seen taking notes, jotted notes (or scratch notes) that contain phrases, quotes, key words that are used to jog the researcher's memory later and finally full field notes. Whilst mental notes and jotted notes may only capture minor detail, Fine (1993) provides reassurance suggesting that it is almost impossible to record the exact words of a conversation. Instead of being what Fine (1993) describes as the 'precise ethnographer', he suggests that the role of the participant observer is more akin to that of the playwright who seeks to reconstruct the scene for the insight of the reader. As well as being unable to record the precise detail of a conversation,

the ethnographer will be unable to be fully observant since Patton (2002) notes that it is impossible to observe everything. Fine (1993) even suggests that what we have observed may possibly be missing a crucial detail and that what we depict may not be the whole picture.

Whilst field notes will not provide a precise, full or comprehensive account of a scene, they should contain the feelings and reactions of the researcher (Patton 2002) since according to Emerson, Fretz and Shaw (2011), no field researcher can be a completely neutral, detached observer, outside and independent of the observed phenomena. Indeed, as Emerson et al (2011) further notes, in learning about others through active participation in their lives and activities, the fieldworker cannot and should not attempt to be a fly on the wall since, according to Patton (2002), part of the purpose of being in a setting and getting close to the people in the setting is to allow you to experience what it is like to be in that setting.

Field notes in this study were collected at the 50 training sessions I attended (from late August to beginning of May as well as the 20 matches). As my role at the club as highlighted earlier was more of an organisational function and not directly coaching, I was able to audio record field notes from observations which were then transcribed into a written format. Given observations took place not only at the training ground but during matches home and away, my field notes included the date and location of the note. Given the key characteristic of ethnography is its deep rich data, or as Geertz (1973) describes as 'thick', the field notes produced were also descriptive and included what activities took place and the social interactions that occurred. During matches, whilst I for the most part was a spectator, I was unable to record observations, I

therefore was only able to take down what Emerson et al (2011) describe as 'jottings' that often consisted of key words and phrases in order to jog my memory later that day to construct thick descriptions of the scene. It was these field observations that provided the focus for the semi-structured interviews.

Semi structured interviews

As well as observations recorded via field notes, data was also collected for this study via the use of interviews. According to Patton (2002), we interview people to find out from them those things that we cannot or could not observe directly. Interviews are among the most familiar strategies for collecting qualitative data (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006), and have been categorised in a variety of ways, with many contemporary texts loosely differentiating qualitative interviews as unstructured, semi-structured and structured. (DiCicco-Bloom, and Crabtree, 2006). In selecting the semi-structured interview, other interview methods were considered. As (Rabionet, 2011) noted, in utilising the unstructured interview there is a risk of failing to draw out from the participants the topics or themes related to the research question since according to Corbin and Morse (2003), the participant by telling their own story determines what to include, exclude and how much detail to add. The structured interview was also considered and rejected as an approach since Bowling and Ebrahim (2005) suggested that the structured interview is not an approach that should be utilised where the aim is to uncover the meanings of events in the life of participants since Brown and Danaher (2019) suggested that in structured interviews, the questions are usually more closed in character. Holloway and Wheeler (2010) expanded and suggested that qualitative researchers should in fact only use a structured interview to elicit sociodemographic data.

In utilising the semi-structured interview, it is well suited for the exploration of the perceptions and opinions of respondents regarding complex and sometimes sensitive issues (Barriball and While, 1994). Furthermore, the semi-structured interview enables probing for more information and clarification of answers as well as allowing the creativity and flexibility that ensured that each participant's story is fully uncovered (Knox & Burkard, 2009), since unlike structured interviewing there is a much greater interest in the interviewees' perspectives and points of view (Bryman 2015). In effect, the semi-structured interview seeks to gather data on people's subjective experiences and attitudes on how participants interact with their peers and their environment. Data that may otherwise be overlooked (Nowak and Haynes, 2018). The utilising of the semi-structured interview therefore answered the 'why' question and thereby allowed me to gain a better understanding of the research question. Given the complexity of the research question, the semi-structured interview with its versatility enabled a much deeper understanding of the research question to emerge. Miles and Gilbert (2005) noted that since participants attitudes are not fixed or predetermined, the semi-structured interview approach allowed these attitudes to emerge.

Semi-structured interviews were developed utilising the interview guide approach as classified by Patton (1987). This particular approach to interviewing involves the preparation of a basic checklist to make sure that all relevant topics are covered. My interview checklist was developed following a period of observation where layers of data and analysis were already in place given as Miller and Glassner (1997) highlight the interview would not only allow me to test data already collected and perhaps add a new dimension but it could also provide collaborative evidence.. Within the semi

structured interview, the interviewer is still free to explore, probe and ask questions deemed interesting to the research. This type of interview approach is useful for eliciting information about specific topics.

Furthermore, Sampson (1972) provides further support of this semi-structured approach by noting that the open structure of allowing the researcher to allocate the time to each topic area ensures that unexpected facts or attitudes can be easily explored. The open nature of the semi-structured interview provides for responses in the form in which respondents think and use language. According to Hannabuss (1996), this is vital if we are examining how respondents see and interpret this social world which we have chosen to examine. Claringbould and Knoppers (2008) provided an example of the value of the semi structured interview in a study on sport and gender where they utilised it to explore the ways in which participants made sense of gender in their sport. Furthermore, the value of the semi-structured interview for Claringbould and Knoppers (2008) was in the fact that it permitted interviewers to be as non-directive as possible in order that different meanings could emerge by allowing each participant the ability to talk in whatever way they chose. In preparation for conducting a semi structured interview, Miles and Gilbert (2005) provided tips on its general structure. According to Miles and Gilbert (2005) the schedule should be kept brief with key prompts and questions that should flow in a logical order. In understanding and interpreting 'brief', Ross and Shinew (2008) helpfully outlined the use of an interview schedule of fourteen key questions. This brief interview schedule allows for the researcher to ask more directed questions where appropriate after asking the open ended questions along the key themes.

These semi structured interviews were used in this study with the fifteen professional youth players of Burncastle FC precisely because of the flexibility that they offered. I only conducted interviews with the players mindful of the purpose of the interview was, as Whitehead (2005) points out, to elicit answers from the perspective of the study participant, whilst attempting to gain a greater understanding of the context and meaning of those responses through various forms of probing. As May (1999) highlights, by interviewing the players I was able to obtain insights into the study participants' experiences, opinions, aspirations and feelings.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis, a qualitative method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data (Braun & Clarke 2006) was used for this study as not only is it flexible but it can be seen as a foundational and widely used method for qualitative analysis.

According to Mills et al (2010) the flexibility of thematic analysis allows for a wide range of data sources to be used, including interviews, field notes, diaries, journals research memos, historical or site documents, photographs, drawings, maps, digital audio files, and video files. Boyatzis (1998) suggests that thematic analysis is a useful tactic to employ for reducing and managing large volumes of data without losing the context, for getting close to or immersing oneself in the data, for organizing and summarizing, and for focusing the interpretation.

Miles and Huberman (1994) suggest there are three stages of qualitative data analysis. Stage one is data reduction where the mass of qualitative data one obtains is reduced and organised. Stage two is data display where conclusions are drawn from

the mass of data. Stage three is the conclusion drawing/verification stage where we one begins to develop conclusions regarding ones findings. These initial conclusions can then be verified through reference to existing field notes or further data collection. Braun and Clarke (2006) outline a similar process that was adopted here. Unlike the three stage Miles and Huberman (1994) data analysis process Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that the first stage of data analysis requires the researcher to become familiar with the data by immersion in it which involves repeated reading of the data. Only then can step two begin which involves generating initial codes which are defined simply as a label of any kind which is attached to a piece of data (Elliott 2018). Coding can be done, according Braun and Clarke (2006), either manually or through software programmes. Coding in this study was conducted using NVivo 10 for Windows. Using NVivo 10, codes were generated by tagging and naming selections of text within each data item. Stage three involved searching for themes or categories as Elliott (2018) describes them where several codes are aggregated to form a common idea, by sorting the different codes into potential themes, and collating all the relevant coded data extracts within the identified themes to form an overarching theme. Stage four involved the refinement of these themes. Stage five comprised a process of defining and naming themes that meant identifying the essence of what each theme was about (as well as the themes overall), and determining what aspect of the data each theme captures. Once a set of fully worked-out themes was available stage six involved the analysis and write-up of the thesis

Data for this study was therefore analysed inductively where the primary purpose of is to allow research findings to emerge from the frequent, dominant, or significant themes inherent in raw data, without the restraints imposed by structured methodologies

(Thomas 2006), with the themes identified being strongly linked to the data (Patton, 1990). Inductive analysis is therefore a process of coding the data without trying to fit it into a pre-existing coding frame (Braun, and Clarke 2006).

Coding of the data

For this thesis, all of the semi structured interviews were transcribed verbatim. Hand written field notes were typewritten. These were then imported into the qualitative data analysis (QDA) computer software package NVivo 10. This software package was used as it also permitted images from the club's match day programmes to be scanned in as well as photographs taken by myself to be added. This software package was chosen given its flexibility in arranging the variety of data sources gathered during this research. Once all data was imported into NVivo 10, I began the data analysis by utilising an open coding process by seeking what Corbin and Strauss (2008, p12) call, "conceptually similar events/ actions/ interactions"

within the players' responses and the other data that gave an indication of the ways in which they viewed their experiences of the football club and, in particular, the way in which particular masculinities were constructed. Initially, I identified a number of in vivo codes that (Roulston, 2010, p. 151) describes as being "derived directly from words and phrases uttered by the participant". These codes were then assigned a 'node' within NVivo 10 where all related material was able to be gathered together within a single container. The in vivo codes I developed included *being fit, sacrifice, emotions, success, girls, starting out, family, hard commitment, heroes, swearing* and *team*. Next, I identified analytic codes that (Roulston, 2010, p. 151) suggests are "codes relating to the research questions posed". These analytic codes incorporated terms

such as *toughness, commitment, sexism, and manliness*. Following Braun, and Clarke (2006) the different codes were then sorted into potential themes at stage four that included *becoming a man, muscularity, boys don't cry, sexual objectification, and constructing Identity*. These categories were then considered in relation to the key theoretical concept of masculinities before entering stage five of the Braun and Clarke (2006) process by defining and naming the themes identifying the essence of what each theme was about. The main themes, which are discussed in later chapters of this thesis, therefore included *identity and initiation, emotions and embodiment and everyday misogyny, sexism and masculinity*.

According to Long and Johnson (2000), studies require to be transparent and therefore open to critique and evaluation since failure to assess the worth of a study could at the worst result in the adoption of dangerous practices or at the very least result in wasted time or effort. Within the scientific positivist paradigm the evaluation of a study has centred round the assessment of reliability and validity. Reliability according to Payne & Payne (2004) refers to the property of the measuring device which yields consistent measures regardless of who uses it. Reliability is therefore linked to repeatability. Bryman (2015) suggests that not only must a measuring instrument yield consistent measures for it to be reliable, it also requires that the instrument is stable which is often done using a test-retest method. Secondly, Bryman (2015) suggests that the measure must also have internal reliability where all the indicators are related to each other and finally there requires to be inter observer consistency since when there is more than one observer involved in the translation and recording of observations there is a possibility that there is a lack of consistency in their decisions.

Meanwhile, validity, which can take several forms (Payne & Payne 2004) in the scientific positivist paradigm refers to the issue of whether an indicator devised to measure a concept actually measures that concept. Qualitative approaches have been criticised in the sense that they lack the scientific rigour and credibility associated with traditionally accepted quantitative methods (Horsburgh 2003, Mays & Pope 1995). Indeed, many proponents of positivist quantitative research imply that qualitative approaches to human inquiry are of no scientific value as they are so rife with threats to validity (Angen 2000, Denzin 2009). In attempting to be more scientific some qualitative writers have adopted the positivist criteria of validity to prove the value and worth of a study (Angen 2000). Other writers such as Krefting (1991) suggest that models traditionally used for the evaluation of the worth of a study focussed on an assessment of reliability and validity seldom fit with qualitative research whilst Rolfe (2006) points out that there is an argument that the issues at stake in qualitative research are so fundamentally different from those in quantitative research that an entirely alternative terminology is required to assess and evaluate these issues.

Lincoln & Guba (1985) indeed propose an alternative terminology preferring the concept of trustworthiness. Trustworthiness involves the establishment of credibility where there is confidence in the 'truth' of the findings, transferability achieved by showing that the findings have applicability in other contexts, dependability by showing that the findings are consistent and could be repeated and finally confirmability achieved by establishing a degree of neutrality or the extent to which the findings of a study are shaped by the respondents and not researcher bias, motivation, or interest.

Whilst a range of authors have developed models to ascribe validity to qualitative research (Cresswell, 2009, Whitemore, Chase and Mandell 2001), Denzin (2009) rejects these models and approaches of assessing qualitative research arguing that all of the models proposed seek to fit qualitative research into the positivist paradigm in order to gain credibility with the positivist scientific community. According to Rolfe (2006) there appears to be three distinct positions in assessing the quality of qualitative research, firstly the adoption of positivist validity criteria for qualitative research; secondly, the establishment of distinct and separate criteria from those adopted in quantitative research; and thirdly, a complete rejection of all predetermined criteria. Denzin (2009) ascribes proponents of these three positions as foundationalists who argue that all research whether it is quantitative or qualitative must conform to a set of shared criteria. Quasi foundationalists on the other hand contend that a set of criteria, or guiding framework unique to qualitative research need to be developed, criteria or guiding frameworks such as those described above (Lincoln & Guba 1985, Creswell 2009) and non-foundationalists who stress the importance of understanding versus prediction. Denzin (2009) suggest that three positions exist within the ongoing debate concerning evidence based qualitative research. Sandelowski (1993) agrees with Denzin (2009) suggesting that the interpretive paradigm should be more about creating evocative landscapes of human experience rather than attempting to establish truth or reality via guidelines or criteria that view reality as external, repeatable, agreed, and able to be corroborated. Sandelowski (1993 p3) usefully reminds us that,

“in the naturalistic/interpretive paradigm, reality is assumed to be multiple and constructed rather than singular and tangible.”

Rolfe (2006) usefully suggests, therefore, that the search for a generic framework for assessing the quality of qualitative research should be abandoned in favour of individual judgements of individual studies. This therefore adopts the approach of Sandelowski (1993), who suggests that validity is achieved through consensus on each individual study rather than by the blanket application of predetermined criteria, since no matter how rigorously methodological criteria is applied to qualitative work it will not produce the objectivity desired by positivist researchers (Angen 2000). Indeed, Sandelowski and Barroso (2002) argued for a shift in terminology from 'evaluation' to 'appraisal', which is concerned with 'the exercise of wise judgement and keen insight in recognising the nature and merits of a work' (p. 10). Angen (2000) agrees, suggesting that we can no longer strive for some unitary truth of human behaviour using exclusively reductive, positivist procedures. Instead, Angen (2000) suggests what we require is an interpretive approach to social inquiry that will enlarge and deepen our understanding of what it means to be human. Yet, despite the pleas of writers such as Sandelowski (1993), Sandelowski and Barroso (2002), and Rolfe (2006) the desire for legitimacy in an academic world that is still tied to positivism keeps interpretive researchers questing for a recipe or map that will legitimize their efforts (Angen 2000).

Data integrity

As Hammarberg, Kirkman, and de Lacey (2016) usefully note, any qualitative study must be procedurally robust and must make explicit purpose of the research, how it was conducted, procedural decisions, and details of data generation and management. In ensuring the 'trustworthiness' that Lincoln & Guba (1985) refer to, this

study set out early on the purpose of the study which was to examine the construction of masculinity within Scottish professional football. The above chapter further details how data was collected via field notes during observations and by semi structured interviews. The above chapter further outlines the procedural decisions taken in data collection such as the use of semi structured interviews. Data collection and the management of this data has also been laid out and explained by the use of NVivo 10 and thematic analysis of this data via coding. It is intended by reading the above chapter that a reviewer will therefore be able, as Hammarberg, et al (2016 p500) assert, "to follow the progression of events and decisions and understand their logic because there is adequate description, explanation and justification of the methodology and methods" Hammarberg, et al (2016) further note that that integrity within qualitative research also requires credibility. As the researcher is the instrument within qualitative research, credibility is defended via reflective practice which is addressed as well as initial reflexivity in chapter one. In further ensuring credibility, the researcher as the instrument will also provide substantial description of the process including verbatim quotations within the interpretation. In confirming the credibility of this thesis, the findings chapter includes these verbatim quotations

Sample

In qualitative research sample sizes are often much smaller than quantitative studies since qualitative research is more concerned with meaning than making generalised hypothesis statements (Mason 2010). Guest, Bunce and Johnson (2006) found that there are relatively few recommendations on sample size for qualitative inquiry. Furthermore, according to Mason (2010) studies that use more than one method require fewer participants. Small (2009) suggests however that qualitative researchers

generally and ethnographers in particular are becoming increasingly preoccupied with sample size in order to emulate the natural sciences in pursuit of social scientific methods in particular seeking to increase generalisability.

In fact, Janesick (2003) suggests that rather than continually focus on quantitative issues such as how many or how long, qualitative researchers should reframe these questions interpretively by asking themselves not how many or how long but rather what type of interview and with which actors would be the most sensible based on the purpose of the study. Sandelowski (2001) disagrees that numbers are less important in qualitative research suggesting instead that numbers can be a powerful device, as they can showcase and illustrate the complexity of qualitative work with large amounts of data being produced with even just one participant. Sandelowski (2001) further suggests that counting is integral to the analysis process, especially to the recognition of patterns in data. This pattern recognition implies seeing something over and over again in one case or across a selection of cases. Once something is seen over and over again and each category is rich and thick, then the data set will become saturated. Once this saturation occurs then the researcher will be provided with confidence and certainty that the analysis is strong and the conclusions will be right (Richards & Morse 2013). In ensuring that the data set is indeed saturated, the literature should be re-read looking for the ways a satisfying explanation is expressed (Richards & Morse 2013).

Whilst quantitative studies often depend on large samples selected randomly, qualitative studies typically focus on relatively small samples often even one case selected purposefully (Patton 2002). In purposeful sampling, which is often called

purposive sampling (Bryman 2015) or judgement sampling (Patton 2002), the participants are selected in a strategic way with those selected being relevant to the research question being posed (Bryman 2015). Furthermore, Richards & Morse (2013) suggest that these selected participants will know the information, will have the time and are willing to participate. In purposefully selecting a sample, an intensity sampling approach was adopted. This intensity sampling approach is described by Patton (2002) as a sample that consists of information rich cases that manifest the phenomenon intensely. In utilising an intensity sampling approach to purposeful sampling the participants were able to provide excellent or rich examples of the phenomenon.

Reflexivity

According to Berger (2015), it is important that researchers conducting qualitative research understand the role of self when creating knowledge particularly their own biases, beliefs, and personal experiences. These biases, beliefs and personal experiences, according to Berger (2015), can further be extended to include age, gender, race, political affiliation, as well as a range of other factors including ideology and personal emotions towards participants. This critical reflection or reflexivity is crucial for the qualitative researcher adopting a social constructionist epistemology since the researcher is part of the social world and therefore knowledge creation cannot be independent of that researcher. Mason (2017) supports this view, suggesting that thinking critically about what you are doing and why allows the researcher to challenge and confront one's own assumptions, thoughts and actions since these assumptions, thoughts and actions shape how you research and what you see.

Berger (2015) further explains that the positions taken by a researcher can impact the research in three ways. Firstly, a researcher who appears sympathetic to the situation of the respondents may encourage them to be more willing to share information. Secondly, the biases, beliefs and personal experiences of the researcher may in fact shape the relationship between the researcher and researched relationship. A man may for instance feel more comfortable sharing experiences with another man. Thirdly, the background of the researcher and their world view affects the way they construct the world and thereby makes meaning of it. The researcher therefore will choose the lens for filtering the information obtained from participants which in turn may shape the findings and conclusions of the study. The role and function that the researcher adopts will therefore be crucial to the study.

Insider/Outsider

As Bucarius (2013) highlights, in gaining access to the key information held by participants, researchers must gain the trust of these group members. In gaining this trust, Mullings (1999) highlights a commonly held belief that if a researcher belongs to a group that they study they are more likely as an 'insider' to gain better insights to the knowledge of that group by virtue of their own membership. As Dwyer and Buckle (2009) note, being an insider often allows for more rapid access to a group and complete acceptance by the group, thereby establishing trust. Dwyer and Buckle (2009) highlight that having insider status does have its drawbacks where there is potential for role confusion as the researchers perceptions may be clouded by their own experiences and further may during an interview shape and guide it by these experiences.

Despite this, Bucerius (2013) points to the commonly held belief that the ability to gain the trust of groups depends on his or her degree of similarity to them. Thus male researchers predominate in fields where the topic of the study relates to male dominated activities. Whilst Fonow, and Cook, (1991), argue that it is in fact better to be an 'outsider' that is not being aligned to the group thereby maintaining the ability to be seen as neutral and therefore be more objective. Bucerius (2013) notes that being different to the research participants can be seen as a research liability particularly if the researcher is a woman studying male oriented social worlds. Arendell (1997) explored the gender and power dynamic with male participants and found that the male participants regularly sought to assert their superordinate position via continued displays of gender and assertions of the conventional gender hierarchy. Arendell (1997) contends that in intervening to address these issues, the research would have been different from what was intended as well as even opening herself up to further ridicule and attempts to further subordinate her. Bucerius (2013) suggests that an outsider can negotiate the power dynamics prevalent within all male environments and position themselves as an outsider trusted with inside knowledge by bringing own personality into the research relationship. Indeed, with gender often being salient with research (Presser 2005), it has been suggested that others incorporate this strategy into their research (Oakley 1981). Mullings (1999) provides further insight into the negotiation of the insider/outsider debate by suggesting that it is not a fixed position arguing that no researcher can consistently remain an insider nor ever remain complete outsiders. Much like Bucerius (2013), Mullings (1999 p340) proposes that researchers seek, what she describes as positional spaces, which are areas where the,

“situated knowledges of both parties in the interview encounter, engender a level of trust and co-operation.”

As an example, Mullings (1999) suggests the researcher might demonstrate to the participant group a level of knowledge of the topic or might in fact show no knowledge in order that the participants felt less threatened. Similarly, Dwyer and Buckle (2009) argue that there is no need for researchers to be preoccupied with the notion of being an insider or outsider given as they suggest that researchers can in fact be both by occupying the space between. During this study, I adopted a position somewhere in between of insider/outsider. Whilst I was a male with a knowledge and understanding of the game and could have adopted a research position of becoming an insider, I was older than the participants and did not engage in coaching. By occupying a positional space where I shared information such as my favourite team enabled rapport to be established with participants and gatekeepers alike.

Whilst an understanding and awareness of the impact the researcher may have on the subjects being studied is important, Probst (2015) importantly notes that reflexivity also requires the researcher to recognise how the research is affecting the researcher. As part of this critical reflection a key consideration must be the issue of bias since, as Ellefsen (2017) in agreeing with Berger (2015), points out that all sociological research is biased in one way or another as the position taken by the researcher and their outlook can affect his research questions, methodologies, analysis and conclusions. Bernstein and Friedman (2013) note particularly in the field of ethnography researcher bias cannot be completely purged. As Cousin (cited in Ellefsen 2017 p239) points out,

“our knowledge is always mediated and interpreted from a particular stance and through our available language, and that we should own up to this in explicit ways.”

In being reflexive and considering their own role within social research, the researcher should also, according to Couture, Zaidi and Tyndale (2012), consider their insider/outsider status since this will provide both advantages and disadvantages within the data collection process. If the researcher shares similar characteristics and experiences as the research subjects, this will be defined as an insider status thereby allowing the researcher to easily establish rapport and an increased opportunity for generating more data since the subjects may be more open. Indeed, Couture, et al (2012) go further and suggest that research participants may well see the researcher as being ‘one of them’. This however can also produce negatives as suggest, some participants may not completely explain their experiences if the participants assume that researcher already understands. Outsiders on the other hand may ask more probing questions and seek further clarification but may be open to accusations of a lack of empathic understanding (Couture, et al 2012)

Cromby and Nightingale (cited in Pitard 2017), however, separate reflexivity into two distinct elements: personal and epistemological. Personal reflexivity references our own values, beliefs, and values. In this thesis, personal reflexivity is explored by means of a profile of the researcher with epistemological reflexivity which according to Blaisdell (2015) linked to research ethics being addressed throughout the sections of this thesis that address the methodological considerations including ethical

considerations such as informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, and protection from harm.

This thesis begins with a profile of the researcher from early childhood through to adulthood by exploring the beliefs, motivations, gender, and ideology that translates as critical reflection and thereby providing the framework that locates this study within the world and the production of knowledge that derives from it. As Norton (2017) notes, life story is vitally important in social research since our own particular view of the world has been shaped over time through the social, cultural and political environments in which we grew up in. In addition, and in particular, our view of the world has been shaped by family, gender, race, interactions in relationships via school, university and in work. Norton (2017 p2) concludes,

“This process of "shaping" continues in my daily life. I bring into my research my whole story and, in turn, each of the research participants I meet (and all their stories) shifts my perceptions as we interact together.”

The researcher profile outlined in Chapter One may lead to the perception that the researcher may be viewed as an insider as I share many commonalities with the young men in this study such as a working class background and an interest in and a love of the game. However, the researcher here was acting an ‘outsider’ to this research, since there was a significant age gap, no geographical connection and an inability to play the game; this meant the researcher was free to ask probing questions, whilst being able to retain empathy with the young men.

Conclusion

The main aim of this chapter was to justify, sociologically, the selection of appropriate research methods that could generate the relevant data in order to answer the research questions of this thesis. Furthermore, this chapter also outlined the procedures undertaken to complete the research including the particular stages involved in access to the field and identified how the data generated was analysed. These data are presented in the next three chapters of this thesis. In outlining the methodological, theoretical and philosophical approaches and considerations that underpinned this research, this chapter additionally set out how quality and integrity is ensured via the process of 'trustworthiness' and credibility outlined by Lincoln & Guba (1985). It thereby provided an ethical, robust and indeed scientific approach to the study since, according to Williams (1999), one of the founding fathers of interpretivism - Max Weber - sought to have sociology understood and accepted as a science since understanding meaning can form the basis of causal explanation. For Weber (1947), sociology is indeed a science which attempts the interpretive understanding of social action in order to arrive at a causal explanation of its course and effects.

CHAPTER 6: IDENTITY AND INITIATION

Introduction

I noted in an earlier section that self-identity symbolises the answer to the question of who am I (Myers 2009). Answering this question sets us apart as individuals. For writers in the field of sports science such as Brewer, Van Raalte, & Linder, (1993 p237) "the degree to which an individual identifies with the athlete role" is defined as an athletic identity. So, for example, rather than describe oneself as someone who plays football, the individual may describe themselves as a 'footballer'. Rasquinha, & Cardinal (2017) further note that this athletic identity is higher among those participating in sports with higher cultural significance as football is in Scotland. This chapter describes the meaning and impact of this athletic identity on the players in this study prior to undertaking an analysis of the specifics of this identity creation by describing the particular routes into football.

Athletic Identity

"one of the most important things now about being a football player - your athleticism, you need to be an athlete now to be a football player, you cannae no' be." (Ian)

Brown and Potrac (2009) suggest that this strong sense of athletic identity will benefit the individual since it will have positive benefits on performance and should increase the likelihood that the individual remains involved in sport, exercise and physical fitness in the long term. Holt and Mitchell (2006) point to the importance of the development of an athletic identity particularly in football as it is perceived to evoke increased levels of dedication and commitment to reaching professional status, and to

live, breathe and eat football is therefore strongly encouraged within youth development environments. Again, in this study, Ian appears to concur,

“I’m more an athlete than I’ve ever been and I can train, I can run, I can go-I can do- if I want to do something, there’s nothing that can hold me back.” (Ian)

Brown and Potrac (2009) further note that those with a strong sense of athletic identity may make a strong commitment to an occupation or ideology such as a career in football by routinely sacrificing social and educational aspects of their lives in favour of becoming a professional footballer. Marcia, Waterman, Matteson, Archers, & Orlofsky, (1993) have defined this sacrifice as “identity foreclosure”.

Scott: “It’s all I’ve ever wanted to be was a footballer. I wasn’t very good at school so I suppose that helped a bit.

Researcher: “It’s a big commitment though isn’t it? Three nights a week training and match at the weekend”

Scott: “I suppose so, but to make it you need to make that commitment”.

Researcher: “Does this commitment mean giving things up”?

Scott: “Well in a way. I suppose I gave up on school a wee bit”

Researcher: “What about other things you’ve given up like friends or anything”?

Scott: “Well I don’t see mates that often but that’s the price you’ve got to pay isn’t it”?

Researcher: “Is it”?

Scott: “Yeah, football’s not just like a normal job, it’s more like a lifestyle that you have to like live it”.

This sense of athletic identity prevalent among sports scientists and psychologists has however been challenged. Roderick (2006), for example, suggests that players’ involvement in football is not just an activity that they do but something that they are. Roderick (2006 p17) further noted that football is an “all consuming, and physically

demanding career and that it is inevitable that self-identity is essentially determined by it". Hickey and Roderick (2017) reinforce this idea that identity is not fixed but has multiple elements that are constantly being negotiated and reworked. Hickey and Roderick (2017) further assert that it is impossible to characterise an athlete (footballer) in the purely one dimensional terms of sports person thereby neglecting other social roles. For Hickey and Roderick (2017), this notion of the renegotiation and reworking is crucial since they argue that self-identity is further constructed and influenced by audience expectation. There exists therefore the possibility that multiple identities exist, as Huang and Brittain (2006) contend that identities are in fact social products and shaped through interaction by others definition. The young men in this study are therefore defined not only by themselves but by the environment that is the football club. This notion of interactional construction of identities cements and concludes our earlier discussion on who we are. As I noted earlier, given this study was set in Scotland, often national identity could be defined as civic or national that is a given identity based on birth or residence. However, Topic and Coakley (2010) further separate out national identity with nationality, arguing that national identity develops via citizens identifying with the imagery and stories associated with the nation and using them to express their connection with the collective and identifying others as part of that collective. This clarity and conclusion around the multiplicity of identities allow us to consider how identity is constructed within the environment of the football club.

This interaction with others, the stories and imagery and the all-consuming environment that is the football club is developed by Gearing (1999) who notes that the football environment whilst not physically separated from the outside world, is

semi-enclosed with activities carried out alongside others with rules and sanctions imposed from above. As Gearing (1999) further notes, these rules and sanctions applied via regimentation and discipline often goes beyond the actual game itself. Parker and Manley (2017) argue that far from the identity of self being defined by the individual like the athletic identity, identity within professional football is created and developed by the adoption and embracing of notions of power, dominance, authority and organisational and social control much like the construction of other identities. As Parker and Manley (2017) highlighted, the football club and the operation surrounding it remain relatively secluded, discrete, and organised around hierarchy, discipline and organisation.

The following field note provides an example of regimentation involved Burncastle FC:

“Its my first day and as I approach the training ground, the players are easily identifiable in their black tops adorned with the sponsor’s name, with black shorts and black socks all acting in unison with an apparent shared aim and shared mission. If this wasn’t a football field the players may even resemble a gang milling about” (field note).

Dougie continues this theme of regimentation but provides further insight into the level of social control:

“when you become a football player- everything is guided, so they want you to be in the best shape you can be in. Peak fitness. Then you can perform the best. And then they do that. They set rules, you live by those rules and eventually it becomes a lifestyle, it’s a lifestyle choice” (Dougie).

Football for these young men is all consuming and provides the context, framework and environment for them to construct a particular identity:

Researcher: "So, clearly football is, is important to you. It's a huge part of your life".

Sean: " Uh-huh., it's my life. It's all I want to do is kick a ball since I was at a young age, like. It's all I wanted to do. At school I'd kick a ball. At home I'd kick a ball, then I'd go to training, then I'd come home and practice more".

Researcher: "Football's important in your life. How important- can you put that into words how important football is to you"?

Ian: Well..."what happens at the end of this season is gonna be life changing. This is what I've- at school I wasn't paying lots much attention cos I thought I could be a footballer and I'd make enough money in the footballing so I didn't really need tae concentrate enough in school, but now I wish I stuck in a wee bit in school".

Researcher: Okay. So?

Ian: "Cos I just put everythin' intae football".

Researcher: "So football's"?

Ian: "My life. I really don't know what I will do if I've not got football. It's seven days a week for me, the training, the games, the gym everything. When I'm not playing, I'm watching, looking at how the top players play and trying to get tips from them. If I do get kept on next year then I'm gonna just stick in and try to keep getting better"

Initiation

This athletic self-identity developed early on for the participants in this study. All of the young men in this research began playing football from an early age and many recalled their first memories of playing football and being taken along to a local team. For these young men football was an important part of their development given that Messner (1992) reminds us that boys are judged according to their ability in competitive sport. The following comments illustrate the participants' involvement in football as young children:

“I suppose I just kinda fell into football really, my da’ who was starting up a team and he just took me along with him. It just seemed natural. Football runs in the family so I didn’t really think about it. It was just something that we did.” (Ian)

“I got into football from my uncle who was the coach of a local team and he asked me if I wanted to play, so I just said yeah’ and that was it. I just went along and it was fun so I suppose I’ve never looked back”. (Jack)

Not only were the young people taken to football by a family member, in particular this family member tended to be male and mainly their father. Family influence therefore appeared to be a significant factor on the young people’s decision to become involved in football. Not only do fathers seem to be the main factor in beginning a football career, they remain the key influencer in maintaining it. Dziubiński, and Czachowski (2014) note that fathers tend to be responsible for encouraging their sons to attend training as well as driving their sons to training facilities. The influence and role of fathers in this initiation process cannot be underestimated or minimised since as Milošević & Vesković (2013) note, it is primarily fathers who are the dominant agents of sports socialisation. This is illustrated by Neil whose father and brother both played the game:

Researcher: “Why football? What drove you into being a football player”?

Neil: “Just, been kicking a ball since I can remember. My brother played football, my dad played football so I was always drummed into it and always had a season ticket to watch matches”.

Researcher: “So your brother and dad are at a fairly high level”?

Neil: “My dad was junior but my brother was amateur but both decent players”

Researcher: “So it’s a family thing”?

Neil: "Aye, just was brought up knowin' how to play football and wantin' to watch it an' that kind of thing"

For Alan, it was the influence of this father who appears to initiate contact into the formalised game with no prior background as a player:

Researcher: "Why did you become involved in football, what was the motivation? What was your reasons for doing that"?

Alan: "Just like, since I was young I was always kinda kicking a ball about the back garden and then, from there my dad kinda went to enter me into a team and then, just went fae there, really. I got more involved and interested in it. It was something I enjoyed doing",

Green & Chalip (1997) assert that parental encouragement appears to result in ongoing involvement, particularly when the encouragement takes concrete forms such as watching, as the following field note illustrates:

"As darkness falls and training commences with the rain sweeping across the open pitches, a group of men whom I'd seen earlier dropping off young people wearing football kit huddle under the awning of the nearby school building. The talk is primarily around football with some analysis of the previous week's match that ended in defeat. The men are deep in discussion with some criticism of the coach currently putting the young people through their paces. Inevitably the referee attracts some criticism, as does surprisingly the performance of the team itself" (field note)

Whilst male family members were the main facilitators in initiating engagement with football, for some of the young people their motivation to begin playing the game was as a result of family members playing the game. The following comments illustrate the importance of this family relationship:

“Football is really important to me, my brother was a good player but he got in with a bad crowd and had to stop playing due to the drink..... I want to make it for him as well as me. I suppose it's mainly due to him that I am where I am as he encouraged me to stick in and not make the mistakes he made I want to make him proud of me”. (Gerard)

“All my family played football, my da' was captain of (local junior) team and I remember going to watch him play. I remember the buzz and the excitement when he won games. All the other players looked up to him” (Johnnie)

Fredricks & Eccles (2005) suggest that in the field of sport there is a strong link between parental involvement in sport and involvement of their children in what they describe as role modelling. Birchwood, Roberts and Pollock (2008) go further and suggest that it is the culture of the family that principally determines a child's propensity to engage in sporting activity. Birchwood et al (2008) explain this assertion by suggesting that children acquire what Bourdieu (1977) describes as 'habitus' which he explains as the deeply ingrained habits, skills, and dispositions that we possess due to our life experiences, or in a sporting context 'a feel for the game'. Birchwood et al (2008) suggest that this habitus is transmitted via socialisation in the family as this comment illustrates:

“I don't really remember how I got into football but I do remember always kicking a ball about the house and the back garden from as long as I can remember. Football was always on the telly and it was really all everyone in my house talked about. Everyone in my family played football, as well, my dad, my uncles, my brothers, so I guess it was just something that I got into through them” (Paul)

Since one acquires habitus as a result of occupying a particular place and position within the social world, everyone will have a different habitus although those who

occupy the same position tend to have similar habitus (Cushion and Jones 2006). As McGillivray & McIntosh (2006) note, habitus is characterised further as being what one is in that it is unthinking and natural and is therefore “a subconscious manifestation of social structure that includes social habits, values, ways of being, thinking and moving, which are collectively generated by social actors while being reinforced in others” (Atencio et al 2009, p5).

The football habitus therefore develops early in young men as the football culture is introduced early in their lives and becomes embodied via peers, family, media and the socialisation processes that encompasses this. Of course, as McGillivray & McIntosh (2006) note, this notion of habitus as being unthinking and natural has attracted some sociological critique particularly around the suggestion that the use of this terminology gives the impression that habitus is an inflexible, structuralist concept but McGillivray & McIntosh (2006) point to Bourdieu’s work where he notes that that actors work with and against the sociocultural contexts within which they find themselves embroiled to dismiss the critique. However, for the young people in this study habitus was only transmitted via male family members as these field note illustrates:

“As we take to the pitch for the league game I recognise some of the faces of the supporters are the men that I see at training sessions. Those men that I don’t recognise I assume have travelled with the away team” (field note)

“Not long into the game and the away team have scored. The applause from a section of those spectators seems to confirm my earlier suspicion that the ‘travelling support’ are family and friends of the away team player” (field note)

Female members of the family appeared not to have played any significant role in the football lives of the young people, which they appeared to readily accept as this comment illustrated when asked about his mother's involvement in his football career:

"My ma isn't really interested in football, don't get me wrong, she does like to see me doing well coz when I go home, she asks me if I've scored and that, but that's about it." (Ian)

Ian when asked about his mother's involvement suggests that his mum doesn't understand the game:

"My mum? Nah, I don't think she understands football. When there's a game on the telly she watches something else on the other telly. She'll maybe ask whose playing and that but that's about it"

Additionally, there was a sense that that female family members had other roles that were traditional in nature such as providing a caring function. Another young player, when asked about the involvement of his mother, explained:

"She has seen me play a few times particularly if it's a big game like a cup game or something but she watches my wee sister when me and my dad are at football" (Dougie)

A similar theme of the provision of care was outlined by Alan:

"She doesn't really have time to watch me play coz she looks after my gran at the weekends".

When asked about his mother's participation in his football career Wullie identifies a 'traditional' role for his mother:

“At weekends when I’m playing my ma normally does shopping and stuff.”

This sense of females within the family facilitating the football activity of the father and son is consistent with the findings of Votík, and Válková, (2011) who describe the “football family”, where the mother provides the family background, a service for the football activities of males. According to Votík, and Válková, (2011) the mother more or less sacrifices and provides service and support for its functioning in terms of football requirements.

Most of the young men, therefore, appear to have significant male influence on their decision to play football. Writers such as Bandura (1977) suggest that this decision may be as a result of socialisation that suggests children imitate and model behaviours exhibited by their parents. Therefore a boy will naturally gravitate towards football if his father or other significant relative has played the game and therefore become socialised. Socialisation according to Allison (1982) is the process in which individuals are taught and/or learn about the nature of their culture. Allison (1982) suggested that this explanation is inadequate and flawed given that socialisation not only views the learner (the young person) as passive and someone who is acted upon by socialising agents (parents). Furthermore, Allison (1982) also suggested that socialisation oversimplifies the complexity of the relationship which exists between socializing agent, social situations, and personal attributes as well as neglecting the significant issue of culture.

Therefore, whilst recognising that the young men in this study engaged in football for more complex reasons than parental modelling, as Allen (2003) notes there are very

few young people who engage in a sport (in this study, football) on their own. Indeed, in this study, not all of the young men recalled family involvement in their initiation into football. One young person suggests that a peer group was a key influencer, with the following comment:

“I don’t really have memories of how I actually got into football, I suppose I got into it quite late on coz I wasn’t really into football when I was younger coz nobody in my family was really interested but all my pals were and they played football all the time and talked about it all the time so it was something I had to get into. I discovered that I was quite good so I think that helped.” (Derek)

All of the young men had played for several clubs prior to joining their current club. After beginning their footballing careers with local community clubs, all arrived at their current club after being scouted by coaches of professional clubs. One young man recalled his first experience of playing for a professional club with the following comment:

“I was really really nervous. I just wanted to do my best and not let anyone in the team down. I think I scored a goal so I did ok.” (Scott)

Another young man commented that it was the first step on a road to stardom, riches, fame and fortune:

“I just wanted to be the best I can, yeah of course I wanted to play for Barcelona or Real Madrid. I guess I felt I was on my way.” (Paul)

Whilst most of the young men involved in this study initially engaged in football as a result of male influence, a decision to continue playing was influenced by social

acceptance, and an opportunity to attain a lifestyle that will make them rich and famous:

Researcher: "Do you have any ambitions for football"?

Jack: "I want to play at the highest level. I want to play against all the folk you see on the telly and I want to play against them. To be on the telly and be like them. They're living their lifestyle. I mean it's amazing"

Researcher: "What do you mean by that"?

Jack: "They- they're like- they don't- want for nothing. They can- say they take a fancy to a car, they go buy it. They take a fancy to a house, they go buy it. If they want to go somewhere, so long as it's alright with the manager, they go there. So that's – that kind of living, where you don't have to worry about bills, mortgages, debts where it's basically all done for you. It's like a dream isn't it. I definitely would love to follow that dream and as long as I work hard then why not"?

According to Allen (2003) social acceptance by a peer group is a powerful influencer in beginning sport. Like Derek (above), who reported that football was something he 'had' to get into. This social acceptance therefore becomes a significant element in the journey to becoming a man. This social acceptance and interaction with the peer group is outlined by Bird (1996) who describes this interaction as homosocial interaction that is defined as the nonsexual attractions held by men for members of their own sex or more informally the relationships between men. Crucially, for Bird (1996) homosociality promotes clear distinctions between hegemonic masculinities and non-hegemonic masculinities by the segregation of social groups. In this instance, via membership of a professional football team. This homosocial interaction between men often, according to Bird (1996), manifests itself into a competition. This competitiveness is about proving and asserting your non- femaleness and your own

maleness. Flood (2008) notes that this competition is double faceted. Whilst men do indeed compete by using what Flood (2008) refers to as 'markers of manhood', in this case sexual prowess to improve their position in the hierarchy of masculinities, men also seek the approval of their homosocial group.

For Bird (1996), not only does homosociality promote distinctions between hegemonic masculinities and non-hegemonic masculinities it actually perpetuates and maintains gender inequalities and the dominance of the hegemonic form of masculinity. Flood (2008) notes that within homosocial interactions, sexual experience is directly correlated to masculine status as does Richardson (2010). As Hammarén and Johansson (2014) put it, women become a kind of currency men use to improve their ranking on the masculine social scale. Hammarén and Johansson (2014) do, however, question whether homosociality exists purely to maintain hegemony and point to the development of the more inclusive, cohesive and intimate non-sexual friendship relationships that have recently been described as 'bromances'. These 'bromances' (combining brother with romance) according to Chen (2012) provide a space for intimate male friendships. Hammarén and Johansson (2014) further note the work of Anderson's (2008) inclusive masculinity study where he suggests that there is now considerable change in masculinity with the lessening of homophobia that will gradually lead to a widening of the range of masculine identities and positions that are possible to embody and perform. Whilst no homophobic language was observed during this study and McCormack (2014) notes that homophobia was on the decrease in the UK, even in football by illustrating a study that indicated that 93 per cent of football fans would accept an openly gay player on their team, McCormack (2014)

accepts that this reduction in homophobia is more prevalent in middle class young people.

The young men in this study utilised heterosexuality to distance themselves from other subordinated and marginalised gender constructions such as homosexual men. Given this perceived reduction in homophobia, Hammarén and Johansson (2014) propose that homosociality requires to be extended and redefined into what they describe as vertical/hierarchical and horizontal homosociality. Vertical/hierarchical homosociality refers to the previously mentioned maintenance of hegemonic masculinity whilst horizontal homosociality describes the intimate non sexual relationships between men. Whilst challenging Bird's (1996) concept of a unilateral definition of homosociality, Hammarén and Johansson (2014) accept by defining vertical/hierarchical homosociality that it does defend and maintain hegemony as does Anderson (2008). By accepting Hammarén and Johansson's (2014) assertion that that homosociality can be redefined then we require to further define the homosocial interaction among young professional football players in this study. We return therefore to Bird's (1996) notion of competition. Whilst men compete within homosocial interactions to affirm their masculinity, being competitive in itself relates to masculinity. As Bird (1996) notes men whose conceptualisation of masculinity related to its hegemonic form prefer homosocial interactions in sports. Indeed, according to Bird (1996), in homosocial groups of men a lack of competitiveness leads to a loss of status. In this study, the young men competed to assert and confirm their heterosexuality within the confines of a homosocial group of sports professionals.

Within this sporting environment, competition was central and fundamental to the group's success and existence with vertical homosociality being in evidence among the young men there was also evidence of horizontal. Relationships within this homosocial group are important for the young men and there is a degree of bonding that occurs:

Researcher: "Right, so you've all came through the ranks"?

Jack: "Aye, since we were like thirteen, fourteen. When we were in there, we were all kind of strangers to each other, and the football would take over and we would talk to each other, get on with each other, have a laugh and stuff".

Researcher: "so tell me a wee bit more about this dressing room atmosphere"?

Jack:" I put music oan, turn it up loud on the speakers an a' that and everybody's talkin', chattin' away",

Researcher: "does this atmosphere extend to outwith the dressing room"?

Jack: Aye. "You want to get every aspect of being a team. You get the team winning, losing, drawing, having a laugh on nights out, winning the league and going up the road and doing stuff, ken, the final, go to boot camps and all that and everything in between it- training. Everybody likes to experience that".

Researcher: "Do you all socialise together"?

Ian: Aye," the boys get on well with each other. We've obviously say we'll get a team night out and a team night out at Christmas. So we kinda arrange stuff like that."

Researcher: "Okay. In your time, have you achieved or have you seen any kind of personal benefits for your time in football? I mean, what have you got out it"?

Scott: "A lot of my pals have been fucking up at court and it's been kept away from that cos where I'm from- It's quite a rough area, a lot of stuff does happen. So obviously being away at weekends and whatnot, football has helped there."

Researcher: "So it's kept you on the straight and narrow a wee bit"?

Scott: "Aye definitely".

Homosociality for these young men is an important aspect of their gender construction. It is a key artefact for them that they use to construct hegemonic masculinity coupled with the element of bonding produced by the confirmation of heterosexuality. Whilst recognising that male bonding is culturally accepted and often valued, other elements are destructive and toxic. It is therefore useful here to discuss the terminology of toxic masculinity as it separates out the elements of hegemonic masculinity that are destructive to the individual himself such as violence, excessive alcohol use and so on (Kupers, 2005). Kupers (2005) reasserts that some elements of hegemony are culturally accepted and valued such as being a provider for family, an ability to succeed in sport or having a successful career or indeed an opportunity to bond with other males but other elements of hegemonic masculinity are not culturally accepted or valued such as the aforementioned misogyny or violent and aggressive behaviour. Messerschmidt (1993), for example, argues that for working class men, crime is often used to perform hegemonic masculinity, and in the communities that these young men live crime plays a significant role in particular violent crime.

Whilst bonding and socialisation evident in the football team are key artefacts in the construction and performance of hegemonic masculinity, gender identity and construction is also performed by these men out with the football club and often it is of a toxic nature. We suggest that whilst recognising that masculinities are multiple and are situationally specific with men producing and performing multiple masculinities, being a footballer in Scotland confers status as an idealised man. For these young men, therefore, performing, producing and reproducing hegemonic masculinity is an important element in their lives meaning that they must continue to live to the ideal no matter the situation even although often this could result in a more toxic construction:

Scott: "last season I wasn't fit for starting when I came back from holiday"

Researcher: "why was that"?

Scott: "I got jumped by three guys coming out of the sauna"

Researcher: "What happened? Can you tell me a bit more about that? Were you hurt"?

Scott: "Where I come from you need to watch where you go as there are lots of gangs and gang fighting".

Researcher: "Are you in a gang"?

Scott: "no I'm not in a gang but that doesn't mean I won't stand up for myself. I probably got hurt a bit more than I would have coz I did stand up for myself and not just lie down and take it".

Conclusion

This study recognises that not all the young men in this study are involved in the construction of the most toxic elements of masculinity; indeed, the above conversation was the only notable example of physical violence but we argue that its inclusion is noteworthy since it describes and outlines a configuration of practices. The toxic masculinity learned and practiced on the football field was via the creation of a strong athletic identity where commitment, athleticism, belonging and all being in it together translated to activity in the community where being a man for these young men was a full time occupation. The footballer as an iconic male must be seen to conform to that standard and must be seen to be keeping up appearances. Of course, as I already briefly noted, not every young man in this study constructed their gender around the most toxic form of masculinity but they are complicit in it via the constructed athletic identity. As Connell (1995 p79) reminds us complicit masculinities are,

“masculinities constructed in ways that realize the patriarchal dividend, without the tensions or risks of being the frontline troops of patriarchy”.

This complicity allows the other young men to construct their gender identity in such a way that their status will be retained thereby conferring on them by virtue of belonging to the school of masculinity the title of ‘real man’. This school of masculinity only limits its teaching to those constructions of masculinity that are the most socially dominant. Whether hegemonic, toxic, tough or complicit the result is always the same with a home win always being awarded. The next chapter further explores the nature of this athletic identity via an exploration of the emotions and embodiment related to masculinity.

CHAPTER 7: EMBODIMENT AND EMOTIONS

Introduction

This chapter describes the manifestation of hegemonic masculinity among the players at the club via perceptions of the value and imagery associated with body image and emotions. In doing so, it expands on the previous chapter by exploring the embodiment of this athletic identity. Utilising the data gathered from the interviews and field notes described in a previous chapter, it firstly outlines the importance of the role and function of a muscled body in the construction of idealised man and identifies specific examples that the players aspired to emulate. Next, the chapter outlines particular emotions inherent within the wider social world and highlights those deemed acceptable or not within football.

Muscularity

Hegemonic masculinity is multi-faceted and comprises many artefacts from the culture and environment. Chris, outlined for him a key component in the performance of hegemonic masculinity:

Researcher: "What do you like about being a footballer"?

Chris: "Being fit"

Researcher: "so your health is important to you"?

Chris: "Yeah having a body for the burds on the beach.....ha ha"

Researcher: "What do you mean by this"?

Chris: "Well women like to see fit guys don't they"?

Researcher: "Do they"?

Chris: "Yeah its like they like to see that you look after yourself and stuff they don't want to see big bellies on the beach and that, they wanna see muscles an' that".

For Chris, body image was important and it was a particular aspect of body image that the young men aspired to. According to McCreary, Saucier & Courtenay (2005) young men in developing ideal body image tend to focus on the chest area and in particular the muscular development of the pectorals, biceps, and shoulders. For McCreary et al (2005) it is these areas of the body that signify the ideal body image for men.

Chris was not alone in associating muscle with attractiveness to women. McCreary et al (2005) identify significant prior research that demonstrates the importance of being muscular in young men. In fact, McCreary et al (2005) suggests that men feel that women are more attracted to men who are heavily muscled. Not only do men feel that women are attracted to muscles, but in fact muscularity for many men equates to and exudes sex appeal and is therefore directly associated with attracting a mate (Steinfeldt, Gilchrist, Halterman, Gomory, & Steinfeldt 2011). Muscularity for men, whilst having sex appeal, remains predominantly associated with power, strength and therefore dominance (Gattario, Frisen, Fuller-Tyszkiewicz, Ricciardelli, Diedrichs, Yager, Franko, and Smolak, 2015). I noted earlier in this chapter that young men use a range of artefacts in becoming a man. Gattario et al (2015) suggest that the attainment of a muscular body completes the quest in actually being a man. Achievement of muscle mass, we have noted, correlates to the ideal body for men with the perceived benefits that it brings and its correlation with hegemonic masculinity. We also demonstrated earlier that being a man means not being a women and the rejection of femininity. Extensive research identified by McCreary et al (2005)

holds the same to be true for muscularity in that, whilst muscularity and muscle mass correlate with masculinity, a lack of muscle mass correlates to femininity.

I noted in an earlier chapter the significant role of sport in developing 'manliness' after the leisure revolution brought about as a result of the industrial revolution in Victorian Britain. These muscular Christians advocated sport for developing a 'manly' character since manliness was viewed as an "antidote to the poison of effeminacy" (Watson, et al, 2005 p1). It would appear therefore that little has changed with football's link with muscularity and muscularity's association with masculinity. This study appeared to confirm and affirm those early Victorian values, as illustrated during multiple interviews with the young players when asked to define masculinity:

Researcher: "If I said the word 'masculinity' to you what do you think that means"?

Ian: "Strength"?

Researcher: "Can you say a bit more"?

Ian: "dunno? Like having muscles and that".

Researcher: "Do you need to have muscles to be masculine"?

Ian: "Be like a man I suppose".

Researcher: "If I said the word 'masculinity' to you what do you think that means"?

David: "Being big".

Researcher: "What do you mean being big"?

David: "Like being strong, going in for hard tackles"

Researcher: "Do you consider yourself masculine"?

David: I think so, coz I'm tall and I go to the gym as often as I can"

Researcher: "If I said the word 'masculinity' to you what do you think that means"?

Mark: "Being a man"?

Researcher: "Can you tell me more about what you mean"?

Mark: "Being strong and that"

Researcher: "Are there other features that make someone masculine other than just being strong"?

Mark: "Looking after your body I suppose, being fit and having muscles".

Whilst the participants, despite probing struggled to define what being masculine was or what defined masculinity, Ian, David and Mark, like Chris saw being a man equated to being strong and muscular and football provided this for them. Body image was vital to their construction of masculinity and defined what being a man was about. Indeed, as Murray & Touyz (2012) indicate, the drive for a more muscular physique and muscularity is the preference for most men as it provides the idealised body image currently accepted in Western culture. This is consistent with the findings from Connell (1995), who identified the role of body shape and body size as markers of gendered identity. Indeed, as Gorely, Holroyd and Kirk (2003) indicate, echoing the thoughts of Chris, having an idealised male muscular body indicates that you are heterosexual. Being male and having a thin 'feminine'-type body indicates that you are homosexual. I intend to discuss the issue of sexuality and sexual orientation later in this thesis.

For the young men in this study, being a man and masculinity were closely linked so the study sought to investigate how the young men defined themselves:

Researcher: "Okay, I wonder if I used the word 'masculinity', What would that mean to you"?

Steven: "Manly, be the kinda, dominant person".

Researcher: "So there's certain characteristics that are masculine"?

Steven: "Kinda...somebody's said to me they were masculine then I'd expect them tae be brave, an' bold".

Researcher: "Can you tell me more"?

Steven: "Not being afraid, kinda stick up for themselves"

Steven equated manliness and masculinity but further identified qualities and characteristics of being a man rather than the physicality of it. In investigating further, I sought to investigate how these identified qualities of being a man translated into football for the young men:

Researcher: "Who would you say was the most masculine footballer in the Scottish premier league"? (the top division in Scottish football)

Ian: "Virgil Van Dijk"

Researcher: "Why"?

Ian: "He's big, strong, muscly, and he is able to bully people".

Virgil Van Dijk is a Dutch footballer and at the time of this study was playing for Glasgow Celtic. His Wikipedia entry puts him at 1.93m and 92kg. Virgil Van Dijk currently plays as a 'central defender', traditionally, this position is the preserve of players known for their height and physicality. We surmise, therefore, that the young men's definition of masculinity as being about 'big and strong' can also translate to being tall and physically strong. Strength and muscularity seem to go hand in hand and appear to have almost the same meaning for the young men as strength was regularly quoted as a key element of masculinity but 'muscly' was quoted as a key element of being a man. As well as the tall, strong defender Virgil Van Dijk being identified as being masculine, it was somewhat unsurprising given that he played for arguably the biggest club currently playing football in Scotland. However, in identifying the most masculine footballer in Scotland, many of the young men identified a midfielder playing for a provincial club in Paisley. The footballer Jim Goodwin is not

particularly well known even among followers of the game, having played for less glamorous clubs in Scotland and England (Stockport County, Scunthorpe United, Huddersfield Town, Hamilton Academical, St Mirren and Alloa Athletic.) However, it is perhaps his reputation that suggests his masculinity and therefore the reason for selection by the young men. The popular football statistics website Transfermarkt.co.uk (2018) lists Jim Goodwin as having received 49 'yellow' cards from 151 games played, having the 11th worst disciplinary record of all time (since season 2003/04):

Researcher: "Who would you say then was the most masculine footballer in the Scottish premier league"?

Paul: "Jim Goodwin"

Researcher: "Jim Goodwin? Why him"?

Paul: "Well he plays in my position and he's tough, quite aggressive like".

Researcher: "So is he someone that you use as a role model"?

Paul: "Definitely, you can see that he's not afraid to get stuck in and put himself about".

Researcher: "Put himself about"?

Paul: "Yeah like I said, he's aggressive and doesn't back down from tackles and that".

Researcher: "Who would you say then was the most masculine footballer in the Scottish premier league"?

Dougie: "Jim Goodwin".

Researcher: "Who plays for? Sorry you need to help me".

Dougie: "St. Mirren".

Researcher: "Why do you think he's the most masculine"?

Dougie: "Just the aggression he shows in the game, he's never afraid to get in about the game and nobody bullies him"

Researcher: "Who do you think is the most masculine, footballer playing in the SPFL"?

Wullie: "Probably Jim Goodwin fae St. Mirren".

Researcher: "Why? What is it about him"?

Wullie: "He's quite a – a hardy person, he's quite, he gets himsel' in the park and he's just, he's quite a scary guy, you think, he's quite, you wouldnae go near him if ye see 'im cos he's quite a big guy".

A key element of this research was to establish how gender was constructed among young professional footballers in Scotland so utilising the imagery from the exemplars identified by the young people as well as the adjectives used to describe qualities of manliness, the researcher asked the young men to describe themselves:

Researcher: "How would you consider yourself masculine"?

Scott: "Through appearance- you can tell if someone's masculine. Tall, strong, big and you get people who are small and you don't really think they're masculine".

Researcher: "So you think that there are characteristics that aren't masculine"?

Scott: "Aye- like small, really skinny".

Researcher: "You told me earlier that Jim Goodwin was masculine due to his qualities. Do you think there are characteristics and qualities that are not very masculine"?

Wullie: "Aye, being weak and shy".

Researcher: "Do you think there are characteristics of people who are not masculine"?

Ian: "Aye, kinda weak...kinda get awa' fae situations".

For these young men, being weak, small, shy and afraid were characteristics that were less desirable in a man. To be weak and afraid is in the eyes of these young men was to be less of a man:

Researcher: "How would you respond if I said to you, if I say the word masculinity. What would that mean to you"?

Paul: "Mmm, I don't really know. 'Masculine'? What does that mean? Is that being a man's man"?

Researcher: "Okay- what do you think it means".

Paul: "That's what I think it means; being a man's man. Getting people to shave their chest and that like erm, girl's kinda man, I don't know, haha"!

Gender hegemony operates not just through the subordination of femininity but also through the subordination and marginalization of other masculinities (Connell 1995). For the young men in this study they identified that there are other constructions of masculinity available and indeed multiple masculinities. There are clearly men out there who are "weak and shy" or "small and skinny", but are dismissed as weak and even ridiculed. Connell & Messerschmidt (2005), in rethinking the concept of hegemonic masculinity, concede that an understanding of hegemonic masculinity requires the incorporation of a more holistic understanding of the gender hierarchy that recognises and takes account of the role and function of subordinated groups. Further Connell & Messerschmidt (2005) note that gender is relational and constructed with respect to femininity. For the young men in this study this gender hierarchy provided clear delineation of what qualities and characteristics make a 'real man' and the relationships within this hierarchy were defined by the young men in this study who recognised multiple masculinities and even made reference to men who shaved their chests as being like a 'girl' kind of man. The young men in this study recognised multiple masculinities but subordinated some by reference to characteristics of them that often were associated with femininity. Being weak, shy, afraid were not qualities and characteristics that were viewed as desirable in men and these qualities were ridiculed, diminished and dismissed. The next section of this thesis further explores

the qualities that were seen to define a real man and begins to examine the components that define hegemonic masculinity.

Boys don't cry

The importance of the naming of professional players by the young men in this study who exhibited physical strength, height and power cannot be underestimated. For them, 'toughness' and 'hardness' were key attributes of their role models. Similar to an educational environment, visual aids such as tactics boards were often employed by the coaches to illustrate and emphasise a specific learning point.

Match day programmes, for example, were such visual aids as they regularly carried a feature headlined "The Hard Men" that contained a short biography of players from the past years. Most of these players exhibited physicality, strength and height, much of the attributes that according to participants defined what being a man was all about. Invariably these 'hard men' played as central defenders or central midfielders. The biographies of these players was presented alongside a large picture of the individual player. These photographs often depicted the player in action. One particular 'hard man' was playing with a head bandage stained with blood. In another photograph, the 'hard man' is seen challenging for a ball with a member of the opposition captured almost mid-flight heading towards the ground as a result of the 'hard mans' challenge. The feature that regularly appeared throughout the match day programme celebrated the contribution to the team of the 'hard man' and ends inevitably with the hard man's career ending prematurely. Toughness and 'hardness' for these young men were implicit parts of being a footballer and were often interchangeable as these field notes illustrate:

“The midfielder looks like he is through on goal with only the goalkeeper to beat. As the goalkeeper advances to narrow the shooting angle, a collision occurs. As the players collide a crack like a gun going off echoes across the field. This stomach churning crack is immediately followed by screams of pain and I realise a serious injury has occurred. As the coach tends to the injured player and an ambulance is called due to the severity of the injury, the rest of the team undergo some exercise to keep the muscles warm seemingly oblivious to their team mate who awaits the arrival of paramedics” (Field note)

“We’re midway through the second half now as a lunging tackle by a defender results in another stomach churning moment, This time it’s an opposition player awaiting the arrival of medical help and a trip to hospital. After consultation with the referee the match is abandoned and we troop off to the dressing room” (Field note)

“On board the bus ready to return home, as the coach calls a roll call to check everyone is present, loud laughter accompanies the injured player who is presumably by now in hospital”
The young men appear afraid to show sympathy or empathy for their clearly seriously injured team mate perhaps due to the fear of being branded weak or showing unacceptable emotion
(Field note)

In the previous section, I identified specific qualities and characteristics of being a man but in addition being a man was not simply about the presence on the football field. Being seen as hard and tough is important for the young men. Standing up for oneself whether it’s on a football field or elsewhere in life is important too:

Researcher: “I wonder if I used the word ‘masculinity’, what would that mean to you”?

Douglas: “Manly, kinda...don’t let anybody push ye around”

Researcher: “what do you mean”?

Douglas: "Being able to stand up for yourself, like don't get intimidated, not backing down I think"

Not being weak or seen as a pushover are important elements of their identity. The ability to stand up and take on other men when challenged in a fight or not to be pushed around, or not to want to shy away from situations. Being tough or hard is important to them and as Frosh, Phoenix and Pattman (2003) note that being hard plays an influential part in male views of themselves on being properly masculine.

I further noted earlier the influential role played by male family members in the development of gender identity and the construction of hegemonic masculinity among these young men, by the role that particularly fathers play in initiation into the game. Within this culture there exists a number of actors whose influence on others cannot be ignored and for these young men others within their cultural sphere can be significantly important in constructing their gender identity by teaching and modelling. It is therefore useful at this juncture to introduce the concept of the football club as a school of masculinity. Like the school setting, football offers a range of role models. Like the school, skills, strategies and techniques are learned that equip the young person for modern Western life. Like the school, there are rules to be followed and penalties for breaking the rules with the ultimate sanction being exclusion for failure and like the school there are codes for dress and codes of behaviour that have to be followed. Parker (2006) highlighted that the participants in this study, as football apprentices were in fact still within an educational within the broader context of lifelong learning where much like the traditional trades apprenticeships work based skills were passed on. Within the educational establishment like in the school setting highlighted by Lunenberg, Korthagen, and Swennen (2007), a teacher performs a number of

functions including that of role model. In this school of masculinity the first team players ultimately perform this role as the young men aspire to gaining a first team place alongside these 'exemplars'. Parker (2006) identified communities of practice where younger players are increasingly exposed to the practices of more experienced players, thereby gradually developing the ideas and skills that ensure that the young players then adopt this practice and fit into the community. Bricheno, & Thornton, (2008) however note that often it is not only teachers but peers that can be influential as role models. In this school, role models are across the organisation and are clearly understood as this conversation with Craig reveals,

Researcher: "So how important is it to be involved in a team then"?

Craig: "Yeah cos you learn off your team mates and everyone"

Researcher: "What do you learn"?

Craig: "Just like, responsibilities and you get maturity from it because ye look up to them as if-like especially if you're looking to the older ones and you look up to them and they're your role models and you want to be where they are".

Researcher: "What do you mean by that 'role models'?"

Craig: "Eh, just like, you just aspire tae be like them. You see what they have done and what they have achieved and you want to do what they have done".

Craig aspires to be like the older players and looks up to them. These older players, the teachers in this school of masculinity, stare out at them regularly in full colour from the pages of the match day programme, battered, bruised and bloodied whilst often inflicting similar outcomes on opposition players. We noted earlier that the players outside the team that are role models are those players who are big, strong, tough, and aggressive, in fact for these young players the embodiment of masculinity. Connell (2015) reminds us that for a form of masculinity to be deemed hegemonic it must be

culturally exalted with exemplars celebrated as heroes. The exemplars for these young men are throughout the team from their peers, the older players in the squad, ex-players and players currently playing for other teams. Being strong and tough is often not just about physicality, or muscularity or having an idealised body. Often, being tough for these young men is about an ability to control emotions, remain emotionless, or to only exhibit the emotions that are desirable of a real man:

Researcher: "So if you got beat in a game you wouldn't cry, for example".

Sean: "Naw, you wouldnae".

Researcher: "Why not"?

Sean: "You just wouldnae express that in case somebody like, brought it up and slagged you for it, kinda thing"

Researcher: "Why would it not be alright"?

Sean: "Because it's not really a male thing to do is it"?

The above conversation with Sean sought to explore the emotional aspects of being a footballer and the range of emotions experienced and how individuals respond and cope based on the particular situation. Sean for instance recognises that a negative emotion like sadness can be demonstrated in a high profile important game but crying is not allowed as you will be 'slagged' (ridiculed) as it's not a male thing to do.

Researcher: "What about individual emotions, y'know on the pitch. Do you think it's acceptable to... you know, be sad on the pitch- to cry, for example"?

Paul: "You shouldn't be that low, you shouldn't be crying".

Paul views those who cry as 'low' inferring similar to Sean that men who cry are not male. Real men do not cry as crying goes against everything that defines a man

(Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; Messerschmidt, 2010). In addition, this expression of emotion, particularly crying is further associated with femininity and is seen as a particularly feminine trait (Wong, Pituch, and Rochlen 2006). Whilst this emotional response is viewed as unacceptable given its links with femininity, it needs to be set against the background and the context of this particular peer group. We know from Swain (2006) that a peer group has a significant influence in the construction of masculinity and the construction of this masculinity will determine the status within that peer group. Crying would therefore diminish a player's status among the rest of the team and thereby diminish his status as a man playing a man's game. We assert and conclude therefore that Paul's retort that crying is 'low' might indeed refer to the status of those who cry and that it refers to their status as men. In showing emotions, your status as a man is diminished as crying is often seen as a feminine emotion. As Oransky and Marecek (2009) note, feelings and emotions that display vulnerability or trouble are emotions and feelings that are undesirable in a man. Oransky and Marecek (2009) confirm our earlier assertion that often it is better just to remain emotionless in case this becomes misconstrued. Alan appears to confirm that emotion and being a man are incompatible:

Researcher: "Do you think it's okay, or how acceptable or how okay is it for men to show emotion on a football field"?

Alan: "Big so it is, a lot of men won't show emotion off the field but when they're on the field they're a completely different person".

The young men in this study suggest that with football being such an emotional game that whilst crying was not an appropriate emotion to display, some emotions are okay to display. As Alan continues,

Researcher: "Why? Why do you think that is"?

Alan: "Though determination to win. If they don't win they're disappointed in themselves".

Researcher: "Okay, so any other emotions"

Alan: "Mmm, yeah, you get all different emotions really. Anger's one of the main yins. You get angry at the people with bad tackles or not doing something right".

Sean agrees that emotions are okay to display but quantifies this,

Researcher: "Do you think football's an emotional game then"?

Sean: "I think it is, yeah. It's a bit emotional, aye, because, like ye need tae have something in ye, like desire, kinda thing, tae get through it and sometimes there's ups and downs. You need tae kinda deal wi' them".

Researcher: "How acceptable is it then, to show those emotions on a field"?

Sean: "I think it depends on what emotions it is".

Researcher: "Okay, tell me a wee bit more about that then".

Sean: "If it wis, anger kinda thing sometimes you can show it but if you take it too far then I don't think it is right tae show it and- I dunno what you call it, but if you were, if you're eh, happy or what, then cannae really show it til the game's finished in case you get overconfident and maybe lose".

Sean is prepared to accept that anger is permissible. Ian agrees that anger is an acceptable emotion:

Researcher: "Is it okay to be angry on a football field and to show that anger"?

Ian: "Uh-huh cos it can come down to how passionate you are, it shows that you are committed".

Our ontological perspective of social constructionism offers some explanation of the emotions that are seen as permissible or prohibited. Walton, Coyle, & Lyons, (2004) explain that emotions are in effect resources which allow for positioning relative to

others. Furthermore, Walton, et al, (2004) suggest that in constructing the hegemonic form of masculinity it is therefore acceptable to hide emotions that suggest or imply vulnerability or weakness but emotions such as anger are permissible. For men, the display of emotion is specifically centred and contextualised. Like this study, for Walton, et al (2004) football provides the ideal situational context for the display of permitted emotions. Whilst it is permissible to demonstrate anger the following field notes suggest that anger directed towards you is also permissible

“If you thought that performance was acceptable then you better think about taking up another sport. hurry up and get dressed and get the fuck out of here.” (field note – coach full time team talk)

“Did any of you actually listen to what I said before the game? And as for you (points to player) what the fuck do you think you’re doing out there? I could’ve taken you off after five minutes buck your fucking ideas up or you’re out of here. You’re playing in the first division for fuck sake. You really cant get any lower”. (field note – coach half time team talk)

“Don’t you fuckin’ dare talk back to me and try to tell me you played well out there today, who the fuck do you think you are” (field note – coach full time team talk)

Anger and aggression are part of the game and displays of anger and aggression are acceptable and perhaps even expected and welcomed:

Researcher: “What if it’s not been a good performance”?

Paul: “Just, coaches shout an’ things...”

Researcher: “And how does that make you feel”?

Paul: “Spouse, I mean. It’s good if it didn’t happen, you know what I mean, then you come back and try perform better then next week”.

Researcher: "Do you think, that shouting helps you"?

Paul: "Aye".

Researcher: "How does it help"?

Paul: "Makes sure you do better next time"

Wullie echoes the sentiments of Paul and suggests that this aggressive behaviour by coaches is the fault of the players themselves:

Researcher: "What's the feeling like in the dressing room after a loss"?

Wullie: "Everybody's down and that and you try to think about what you could have done better"

Researcher: "Do the coaches help"?

Wullie: "Sometimes, depends how you've played. Like if we should've won or something then you know you're going to shouted at and that but you've only yourself to blame really".

According to Bekiari and Sympas (2015) however this verbal aggression by the coach does not lead to better outcomes. In fact, Bekiari and Sympas (2015) highlighted that verbal aggression may in fact confer negative outcomes on the players as it may actually make them less motivated. Mazer, Barnes, Grevious, and Boger (2013) agreed that a verbally aggressive coach reduces motivation however, Mazer, et al (2013) go further and suggested that verbally aggressive coaches are also viewed as less competent, trustworthy, and caring. Despite the negative outcomes associated with aggression in coaches, Mazer et al (2013) highlight that this behaviour is widespread in competitive sport. Bekiari, Digelidis and Sakelariou (2006) noted that this aggressive behaviour is more widespread in contact sports. Furthermore Bekiari, et al (2006) suggest that the more contact that is allowed in the sport, the higher the incidences of coach aggression.

As Messerschmidt (2017 p75) notes “hegemonic masculinities must be culturally ascendant to provide a rationale for social action through consent and compliance”. It is this consent and compliance through the acceptance of aggressive and angry behaviour that allows the culturally ascendant hegemonic form of masculinity to be constructed in the context of football. The use of swear words is a particular artefact in this construction and social context. The use of swear words are not acceptable in other contexts and situations:

Researcher: “So is there things you would do, or things that are okay in football that are maybe not okay outside of football”?

Alan: “Well, maybe like swearing on the park an’ that. You wouldn’t want to be walkin’ about swearin’ in the streets”.

Researcher: “Okay, but swearing on a football park is okay”?

Alan: “Aye it is, its part of the game, everyone swears in football”.

Swearing is part of this localised cultural context and performs a dual function in the construction of gender identity. Swearing maintains status (Swain 2002) as well as intensifying an emotion or sentiment within football (Byrne. and Corney 2014). Swearing was a regular feature of this masculine discourse and seemed to be part of part of the language of the game as much as corners, offside, fouls and penalty box are. Nuhrat (2017) confirmed that swearing is part and parcel of the game of football. Despite efforts by the football authorities in Turkey to eliminate swearing by suggesting that it is not compatible with fair play, swearing allows for the construction of hegemonic masculinity among men (Nuhrat, 2017).

We illustrate the use of swearing to highlight the more toxic element of gender construction in this thesis particularly around the emotional responses of anger and aggression but swearing is utilised in the game in a variety of contexts becoming part of the tradition of the game:

“Fuckin’ great pass” (Field note)

was a regular term used at training as was its opposite,

“fuckin shite pass” (Field note)

or more commonly,

“fuck sake [Scott,] [Ian] [Alan)” (Field note)

Even during the game itself swearing goes unchallenged and appears acceptable:

“Fuck same lino [linesman] that was never offside open your fucking eyes”! (field note)

“Ref, Ref that’s a fuckin penalty”! (field note)

Team meetings held by coaches at the end of training further utilise swearing:

“Now that we’re all packed up and ready to go with cars waiting in the car park to pick the players up we gather in the silence of the now deserted training pitch with only the seagulls for company for the coaches’ parting words in respect of the game tomorrow. “We can beat these cunts tomorrow. Their first team lost 9-1 last week to the worst fucking team in the league. Their big centre half who played in that game will probably play against us” (Field note)

According to Coates (2008), swearing in itself performs hegemonic masculinity particularly the use of the most 'taboo' words as it separates masculine discourse from feminine discourses. Jones (2008) confirms this relationship of the link with swearing and masculinity noting that women disapprove of swearing at football and fail to join in with it as it's not viewed as an acceptable feminine practice. Much like the language developed in the traditional school of education, discourses in the school of masculinity adopt a different language. A language utilising some of the most taboo words in society today but are part of the culture and tradition in football.

In discussing the site of a football club as a school of masculinity, football clearly teaches many lessons for young men aspiring to confirm their identity, but there are several expectations of behaviour expected. As Parker (1996) notes, it is a given that within football you will identify with heterosexuality. With schools being traditionally recognized as socially conservative organisations that reproduce orthodox notions of sexuality, in particular heterosexuality (McCormack, 2014).

I continue to illustrate and evidence that the construction of masculinities are bound within a particular context. Therefore being or becoming a man means constructing oneself by the available artefacts in a particular time and place. In this particular context and localised culture, the peer group has significant influence as it provides boys with a series of shared meanings of what it is to be a man (Connell 2000).

Conclusion

This chapter described what it meant to be a footballer for these young men, and outlined how football shaped their masculine identity. Furthermore, not only does this chapter outline how football shaped this masculine identity and how the idealised form

of masculinity was shaped, the chapter illustrated that this idealised form of masculinity was learned and was in fact taught by coaches and older players acting as mentors and role models.

Much like a school, the semi closed all-consuming environment of the football club described by Parker and Manley (2017) created a specific environment where, through interacting with others, a particular identity was constructed, an identity that sought promotion of it over others, specifically women who are marginalised, objectified and demeaned. An environment where the idealised form of masculinity is celebrated and embraced in a safe protected environment that provided camaraderie and comradeship. An environment that made one into a man, much like the safe male only environments outlined and described by Clayton and Harris (2008) and Clayton and Humberstone (2006). An environment that created expectations and for some could deliver potentially significant rewards thereby further celebrating and authenticating this sense of entitlement and privilege. Very early in this thesis we discussed and outlining the theoretical framework asserting that as Connell (2009) notes, “one is not born masculine, but has to become a man” (p 5).

This chapter illustrated that football remains a significant determinant of becoming a man, but not just a man but of the ideal man who is celebrated. idolised and tough, where emotions such as crying are deemed feminine and unacceptable. The next chapter provides further insight into how masculine identity was constructed in relation to women and femininity.

CHAPTER 8: EVERYDAY MISOGYNY, SEXISM AND MASCULINITY

Introduction

This chapter draws on the thematic analysis and integrates the inductive insights whilst relating to the extant literature within the theme of everyday misogyny, sexism and masculinity in football by providing an analysis of how gender identity is constructed in relation to and in opposition to women and femininity. Whilst the key agents of sports socialisation within the current sample were men (primarily fathers), women were involved in football and were seen to have a role. However, often women are restricted to a peripheral role and function within the game. This peripheral role perhaps played a key part in the development of gender identity in the young men as it promoted hegemony and maintained the patriarchal divide.

Women on the periphery

“Football is a game of hard physical contact, a form of combat. It is, and must remain, a man’s game. Women have no place in it except to cheer on their men, wash and iron their kit and prepare and serve refreshments” Ted Croker – Secretary of the English FA 1988 cited in Dunning (2001).

One of the key principles of hegemonic masculinity is the deliberate exclusion of women, so keeping women excluded and on the periphery is central to developing one’s gender identity. Whilst the female family members of the players were kept on the periphery by often having to take on a caring role, other women performed other

peripheral roles such as providing refreshments for players and spectators as this field note illustrated:

“After a long drive across country which involved an early start the little kiosk serving tea, coffee and hot rolls with bacon, eggs and sausages is a new and welcome sight particularly as it rained non-stop and we’ll get wet again. The players are not allowed food from the kiosk but the friendly women behind the counter are happy to provide the players with jugs of diluting juice to take into the dressing room.” (field note).

Whilst some women were utilised to serve refreshments at football, some provided a caring role for other siblings but others were presented as entertainment before and during the main sporting event, illustrated by these observations from a match involving the first team:

“As the teams enter the field from the tunnel, to the rousing music and cheers from the fans, a guard of honour is formed with teen and preteen cheerleaders waving brightly coloured pom poms” (field note)

“As the players leave the pitch for half time, a high energy dance tune begins to boom out from the public address system and the same cheerleaders who provided the earlier guard of honour for the players form up and begin to wave their pompoms, perform high kicks and even throw in a somersault or two” (field note).

However Giulianotti (2002) suggests that, far from being peripheral to the main event and as entertainment for men, the introduction of cheerleaders into football was as a result of what he refers to as the ‘commodification’ of football via the introduction of features of American sports events in order to generate the associated razzamatazz in order to attract new fans. Giulianotti (2002) further suggests that this

commodification of football has resulted in football fans now being able to be classified into one of four categories underpinned by two basic binary oppositions: hot-cool and traditional-consumer thereby creating four quadrants that a football fan could be allocated to. At opposite ends sit the traditional/hot football fan who will likely have a long term, localised connection with the club. Giulianotti (2002) argues that whilst the traditional football fan may become a consumer by the purchase of shares or club merchandise these acts are to demonstrate solidarity since the fan often has a lifetime relationship with the club. These traditional supporters support the club for life and would never consider switching allegiance to another club whereas the consumer/cool whom Giulianotti (2002) refers to as 'flaneurs' who may be male or female and will have no allegiances even switching clubs where a particular player switches club.

The 'flaneur' will purchase merchandise based on its aesthetic value rather than any emotional attachment. Giulianotti (2002) specifically cites the examples of Real Madrid and Manchester United as clubs that attract the consumer hot and consumer cold (flaneur) fans. These two clubs are global brands with international globally recognised players. It may well be the case that American razzamatazz with cheerleaders, pom poms, hot dogs and merchandise will indeed attract new fans and female fans in particular to watch football played by high profile, global branded clubs, however the profile of football clubs playing in South West Scotland do not have international globally recognised players, a significant media/television exposure, aesthetically pleasing high fashion football shirts or any of the other elements that attract the consumer fans. Whilst Giulianotti (2002) suggests that the introduction of cheerleaders into football may have been an attempt to attract the consumer fan especially the 'flaneur' who may well be female, the cheerleader also allows men to confirm, reinforce

and exhibit the most desirable masculine trait, heterosexuality (Anderson 2005). As Anderson (2005) further notes, men attempt to approximate the hegemonic form of masculinity by devaluing women. As McDowell and Schaffner (2011) note, the role of the cheerleader is to be feminine, glamorous, and cheerful with glittering smiles whilst cheering on their guys. This overt display of emphasised femininity in miniskirts is overtly sexual in nature and contributes to the overall sexualisation of women in football regularly witnessed at football.

This sexualisation of women has not according to Cleland, Pope and Williams (2020) reduced significantly despite the increasing levels of women now attending and playing football. The Guardian newspaper (2015) for example reported on several incidents where the female Chelsea club doctor was the victim of sexual chats that resulted in no action being taken against the club or against the significant number of individuals engaging in such chats. Indeed, the Guardian (2015) notes that one of the most sexualised chants was accompanied by laughter from the surrounding fans. The newspaper reports that during the football season in question (2013/14), thirteen incidents of large scale abusive sexual chanting were recorded with victims including the aforementioned club doctor as well as clubs cheerleaders. As Forbes et al (2015) noted, even when challenged, language that demeans and subordinates women at football is often dismissed as 'banter'. Cleland, et al (2020) suggest that a report highlighted incidences of harassment and sexual discrimination of women actually rising by 400%. Cleland, et al (2020) noted that sexualised chanting, harassment and discrimination are not just confined to the U.K. By way of confirmation, Ncube and Chawana (2018) for example highlighted several songs sung by fans of some of the most popular teams in Zimbabwe that referred to sexual acts against women often

implying rape. In addition, Ncube and Chawana (2018) noted that other songs suggested that women were responsible for men looking at their private parts by not 'sitting properly'. It is therefore unsurprising that women who are interested in football struggle to gain recognition or become involved in any meaningful way and remain in peripheral roles. Whilst Giulianotti (2002) notes the rise of the 'flaneurs' with the respect to high level, high profile football, Pfister et al (2013) reports on a study that shows that even at the high profile, high level football of the English Premier league (EPL), attendances from women range only from between 5% and 8.5%. Despite the introduction of American razzamatazz via cheerleaders in order to attract the consumer fans, attendances at football among female fans remain low.

According to Pfister et al (2013), however, when women do attend football it is not to watch with other women. Pfister et al (2013) further suggested that women follow games alone or, much more often, in the company of men. The following field notes highlighted a lack of female attendance:

"Directly in front of me are a group of young people aged around 11-12 clearly excited about the upcoming game and getting to see their heroes. They are noisy and boisterous. In the group of about 15, none are female. The two leaders with them are also male." (field note)

"Glancing around the stadium whilst awaiting the arrival of the teams, I note the lack of female supporters among the crowd. There are some but those there are, they appear to be accompanied by large groups of men or one man whom I assume is a partner. There does not appear to be any single females or even groups of females." (field note)

Women at football remain peripheral. Pfister et al (2013) further suggested that women may not attend football due to the overt displays of masculinity. This notion of overt masculinity is illustrated in the following field notes that were observed at a match:

“Hullo, hullo we are the (home team) boys, hullo hullo you’ll hear us by our noise, we’re up to our ears in (opponents’) blood, surrender or you’ll die.” (field note)

Here, the chant conjured images of violence and aggression directed towards the opposition fans and players. After a rough challenge by an opposition player that resulted in the home team player receiving treatment the chant began,

“We hate (name of player) he’s a poof, he’s a poof.

We hate (name of player) he’s a poof, he’s a poof”

The player has no option but to ignore the chants and resume playing (field note)

Decisions that go against the home team are often met with displays of aggressive overt masculinity:

“A goal for the away team. The goal scorer shows his obvious delight by running behind the goal to the home support. This seems to rile a section of the home support with some leaving their seats to run to the front shouting angrily and screaming obscenities at him. Whilst I can’t hear everything being shouted, it sounds like every second word seems to be swear words. The anger and aggression on the faces of these supporters is however clear” (field note).

It was not just players who were subjected to aggressive and abusive shouting but also match officials:

“One of the match officials has just decided by means of raising his flag that the goal scored has not been allowed. Amid the chorus of jeers and booing I hear loud calls of stick that fucking flag up your arse” (field note).

Whilst not every man at the games was involved in some chanting or abusive shouting, this however provides evidence of what Connell (2005 p79) describes as “complicit masculinity” in which men practice a masculinity that is complicit with hegemonic masculinity but “compromise with women rather than naked[ly] dominating them”. Whilst not actively dominating women, this kind of complicit provides the opportunity for young men to become initiated into the game in the absence of women and provides the framework and background to becoming a man and the maintaining of the patriarchal dividend.

Whilst one of the reasons why women may stay away from football is due to these masculine displays, others who do attend may perform a level of masculinity in order to distance themselves from the emphasised femininity that Connell (1987 p183) defined as “oriented to accommodating the interests and desires of men”. Indeed, as Jones (2008) suggests, women who do attend football may not want to be seen as women due to the connotations surrounding emphasised femininity. Ussher (1997) suggests that women football fans in effect perform ‘resisting girl’ where women ignore or deny the traditionally signified ‘femininity’, such as the necessity for body discipline and adoption of the mask of beauty, but do not reject all that is associated with what it is to be a ‘woman’. Ussher (1997) further describes subverting femininity’ that refers to those women who ‘knowingly play with gender as a performance, twisting, imitating and parodying traditional scripts of femininity as opposed to ‘being girl’.

An examination of Burncastle FC's website illustrates the growing numbers of girls participating in football. The club now has girls playing football at all ages, in particular via their 7 year olds team, the 9 year olds team, the 11 year olds team, the 13 year olds team, the 15 year olds team and the 17 year olds team as well as an adult women's squad playing in relevant leagues.

In Scotland currently, the Scottish Football Association (SFA) rules allow mixed football up to the age of fifteen. According to the Association, this is because "football is a gender-affected sport in which the physical strength, stamina and/or physique of an average person of one sex puts them at an advantage or a disadvantage to an average person of the other gender as competitors in a football match" (SFA 2015 page 1) thereby reinforcing and maintaining the role of football being considered as the natural domain of men, through the continued reproduction of gendered ideologies. Hargreaves (1986 p110) notes that these gendered ideologies regard men and women as having "a fixed biological and psychological nature that are essentially different". This gendered ideology manifested by rules of the game ensures that sport, according to Dufur (2006), continues to be a vehicle where men can separate themselves from women by restricting women from participating in games and contests and by using those events to emphasize physical size and strength. Despite SFA rules allowing mixed teams until aged fifteen, there were no mixed teams at Burncastle and it was observed that both sexes played at separate times at separate venues and indeed trained separately. The following field notes illustrate that if mixed teams were unachievable, mixed training should be easily attainable:

"After the obligatory stretching, the boys begin a gentle jog around the park whilst the coaches lay out the cones. Upon returning from the warm up three circles are formed. I quickly recognise

this game from my childhood. It's 'piggy in the middle' with the object of the game being the player in the middle having to retrieve the ball as the players surrounding him pass the ball to and fro. If a pass is intercepted the player playing the pass is then in the middle. Much laughter and hilarity is generated but it is taken seriously. No one wants to be in the middle as a misplaced pass that results in the offender being in the middle results in ridicule from others” (field note)

“I am becoming more and more familiar with the training regime and as the players form two lines four or five metres apart I quickly recognise that the aim of the exercise is to make an accurate pass to the player opposite and then join the end of the opposite line.” (field note).

“Another drill involves the three groups of four or five players in a circle where the aim of the game is only to have one touch of the ball. It is fast paced as the players must keep the ball within the circle using only this one touch.” (field note)

The multiple training sessions observed were always skills development in nature and almost all focussed on passing, positioning and ball control. No training sessions observed by the researcher involved particular exercises that required physical strength or power. The whole nature of the game was set up to exclude female participation and even perhaps to discourage female participation as a field note from a game illustrates:

“As the teams line up to await the kick off with everyone in position ready for kick off, the young people behind the goals and at trackside ready to collect and return the ball should it go out of play are wearing bibs that identify them with 'ball boy' clearly marked on the back.” (field note).

Should girls wish to take on this role, I was unclear as to whether a 'ball girl' bib existed since no females were evident in this role. Another field note appears to suggest and illustrates that football was viewed as being for men and men only:

“Whilst awaiting the teams return to the pitch for the second half, my attention is drawn to the advertising around the stadium. Adverts consist of traditional male activities such as alcohol, plant hire, garage services and cars. No adverts are apparent for products or services that traditionally would appeal to women.” (field note).

We know from Connell (1987) that hegemonic masculinity is defined in terms of culturally normative and influential ideals of masculinity. These culturally normative ideals often emphasise strength, size and power, sexuality (heterosexual). Advertising at the stadium clearly played to this ideal of masculinity. As Messner (2000 p390) notes “A real man is strong, tough, aggressive and above all a winner in what is still a man’s world”. Zotos and Tsihla (2014) argue that that advertising contributes to gender inequality and thereby excludes women and demeans them by promoting “sexism” as valid and acceptable. This is confirmed by Schroeder & Zwick (2004) who note that most ad campaigns invoke gender identity, with this gender identity arriving from the stereotyped iconography of masculinity and femininity. The advertising at the stadium at Burncastle F.C. and in the match day programme depicted traditional masculine roles such as drinking alcohol, gambling, operating heavy machinery that requires strength and power and driving fast cars.

Advertising is key component of performing gender and of ‘doing man’. As Avery (2012) notes, we rely on products and brands to perform our gender. Avery (2012) further notes that the first rule of being a man is to not be like a woman. In fact, real

men must never resemble women, or display strong feminine characteristics. Identifying with products and brands that reinforce this masculine identity for men wards off fears that others will see them as effeminate or gay. Alcohol remains a major element of advertising at Scottish football grounds despite its use inside football stadia being prohibited since a riot broke out at the 1980 Scottish Cup Final leading to the introduction of the Criminal Justice (Scotland) Act 1980. (Robertson, Frank and Jepson 2014)

In Scotland, however, the use of alcohol remains much more prevalent in men and as Lemle & Mishkind (1989) confirm, social drinking is a primary cultural symbol of manliness. The advertising of alcohol (particularly beer) has been described by Towns et al (2012) as promoting the myth that there is one stereotypical form of masculinity. This stereotypical form of masculinity is the form that affirms and confirms men's identity as a man and the identity that men aspire to. As such, alcohol retained its prominence in the lives and development of the young players at Burncastle:

Fraser: "Aye, well I do have vodka every now and then with my pals and stuff, but I wouldn't really say I was like, getting drunk every night and stuff like that. It's more kinda, it's more kinda classed myself as sociable drinker. It's just at a party or something, if I'm with my friends. I normally buy a half-bottle and then I'd drink other stuff because there's normally stuff when you get there. I would never drink before a game, like the night before a game or anything like that but obviously I still go out with my pals and have a few drinks but, I don't think I've ever been like in a real state where I take too much. I think I've only ever been in that real state once or twice on holiday when it's offseason and stuff".

Alan: "Like, I'll go out with my pals during the season and I'll have a few drinks especially if it's a party or something or at the weekend, but I'm trying to make sure, never before a game or anything".

Jack: "if I've not got football at the weekend, I'll maybe have a couple of beers. I'm never kind of steaming, it's just a social drink. I never ever do it when I've got a game. If I'm playing a Sunday, I'll never drink the Friday night or Saturday night".

In fact, most of the cohort admitted to consuming alcohol even although some weren't of legal age to purchase alcohol. This cultural symbol appeared to be interwoven into the football culture:

Researcher: "Do you see any linkages between alcohol and football"?

Adam: "Oh, hundreds. Hundreds. 'Cos you see, especially talking with lifestyles, you go out, you get home, you play good, first thing you're thinking is 'I want to celebrate' I want to celebrate that. So as soon as you go out, especially as you turn 18 and that, it's easy to go to places with alcohol, drink, get bloated and no' remember anything".

Whilst many of these young players had not yet reached the age at which it is legal to purchase alcohol (although some had), the use of alcohol featured in their initiation into manhood and their development into becoming real men. Clayton and Humberstone (2006) recognise the significant impact that alcohol plays as a social element in sport.

Gambling is another activity that is traditionally seen as a pastime that relates more to men rather than women, according to Cassidy (2014), with betting shops in particular being seen as a man's world. Gambling adverts often portray sexualised images of women in bikinis adopting provocative poses (McKenzie, Bugden, Webster, and Barr,

2018). By its nature, gambling promotes risk taking and taking chances. Indeed the players in this study often reported going to the 'bookies' on a Saturday afternoon, betting on horses and dogs (since betting on football is outlawed by the football authorities) and boasting when a win was achieved:

Derek: "Got kicked out of the bookies yesterday, was in there from opening and got kicked out when it closed."

Alan: "how much cost you"?

Derek: "I went in with ten pounds though I had to go out to visit the bank machine a few times."

(Field note)

Becoming a man for these young men encompassed several elements that included the maintenance of an environment where women were excluded, with men playing the key roles. This was an environment where the idealised male was promoted and celebrated and traditional male pastimes could be undertaken

Sexual Objectification

We have illustrated that Scottish football continues to be a game by men for men by isolating and excluding women and by ensuring that women remain peripheral to the game. This environment sets the context and framework in which the young men in this study become men. However, becoming a man is much more than the environment in which hegemonic masculinity is performed. Fundamental to and central to the construction of hegemonic masculinity is the affirmation and confirmation of heterosexuality. Furthermore, in confirming heterosexuality, the construction of hegemonic masculinity requires that women exist as potential sexual objects for men

(Donaldson 1993). For the young men in this study, asserting heterosexuality and objectifying women as sexual objects was a significant factor to them becoming a man:

“Hey boays my da says I can go on holiday myself this year”.

“Where you going? Malia”?

“Nah he won't let me go there but somewhere with loads of minge though ha ha ha.” (field note)

The above comment, overheard prior to a training session, illustrates that a main consideration of booking a summer holiday was the presence of women. Additionally, the language used implies that sex will be the main pursuit whilst on holiday. Whilst confirming heterosexuality is fundamental and central to hegemonic masculinity, it is useful at this stage to remind ourselves of how hegemonic masculinity is defined. Connell (1987 p185) reminds us that hegemonic masculinity is "the maintenance of practices that institutionalise men's dominance over women". In institutionalising men's dominance over women the objectification of them enables the young men to not only confirm and maintain these practices but also to distance themselves from other subordinated masculinities such as homosexuality and femininity. When advised by the coach that a number of 'bookings' by referees had resulted in a ban for the next game. Scott responded,

“Does this mean if I can't play that I need to come to the game as I'd rather be in bed spooning a wee burd” (Field note)

In other words, he was publically stating that unexpected free time away from football would be spent having sex with a young woman. In objectifying women, language used by the young men was important. Words like girl or woman were seldom heard

and the use of the term 'burd' was used regularly thereby viewing women as inferior and as sexual objects. Clayton and Humberstone (2006) also note this objectification of women as confirmation and affirmation of heterosexuality by male football players engaging in explicit discussion specifically about breasts or other desired sexual organs and relating fantasies about sexual domination of these women. Clayton and Humberstone (2006) further highlighted women being described as 'it' or 'that' thereby making clear distinctions between masculinity and femininity and devaluing femininities. Women who do not fit the idealised sexual object and are therefore considered unattractive are seen as having no value in the construction of their masculine identities (Clayton and Humberstone 2006) as this conversation overheard at a training session outlines:

"A heard you shagged that dog Hazel on Saturday"

"Naw a fuckin didnae. Who said that"?

"She's pals wae (name not clear) and she told her that you did". (Field note)

Here, the use of the word 'dog' to describe Hazel devalues her femininity by likening her to an animal as she is deemed unattractive and therefore does not fit with the masculine identity.

For these young men, the confirmation and affirmation of heterosexuality was often publically confirmed. On another occasion as players were arriving for training being dropped off by parents or occasionally driving themselves one player emerged from a car driven by a young female. Another player was overheard remarking to an assembled group who had arrived earlier:

“Fuck sake, check her out! Is that [players name] burd? What’s she doing with that ugly cunt? She’s no shaggin him surely? Aye, that’s [player’s name’s] burd, crackin pair of tits on her...ha ha ha ”” (Field note)

These examples of public affirmation of hegemony ties with West and Zimmerman, (1987 p140) assertion that,

“A person’s gender is not simply an aspect of what one is, but, more fundamentally, it is something that one does, and does recurrently, in interaction with others”.

We have demonstrated consistently and more importantly that gender is not dichotomous and is not biologically determined but created through social interaction. As Sallee and Harris III (2011 p413) put it,

“Gender is not a characteristic inherent in an individual; rather, people collaborate to produce gender”.

The public affirmation and confirmation of heterosexuality illustrates this collaboration in performing hegemonic masculinity:

Ian: “Was at Laura’s [second name] party the other night”.

James: “Good night”?

Ian: “Aye, nipped [dated] that wee burd Ashley” [second name].

Paul: “Did ye shag her”?

Ian: “Aye”.

Scott: “You never shagged that wee burd, you don’t have a fuckin shag in you”.

Richardson (2010) confirms that in becoming a man, having sex with women is crucial and central for the transition to manhood much like our first section illustrated. Richardson (2010) further crucially observes, however, that having sex provided more social pleasure with the physical pleasure associated with sex being minimal. For these young men the physical act of sex is not the main item of pleasure, it is the social pleasure that they get by discussing the act. This sexualised discourse, according to Clayton and Humberstone (2006), cements the fraternal bond and allows for the confirmation of status by the disassociation of women to disembodied sexual objects thereby marking the clear distinctions between femininity and masculinity. Even although Parker (1996) reminds us that in the world of professional football heterosexuality is taken for granted, it may be that according to Swain (2000) the confirmation of heterosexuality is important due to fear that failure to confirm heterosexuality could leave the individual open to a suggestion that his heterosexuality is in some way absent or he is in fact is gay:

“A group of young females has wondered around the pitch and have stopped to observe. I notice that the players whilst still participating in their training exercise are making comments to each other whilst glancing over to the young women. It’s become obvious to me that the young women have noticed this as they too are now commenting to each other and are now taking an interest in the training. As the young women eventually move away there are several eyes following their departure”. (field note)

In collaborating to produce gender, this is further demonstrated in the following where a woman was actively engaged in the match rather than the usual peripheral role that women usually or normally play in Scottish football. Whilst the young men were

changing for a match, the researcher offered to deliver the team lines to the referee. On being advised by the coach that the referee was a female and that the researcher should knock before entering the referee's room Paul observed:

“Fuck sake, the referees a burd? that means I cannae fuckin' swear”. (field note)

These perceived qualities of femininity determined that the young man would have to regulate his language on the football field for fear of offending the sensitivity of the woman official. This woman despite holding a position of authority in the game as referee was objectified and was seen as weaker, more passive, and sensitive. Bird (1996) contests that not only does social interaction produces hegemonic masculinity but in fact allows for its maintenance since it suppresses behaviours associated with non-hegemonic masculinity identities, whilst behaviours that relate to hegemonic masculinity are maintained.

Conclusion

This chapter outlined, explored and examined the ways in which the men negotiated masculine positional identity where orthodox notions of sexuality were reproduced within this football school of masculinity. Not only were women often deliberately excluded but were further objectified and demeaned by overt displays of misogynistic language and behaviours towards them. This exclusion of women allowed the young men to affirm separation from the 'other', and maintained football as a male only preserve within which men were safe to engage with and participate in other traditional male activities such as gambling and alcohol use which were promoted and encouraged via advertising within the football stadium

CHAPTER 9: CONCLUSION

Introduction

The central objective of this thesis was to explore the realities of how young footballers use the game to construct a narrow idealised form of masculinity by an examination of their experiences with it. By drawing on the concept of hegemonic masculinity devised by Connell (1987) the thesis sought to understand and make sense of how this particular masculinity was constructed and performed by these players. Utilising ethnographic methods of research involving participant observation over the course of a season within a Scottish Professional football club, as well as semi-structured interviews conducted with 15 young players, the findings of the study suggested that as Parker (2006) observed players were socialised into a restrictive, hierarchical and authoritarian male dominated occupational culture where they are taught by the gendered routines of the sporting world that they inhibit to accept the values associated with it such as toughness and aggression.

From the players' testimonies, it was also clear that on signing for a professional club either Burcastle or another, the process of the player's socialisation into the culture of football began at an early age via male family members and the pursuit of a professional career became all-consuming where opportunities for formal education in school or elsewhere were rejected.

Discussion

Despite increasing attempts to attract women to football within Scotland, figures obtained by the researcher via personal email correspondence from one of the two big

Glasgow clubs reveals that only around 12% of season ticket holders are female. With the publicity surrounding the re-emergence of Glasgow as a city on the rise and the promotion of Glasgow as a destination for top quality food, entertainment and shopping plus the extensive marketing of the top two Glasgow clubs' top stars with experience in European leagues and internationally, it is perhaps somewhat surprising that more of what Gulianotti (1995b) refer to as flaneurs are not attracted to the game. Sensing the opportunities available in a sector that has to compete with others in the entertainment field, Scottish professional football does on the face of it seek to encourage women and girls to the game. With pink scarves for the supporters plus numerous girls and ladies teams available across the professional game, plus women now represented in the boardroom this, one would assume, be the springboard for increasing engagement and attendance and increased recognition of women in the professional game particularly as overall attendances in the Scottish professional game are on the rise.

Whilst the Scottish Professional Football League (SPFL) for men consists of 42 members split over four leagues as outlined in an earlier chapter, its female counterpart the Scottish Women's Premier League (SWPL) - the highest level of league competition in women's football in Scotland - consists of only 16 teams competing over 2 leagues with little or no professional status (Scottish Building Society Scottish Women's Premier League, 2017). Scottish Professional football ultimately remains predominately a game played by men and for men. This is unsurprising given the masculine discourses that surround Scottish professional football. Whilst no doubt some flaneurs will be attracted to the highly paid, promoted foreign stars of Glasgow's two big clubs, the majority of Scottish football is played in the post-industrial

hinterlands where heavy industry once reigned supreme. Where the coal that powered the industry was mined, where the steel that built the economy was forged and the ships were built to transport and trade with the rest of the world were launched.

Burncastle FC is such a club. Formed in the nineteenth century during this industrial revolution, the club continues to draw its players and supporters from this post-industrial hinterland with its legacy of a strong working class masculine culture steeped in the former heavy industries of coal mining and textile production. As I outlined in a previous section, heavy industry in the area is now a thing of the past, unemployment is higher than the national average with much of the local area now being redeveloped to act as a commuter belt for Glasgow.

Whilst much has been written on the construction of masculinity within the sport of football, most of the focus in Scotland has been on the fans of the game. (Giulianotti 1994, 1995a, 1995b, 2007, 2008). Little has been written concerning gender identity and the construction of masculinity within the professional game itself due in part to what Parker and Manley (2017) identify as the restrictive nature of the professional football culture; Parker (2006) and Parker and Manley, (2017) do, however, provide significant insight into elite professional football in England. Whilst these two important studies provide some indicators, Parker (2006) further highlights that whilst general features are identified that contribute to the construction of hegemonic masculinity, each institution will exhibit its own specific brand of hegemonic masculinity based upon particular contextual traits, characteristics and nuances.

Whilst professional football in England has 116 professional football teams split over five divisions (Premier league, English football league – 3 divisions- and the National league), professional football in Scotland consists of 42 teams over four divisions. Whilst all teams in the top four divisions in England are fully professional, only the top division in Scotland contains teams that are fully professional. Burncastle FC, whilst a fully professional team, has never played in Scotland's Premier league and therefore the professional youth academy does not satisfy the definition of an elite club academy defined by Parker and Manley (2017) and Roberts, Anderson and Magrath (2017), where the players are all full time professional, and play in the top division. It is against this background that the particular contextual traits, characteristics and nuances of hegemonic masculinity is constructed within the football club (Connell 2005; Parker and Manley, 2017).

Utilising Connell's (1987) theoretical model of multiple masculinities, this study recognised throughout that gender identity (masculinity) is developed through a complex process of interaction with culture and environment that develops and changes as society changes and develops. As noted earlier, Burncastle FC draws its players from communities where the ideas, customs, and social behaviour of the people has changed over a relatively short period of time. The local environment surrounding the club has changed significantly over the past 20/30 years. The game itself has also changed significantly with the impact of globalisation and the production of football superstars and financial rewards that for many people are unachievable in a lifetime of employment, (Buraimo and Simmons 2015). The complexity of the environment, the change and developments within society and the localised community will inevitably produce particular gender identities, therefore it is

unsurprising that there exists multiple masculinities. This study however sought to identify how an idealised form of masculinity is constructed and to identify this complex interaction.

Following challenge and critique by Demetriou (2001), the concept of hegemonic masculinity was re-examined and redefined by Connell and Messerschmidt (2005). In their response, they reaffirm that fundamentally central to the concept of hegemonic masculinity is a plurality of masculinities. This study has confirmed that the multiple masculinities evident and prevalent at Burncastle FC were the socially dominant masculinities based on cultural consent, institutionalisation and the disregard and often contempt shown for other masculinities. In addition, Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) confirm that hegemonic masculinity need not be the commonest pattern in the everyday lives of boys and men. Indeed, in this study it was often other socially dominant masculinities that, via the actions and language of the young players, were the commonest pattern. These socially dominant masculinities such as toxic, and complicit masculinities provided the maintenance of the patriarchal dividend. However football by the provision of exemplars who are celebrated as heroes and symbols that have authority and by the act of participation in professional sport confirms hegemony since professional sport is in itself a hegemonic masculine practice within Western societies (Connell and Messerschmidt 2005).

This study concludes therefore that whilst hegemonic masculinity is constructed in relation to subordinated masculinities and exists as a hierarchy of masculinities, the current practices within Burncastle FC evidence and demonstrate socially dominant masculinities. These masculinities lend themselves to the configuration of practices

that contribute to the subordination of women and the maintenance of the current system of patriarchy. The club and its culture act as a school of hegemony that through its practices socialises boys and young men into the idealised form of masculinity and teaches them to become 'real men' by preparing them for a world of hegemonic masculinity.

The study sought to answer two key questions

1. How is masculinity constructed and performed in the lives of young professional footballers within the context of one professional club?
2. What implications are there in terms of how football contributes to the construction of masculinity in Scotland?

For the young men in this study, all of whom were from post-industrial working class families, their schooling in the idealised form of masculinity commenced the same way that many working class males are schooled in masculinity via engagement by male family members on the highly masculinised sport of football. With Messner (1992) reminding us that boys are judged depending on their ability (or lack thereof) in competitive sport, football with its continuing imagery of the footballer as the 'iconic' idealised aspirational male (Clark & Paechter 2007), football is the obvious choice for families in which to instruct their children. These young men were enrolled in football very early in their lives with most of them often too young to recall the first engagement. For these young men, football was just something that they did, to follow in the footsteps of uncles, fathers, grandfathers, brothers, and male cousins. To emulate them, to perhaps perform better than them or even to 'make up' for the failings of male

relatives that prevented progression in football such as alcohol problems or injury. To follow the family tradition.

Football for these young men was unquestionably a male pursuit. It was male family members that first introduced the game informally at a young age, it was male family members who introduced them to their first team, and it was male family members who waited as they trained and who critiqued or praised performance. Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) remind us that hegemonic masculinity is more than an identity or a set of role expectations. Hegemonic masculinity is a pattern of practice that allows and sustains men's dominance over women. This pattern of practice is only hegemonic when women are involved as this idealised form is always constructed in relation to women. This study has demonstrated the deliberate exclusion of women from the game and where women were involved, they were kept on the periphery of the game. Even at this early stage of a child's development, females, the traditional care givers, are excluded from this social activity being reduced to traditional female gender roles of care giving to other siblings or providing food and refreshments to players, coaches and spectators.

When females had a participative role in the view of respondents it was to present the idealised imagery of women. It is this emphasised femininity that is portrayed via the teen cheerleaders in their miniskirts with gymnastic displays and dance routines purely for the entertainment of men prior to and during the main event itself. Even when women had key roles in the game such as a referee their profile was reduced to that of a vulnerable individual. Women were objectified and viewed purely by some of the participants as sex objects. Young men were celebrated and venerated and gained

position in the group by demonstrations of heterosexuality. Sexual conquests were celebrated and some free time away from football was for the pursuit of women and sex.

This study, whilst predominantly investigating the production and performance of hegemonic masculinity, examined and identified a number of masculinities that were produced and performed that surrounded the football club. Masculinities that are the most socially dominant were particularly evident. As the football club does not sit in isolation from its community and the players are drawn from this community, performances and reproductions of masculinity are interchangeable and were set against this complex relationship of club, community, society, culture and environment.

The production and performance of other socially dominant masculinities were taught and permitted and contributed to and sat alongside the construction and performance of hegemony. These socially dominant forms such as this toxic form of masculinity (Kupers 2005) was reproduced and performed frequently in the communities where the players lived. Toxicity was further in evidence via the songs sung by supporters resplendent with imagery of war and violence in an attempt to encourage and motivate the team. In addition, this toxicity was further reproduced via the misogynistic narrative that reduced women to sex objects (burds) or by reference to sexual organs (minge), for 'shagging' (having sex), thereby demeaning them and subordinating them in order that players were able to confirm their place within the gender order by the celebration of their heterosexuality.

The school of masculinity promoted that being 'hard' and 'tough' are key skills to learn. Hardness and toughness were promoted and encouraged with images of war and

violence. A will to win and all costs via promotion of a commitment to the challenge even when it may result in a broken limb. Heroes and exemplars both within and out with the club exhibited this toughness evidenced by the selection of players that participants sought to emulate. The hard man imagery of the bandaged head wound or the bleeding leg wound and the 'never say die' attitude were resplendent and in evidence around the club. Being tough like the young men in the study by Lawson (2013) was also evident in the tough narrative used by the young players. Swearing was extremely common in communication among team members and swear words that are often deemed most culturally offensive were regularly used. This tough masculinity narrative was taught throughout the club in the dressing room pre match, at half time, at full time and in coaching sessions.

Whether tough, toxic or complicit, the constructions of gender identity prevalent in this study are in my opinion evidence the construction of the hegemonic form of masculinity that the school of masculinity that the club instilled within these young men. It is in the context of this summation and the forgoing chapters that we outline the recommendations for policy, practice and future research.

Implications for Policy and Practice

This study identified the maintenance, production and reproduction of hegemonic masculinity in one Scottish professional football club. Furthermore, it identified that hegemonic masculinity was always constructed in relation to subordinated masculinities within that club. Whilst this study was small scale, and defined to one professional club there may be some insights that could have implications for wider football clubs in Scotland. This study therefore concluded that in seeking to challenge

hegemony and the current system of patriarchy more requires to be done. Whilst there are implications for change in practice at a ground level, policy changes are also required at a strategic level. This and the following sections will outline the changes required in order to make football more inclusive and challenge the current hegemony.

Football in Scotland administered via the Scottish Football Association (SFA) as the governing body of football in Scotland with the ultimate responsibility for the control and development of football in Scotland currently only recognises binary gender identity via men's football and women's football. No consideration is currently given within the rules for players who are transsexual, transgender, intersex, questioning or non-binary. The failure to recognise other constructions of gender identity inevitably leads to the isolation and therefore the subordination of these constructions within the game. But it is the exclusion of women from the elite game that remains the biggest single issue in Scottish football.

This study has illustrated that hegemony is maintained, performed and constructed by the practice of the deliberate exclusion of women from the elite professional and upper levels of the game. Scottish Football Association rules currently prohibit males and females fifteen years of age and older from playing in the same team. No rule exists that prohibits males and females playing in the same team aged fourteen years and younger. Burncastle FC has no mixed teams and has separate girls' teams at aged 7, 9, 11, 13 and boys teams at 9, 11, 13, 14. England currently allow mixed teams until eighteen years of age and across the North Sea in Denmark, no upper age limit exists for mixed teams. It is therefore unclear and with no apparent rationale surrounding this apparent arbitrary separation of girls and boys that policy makers should consider the

introduction of mixed teams and consider a review of the fifteen years of age rule that prohibits these mixed teams. The existing rules and regulations around coaching also appear confusing and exclusionary. From an early age (aged 7) children are streamed into separate developmental pathways. The first pathway, children and youth is for male children and the second pathway girls is for girls. The developmental pathways are very similar in their processes and structure. It is therefore unclear, as to why girls are treated separately and differently to boys. This study has demonstrated that coaching at Burncastle FC was skills based. Practice drills predominantly focussed on ball skills such as ball control, passing and precision. Warm up fitness regimes were aerobic in nature such as laps of track and muscle stretching exercises. No training exercises were observed where physical strength or physical power was a pre requisite of participation.

Therefore further research requires to be done to help players and fans reconceptualise masculinity to be more inclusive and less hegemonic. Whilst removing the arbitrary rules around mixed teams and having equality and equity within developmental pathways would go some way to integration and the sense of females as 'others' much more can and should be done. This study, for example, illustrated via observation and with reference to the academic literature how female match officials are viewed and are treated. Scottish football should therefore seek to increase the number of female referees and match officials particularly at the in order to normalise females within the game and thereby reducing the perception of 'outsiders' or 'otherness'. Increased participation, either via playing the game, or by officiating will increase the visibility of females and thereby hopefully reduce the perception outlined within the literature of this thesis that football is a game by men for men. The

recommendation of this study is that coupled with the removal of the arbitrary rules around developmental pathways and mixed teams, the Scottish Football Association engages in a visible large scale recruitment campaign to encourage and support increased female participation into the game. This, however, should be coupled with increased action around attracting female spectators. This thesis outlined by reference to the literature that following the introduction of all seater stadia, there was an increase in the number of females attending on match days. Within Scotland however, outside of the top division there are few stadia that are all seater. Whilst the provision of all seater stadia across Scotland may be cost prohibitive particularly for smaller provincial clubs, much more requires to be done to make the game more female friendly and thereby encouraging more females to attend.

This thesis notes that a study has been commissioned by the Scottish Football Supporters Association (SFSA), a voluntary organisation funded by donations from fans and other interested parties seeking the views of female spectators in relation to their participation in the game. It is recommended that the findings of this study are published and are acted upon. Despite this ongoing study, this thesis noted via observation that football stadia remain highly masculinised arenas where homophobic language continues to be used. Songs that conjure imagery of war continue to be sung. Pre-match entertainment, and half time entertainment is sexualised by teen cheerleaders in short skirts. Advertising within the stadium is directed at men. Policy makers should therefore consider the physical environment that is the stadium itself in order to further increase the levels of female spectators attending Scottish Football matches.

Policy and practice are often interlinked and the practice reflects the policy and vice versa. As illustrated elsewhere in this thesis, training nights at Burncastle FC professional youth training consisted predominantly of ball skills, passing and spatial awareness. This study therefore contends that with no regulatory barriers existing to prohibit mixed teams under the age of fifteen years of age mixing teams begins to address the separation of binary gender football and the exclusion of women from the elite game. Additionally, no rules exist at all that prohibits male and female players training together developing skills and tactics together. The mixing of teams at all levels, further recognises and is inclusive of those whose gender identity is non binary.

Throughout the game, women and girls are excluded. At elite levels, the SFA has 32 grade one referees. These referees have the authority via the SFA to referee at all Scottish Football games. Via nomination by the SFA grade one referees are further authorised to referee games in Europe administered by the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA) as the governing body of European football. Furthermore, grade one Scottish referees also have the authority to referee international matches administered by The Fédération Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) as the governing body of world football and the organiser of The World Cup. No women as of May 2018 are currently on the SFA grade one referee list. We noted earlier that there exists sixteen senior women's teams in Scotland with most but not all linked to a corresponding senior male team. Despite these linkages the women do not share the same stadia as the men and are on the whole relegated to play matches in amateur stadiums or at community venues. Not only are women's matches played away from the home of the senior team but training is also conducted separately away from the training facilities used by the men's teams. For some senior

clubs in Scotland, these training facilities are state of the art but are inaccessible for women players.

My recommendations for policy and practice have so far focussed on increasing participation of females but we further make recommendations concerning this participation. My observations at Burncastle FC noted that aggression, anger, toughness and 'hardness' was coached and encouraged. Players readily accepted as part of the game being shouted at and sworn at. Misogynistic behaviours are unchallenged and accepted by coaches and within the peer group. It is therefore recommended that codes of conduct regarding language are drawn up as part of overall acceptable behaviour within the game. The practices observed within Burncastle FC sought to school these young men in forms of hegemonic masculinity that is currently the socially acceptable custom and practice that is deemed essential to currently playing the game in Scotland. Reducing and discouraging the type of masculine construction evident at Burncastle FC requires change at an operational and ultimately strategic level where such practices become less common and are readily and regularly challenged.

Limitations and Future Research

In recognising the limitations of this study, I reassert that it takes place within a particular football club with a particular group of young men during one particular football season, it did not set out to study or understand the women's game in Scotland, especially how their gender identity is constructed and performed in a highly

masculinised sport. Hence the lack of focus in this thesis on female players. It is useful here to recall and note the study by Jeanes (2011) who found that far from creating opportunities for women to construct and perform alternative feminine gender identities, football limited women by the need to look feminine by cultivating an idealised slim body and by the dominant feminine discourses. As women's football in Scotland has grown recently, a further study into emphasised femininity in football in Scotland would provide additional research data on the specific role of football in constructing gender identity.

This study in examining the construction of the idealised form of masculinity as well as not examining or addressing gender construction in women did not seek to address or indeed examine the role of other subordinated masculinities within football or how other masculinities outwith those most socially dominant are produced, negotiated and performed in football. More specifically, gay masculinities within the game were not under consideration nor was the impact of homophobia considered even although a homophobic chant was observed at a Burncastle FC match. Given the limitations of this study, further research is therefore suggested specifically:

How does hegemony within the game football impact on LGBTQI players and supporters?

What barriers exist for LGBTQI players and supporters in accessing football?

Football, including its culture and the environment in which it exists, continues to remain a site for the performance of the idealised form of masculinity. Football

continues to contribute to the perception of a natural order of gender via the recognition of a binary gender order with roles being naturally defined or given. There is therefore no obvious place in football for other masculinities such as those who are transgender, transsexual or intersex that are alternative to or challenge the idealised form. Practically, attempts are ongoing across world football to address the toxic impact of racist activity in football. A report by the Equality and Human Rights Commission in England (2017) that evaluated the UK's anti-racism educational charity *Show Racism the Red Card* which uses football to help tackle racism in society showed significant declines in prejudice against black and minority ethnic communities and individuals. A similar programme to use football to tackle homophobia by promoting the use among players of rainbow laces (The Guardian 2013) for football boots was discussed earlier in this thesis as was the failure of the campaign to garner any level of support among the football clubs themselves.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study identified the exclusionary and stigmatising actions and behaviours towards women in a Scottish professional football team. It concludes by proposing the promotion, recognition and permitting the expression of multiple masculinities within football. This should be done in such a way that other masculinities will become constructive and attractive alternatives to the traditional real-man image of hegemonic masculinity will emerge. In encouraging multiple masculinities, then equity of gender and an end to domination and subordination may be a real possibility.

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Interview Schedule

Demographics

Tell me about yourself, age, home, family etc,

Initiation

How did you get into football? Who took you? Why?

What was your first game like?

Football subculture

Can you describe your life as a footballer?

Are there any initiation rituals you go through when you first join a club?

Can you tell me about rituals or antics that go on at the club?

How does football impact other areas of your life?

What does it mean to be involved in a team?

How important has football been in your life?

How would you feel if you got injured and couldn't play for 12 months/anymore?

How would you feel if it was all taken away from you?

When you win what is it like in the change room after a game?

When you lost what is it like in the change room after a game?

How emotional is the game of football?

How acceptable is it for men to show their emotions on the football field?

Alcohol use

Do you use alcohol?

How often?

How much?

Is alcohol use and football compatible? If so, why? If not why?

Male Body

How would you describe your body?

What do you like best about your body?

What do you like least about your body?

Masculinity

How would you describe masculinity?

Do you think of yourself as masculine?

Do you think there are certain characteristics that are manly/masculine?

Are there any characteristics that you think are not masculine?

What do you think influences what it means to be masculine in today's Western culture? (Explore in relation to media)

What do you think the male role in society is?

What do you think the female role in society is?

Who do you think is the most masculine footballer playing in the SPFL? Why?

What does the typical masculine man look like?

How would you describe yourself as a person?

What influences your identity?

How does football create masculine identity?

How does football reinforce masculine identity?

Can you describe if and how the media impacts on your feelings of masculinity?

What affects your self-esteem?

How do you think others would perceive you?

How do you perceive yourself as a person?

How has playing football influenced your masculinity?

Participant Information Sheet: players of Burncastle Football Club**Name of department:**

School of Education

Title of the study:

An ethnography of masculinity in male football players

Introduction

My name is Liam Wells and I am a research student at the University of the West of Scotland

What is the purpose of this investigation?

As a sport described by many as Scotland's favourite sport, football plays an important role in the development of many young men. It is thought that it shapes and develops their character and is an important factor in assisting young men to construct and recognise their gender identity.

The University of The West of Scotland has arranged this study In order to discover and further understand the role of football in shaping the characteristics of young men.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been *invited to take part* in this study because as a male involved in football you will have experience of what being a footballer is all about and what it means to be a professional football player

Do you have to take part?

You do not have to take part in the study, and even if you do agree to take part, you may withdraw at any time. If you do decide to withdraw, you can be assured that any data collected up to the point of withdrawal will be destroyed. Participating or not participating in the study will not affect your relationship with other players or coaches. If you decide to take part in this study then you should let me know during my early visits to the football club

What will you do in the project?

During the study you will be invited to talk to me informally about:

- Your views on what it means to be a male in 21st Century Scotland.

- Your relationship with football and the role it plays in your life
- What you understand about masculinity
- How masculinity and football are related
- Your future ambitions in relation to progression within the game

There might be some questions that make you feel uncomfortable. You absolutely do not need to answer any question like that. The interviewer may when asking a particular question ask you if you are comfortable with that one. You can be assured that information passed on during the interviews will remain confidential.

If you agree to participate in this study, I will ask you to take part in an interview which will be audio-taped. You do not have to take part in the study, and even if you do agree, you may withdraw at any time.

What happens to the information in the project?

The findings from this study may be published in various places, including journal articles and reports. However, your name will never be mentioned and all participants who take part will remain anonymous. You can be assured that the name of the football club or the name of the local community will not be used in any written reports arising from the study. The information that you provide us with will be kept for six months before being destroyed in keeping with the requirements outlined with the General Data Protection Requirements (GDPR)

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

What happens next?

If you are happy to be involved in the project, you should sign your name on the form below. If you do not want to be involved in the project then I would like to thank you for your attention. After the investigation has been completed, I will forward a report to the football club to provide you with feedback from the study.

This investigation was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee.

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Extracts of Raw Data

Field notes

Given it appears that our head coach is happy to leave the fitness training to the 'new' coach I take the opportunity to discuss the changes with him and learn that our previous assistant coach has left to take up an assistant manager/player role with a local junior side and the missing player has joined him at the junior side on loan. I further learn that the 'new' coach was previously a coach with the 17's and has moved up temporarily to the 19's.

I sense that as in all walks of life, management decisions are often unpopular but it seems that players and coaches despite the short mumblings of discontent have just accepted the regime change and the imposed training regime.

As we are chatting, another of the regular players joins us dressed in 'normal' clothing as opposed to his training gear. I'm interested in why he is late for training and not kitted out since being on time for training seems to be a key requisite. Additionally as a paid player of the club and one who has been singled out for particular criticism in the past around performances then it seems strange. Initially it would appear that he is injured which appeases my curiosity but I learn quickly that the explanation of injury is not the full explanation. In fact, it now appears that due to poor performances that the player explains through an unrecognised injury, the club management has decided to terminate his youth contract and release him from the club. The coach makes it clear that when he is fit, he is still welcome to play for the club and he would still be available for selection, but given the decision of management he would not however be available to play for the first team. As the player leaves – probably for the last time – the coach unhappily notes that an eighteen year old boys footballing future has been decided

As the training game ends, we are called in and it's noted that several of the players are on 'yellow cards' going into the final few games of the season. It appears that further bookings will result in match bans.

"see if you're banned" one player enquires "does that mean you don't have to go to the game?" "coz you'd find me tucked up in bed spooning a coupla wee burds oan a Sunday!"

Much hilarity ensues with the player reminded that a match ban does not mean a long lie on a Sunday. "you'll just be playing under a different name" the coach assures him. I'm not sure whether the coach is actually planning on breaking the rules but as the player in question is a senior player then it's more than likely

With our spirits lifted, we arrive at the stadium to discover that we are not playing in the stadium but on one of the pitches outside the stadium. Whilst there are no overt statements of disappointment, I sense from previous games played in a stadium that the players enjoy the experience of playing in the stadiums despite often playing to spectators numbering in the single figures. However, if it's any consolation, we get to use the stadium changing facilities unlike the general public who use the adjoining sports facility.

Once changed, it's team talk time and after the now familiar line up starting positions we are reminded of the importance of a victory if we are to proceed in the competition.

It's now time to head out for our warm up— a warm up in its truest sense as the sleet swirls round the open pitch. I'm wrapped in hat, scarf, gloves and padded rain jacket whilst the players are in short sleeves and shorts. I take the opportunity to raise the

question as to whether football should be a Summer sport and my question is met with a look to the sky and a laugh

Interview data

Do you think it's okay, or is it accept- or how acceptable or how okay is it for men to show emotion on a football field. On the field itself- no in the dressing room- on the field.

Big so it is, a lot of men won't show emotion off the field but when they're on the field they're a completely different person.

Why? Why do you think that is?

Though determination to win. If they don't win they're disappointed in themselves.

Okay, so individual emotions, y'know, anger. So anger's okay on a football field?

Mmm, yeah, if you get all different emotions really. Anger's one of the main ones. You get angry at the people with bad tackles or not doing something right. That's just on the field and not off the field.

Right. What about, y'know, on the field- you've just lost the cup final, for example or you've lost a last minute goal to lose the cup final, y'know. Sadness on a football field- is that okay?

Aye.

Kinda thinking about, y'know, Paul Gascoigne and crying and stuff when they didn't qualify for the world cup- is that okay to show emotion?

Acceptable – you understand it more than you understand if off the pitch.

So it's different- Why's it different to show emotion on a pitch whereas in- in some other situations you wouldn't do that?

Understand it more and you ken where it's coming fae. Off the pitch ye just have tae ask them, but when you're on the pitch you know what's wrong with them so you don't need to ask them about it.

Do you have any ambitions for football?

I want to play at the highest level. I want to play against all the folk- you see Nessian, Aldon and that on the tele and I want to play against them. They're living their lifestyle. I mean it's amazing.

...What do you mean by that?

They- they're like- they don't- they can- they want for nothing. They can- say they take a fancy to a car, they go buy it. They take a fancy to a house, they go buy it. If they want to go somewhere, so long as it's alright with the manager, they go there. So that's – that kind of living, where you don't have to worry about bills, mortgages, debts where it's basically all done for you because-

So is it about money? Or is it about fame and fortune?

No, no no. It's more about the love of the game, cos I love playing football. But, it's kind of like incentive slash like a plus to playing football more than anything else. It's there and it helps you out, but you still love playing football which is a ..

And is that why you give up what, three nights a week to come to training?

Aye, it's a no brainer. I mean it costs a lot of money to get there, especially if you're no, well some folk, aren't getting paid to play here. It's a lot of money and a lot of time and their parents need to drive them as well, but it's still, it's just football, it's just what everyone wants to do.

I think that you're asking football and stuff, I think one of the main reasons I'm still at football and I'm no drinking is seeing the amount of players that I've played with that've been like double the player I've ever been. They've ended up hitting the drink and an' that.

Why do you think that is?

I don't know. I seriously couldn'ae answer it. I think for my big cousin's sake, he went out one night before a game, probably because his pals were going out. Drinking turned ups his game the next day and someone had grassed him in to his manager. So he got told off and got given another chance but he said 'no, stuff it'. I think that was his getout so he could go out every week. He tells me now that he regrets it and- but I think that it's just, ken when you turn eighteen, everyone's going out and stuff like. All your pals. I think that's a push. You kinda need to choose a pathway. You'll stick to your football and keep working hard and you'll get the rewards later on or just go out and get steaming every weekend.